

**Universidad
Andrés Bello**

**Destino ambiental de los Contaminantes Orgánicos Persistentes
(COP) durante el verano austral en la Antártica.**

**“Environmental fate of Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)
during the austral summer in Antarctica.”**

**Tesis para optar al grado de Doctor en Medicina de la
Conservación**

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Santiago – Chile

Septiembre, 2023

VICERRECTORÍA DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y DOCTORADO

ACTA DEFENSA PÚBLICA PROGRAMA DE DOCTORADO EN MEDICINA DE LA CONSERVACIÓN

En Santiago, el día 08 de septiembre de 2023, en ceremonia solemne se efectúa la defensa pública de la Tesis presentada por la **Srta. Thais Danae Luarte Anduaga** titulada "**Environmental fate of Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) during the austral summer in Antarctica**", como el último requisito para la obtención del grado de Doctora en Medicina de la Conservación de la Universidad Andrés Bello. La comisión examinadora está integrada por su Director de Tesis Dr. Cristóbal Galbán y su Patrocinante Dr. José Pulgar además de los Doctores Mauricio Carter, Elizabeth Garrido, y Rodrigo Orrego.

Esta ceremonia es co-presidida por la Vicerrectora de Investigación y Doctorado, Doctora Carolina Torrealba y por el Decano de la Facultad de Ciencias de la Vida, Doctor Alfredo Molina y la Directora Académica de Doctorados, Doctora Erika Poblete.

Luego de escuchar la defensa de la Tesis expuesta por la Srta. Thais Danae Luarte Anduaga, la comisión ha decidido aprobarla y manifestar sus felicitaciones.

Por lo anterior, se otorga el grado de

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Agradecimientos

En este momento crucial de culminación de mi tesis, quiero expresar mis más sinceros agradecimientos a todas las personas que han sido parte fundamental en este recorrido académico y personal.

En primer lugar, deseo extender mi profundo agradecimiento a mi director de tesis, Cristóbal Galbán. Nuestra colaboración ha sido invaluable desde el año 2017, y su compromiso no solo me brindó la oportunidad de realizar una pasantía en España, sino también de viajar en tres ocasiones al continente antártico. Reconozco su cercanía, paciencia y la generosidad con la que compartió sus conocimientos, lo cual enriqueció tanto la elaboración de mi tesis como la creación de los artículos publicados.

Quiero expresar mi gratitud a José Pulgar, patrocinante de esta tesis, por el constante apoyo brindado durante todo este período. También, agradezco a mi comité evaluador, conformado por Elizabeth Garrido, Rodrigo Orrego y Mauricio Carter, por sus valiosos comentarios y sugerencias que contribuyeron significativamente al refinamiento de mi tesis.

A mi familia, en especial a mi madre, Elizabeth Anduaga, le dedico un agradecimiento sincero por ser mi fuente constante de apoyo en cada paso que he dado. A mis hermanos, Víctor y Paula, y a mis sobrinas, Emilia, Josefa y Alfonsina, les agradezco por su inmenso cariño y por ser un motor de inspiración en mi vida.

No puedo dejar de mencionar a mis compañeros de generación, Carlos Calvo, Camila Dunner y Bárbara Toro, cuya compañía y respaldo hicieron que la experiencia del doctorado fuera aún más enriquecedora y gratificante.

Concluyendo este recorrido de gratitud, deseo ofrecer un sentido reconocimiento a mi padre. Su constante apoyo, cariño, protección y las oportunidades que generosamente me brindó en vida son un legado que sigo llevando conmigo. Aunque ya no está físicamente a mi lado, tengo la certeza de que desde el cielo continúa inspirándome y animándome a perseverar, alcanzando cada meta que me propongo. Este logro lleva consigo el amor y la influencia de su presencia en mi vida, siendo un tributo a su memoria.

En definitiva, a todas estas personas que menciono, y a muchas otras que han influido en mi camino de alguna manera, les dedico mis más sinceros agradecimientos por ser piezas

fundamentales en este logro que hoy celebro. Su contribución ha sido vital para mi crecimiento académico y personal. ¡Gracias!

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List of acronyms

$-\Delta U_{AW}$: Heat of phase change from liquid to gas.

AMAP: Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program

BCF: Bioconcentration factor

CG: POPs concentration in the gas phase

ChlA: Chlorophyll a

LRAT: Long-range Transboundary air pollution

C_{Oct} : POPs concentration associated to octanol

C_P : POPs concentration associated to water particulate matter

C_{Phyto} : POPs associated to phytoplankton

C_{Zoo} : POPs associated to zooplankton

C_W : POPs concentration in the dissolved seawater

C_{TD} : POPs truly dissolved seawater concentration

DDT: dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

DDD: diclorodifenildicloroetano

DDE: diclorodifenildicloroetileno

DOC: Dissolved organic carbon

F_{DegM} : Microbial degradation flux

HCB: Hexachlorobenzene

HCHs: Hexachlorocyclohexanes

HLC: Henry's Law Constant

$f_w f_a^{-1}$: fugacity ratio between the air and water

K_{AW} : Mass transfer coefficient between the air and water

K_{AW} : Air-water partition coefficient

K_{DOC} : Water-dissolved organic carbon partition coefficient.

K_{OA} : Octanol-water partition coefficient

K_{OW} : Octanol-water partition constant.

K_P : Gas-Particle partition constant

PCBs: Polychlorinated biphenyls

POP: Persistent organic pollutant

P_v : Vapour pressure

R: Ideal gas constant

UNEP: United Nations Environmental Programme

S_w : Solubility in water

OCP: Organochlorine Pesticides

S_{Oct} : Solubility in organic matter and octanol

General abstract

This study investigated the environmental fate of Antarctica's persistent organic pollutants (POPs). These anthropogenic compounds are stable, resistant to degradation, and can bioaccumulate in organisms and biomagnify through the food chain. The fate of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the environment depends on their chemical properties and the exchange processes between different compartments. In particular, the air-water exchange is important in aquatic systems, affecting POP levels through atmospheric volatilization and deposition. Once POPs reach the water, they may remain dissolved, volatilize again, or bind to particles such as phytoplankton. These contaminants can follow different environmental pathways, including transfer to higher trophic levels, resulting in biomagnification, export to deep water, and subsequent inclusion in the biological pump. In Antarctica, there needs to be more information on these processes, although the polar regions act as ultimate sinks for POPs. It has been observed that during periods of high productivity, POPs are transferred to sediments due to high biological pump fluxes and accumulation in living organisms. However, previous studies in Antarctica have had limitations in accurately quantifying POP levels due to samples taken at different locations. In addition, the assessment of POP cycling in aquatic systems has been conducted regarding organic carbon, which has left uncertainty about the fate of POPs in the Southern Ocean. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to assess the environmental fate of POPs, such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), during periods of blooms in Antarctica. Simultaneous air, water, phytoplankton, and zooplankton sampling was conducted in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica, from December 2019 to January 2020. Several factors were calculated, such as air-water exchange and bioaccumulation, bioconcentration, and biomagnification factors. In addition, the atmospheric half-life was estimated using characteristic decay times (TD), where we observed that HCB levels in the Antarctic atmosphere were higher than those of the other target OCs. However, HCB also showed greater fluctuations and did not significantly decrease over time.

In contrast, atmospheric levels of HCH and some DDT and PCBs have decreased significantly. The estimated atmospheric half-lives of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) vary by compound. For DDT compounds, the half-lives are 4,4'-DDE (13.5 years), 4,4'-DDD (12.8 years), and 4,4'-DDT (7.4 years). For HCH compounds, the half-lives are 2,4'-DDE (6.4 years), 2,4'-DDT (6.3 years), α -HCH (6 years), HCB (6 years), and γ -HCH (4.2 years). For PCB congeners, half-lives decrease in the following order: PCB 153 (7.6 years), PCB 138 (6.5 years), PCB 101 (4.7 years), PCB 180 (4.6 years), PCB 28 (4 years), PCB 52 (3.7 years) and PCB 118 (3.6 years). These estimates show the persistence of POPs in the atmosphere and their ability to remain in the environment for long periods. In the case of HCH isomers and PCBs, the ban on POPs imposed by the Stockholm Convention has reduced their levels in recent decades. However, their ubiquity in the Antarctic atmosphere shows the problems associated with highly persistent synthetic chemicals. The results showed that hexachlorobenzene (HCB) was the most abundant compound in air and water. Significant concentrations of PCB 11 were also found in air and seawater. The estimated fugacity gradient for PCB compounds indicates a predominance of net atmospheric deposition for HCB, α -HCH, γ -HCH, 4,4'-DDDT, 4,4'-DDE, and close to equilibrium for the compound PeCB. The observed deposition of some OCs may be due to high biodegradation rates and sedimentation fluxes contributing to the decrease of these compounds in surface waters, supported by the measured ability of the microbial consortium to degrade some of these compounds. Estimated fugacity gradients for PCBs showed differences between congeners, with net volatilization predominating for PCB-9, a trend close to

equilibrium for PCB congeners 11, 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, and 153, and deposition for PCB 180. Snow amplification may play an essential role in decreasing PCBs in surface waters. Snow amplification may play an important role in less hydrophobic PCBs, with volatilization predominating after snow/glacier melting. As hydrophobicity increases, the biological pump decreases the concentration of PCBs in seawater, reversing the fugacity gradient toward atmospheric deposition.

Finally, regarding the levels detected in plankton, we recorded high concentrations of HCB in phytoplankton and of the congener PCB 11 in zooplankton, elucidating for the first time the presence of this congener in Antarctic biota high concentrations. On the other hand, BCF and BAF estimates of OCP and PCB show a direct and significant linear relationship with Log KOW, evidencing a trend of equilibrium or near equilibrium between water and phytoplankton and between water and zooplankton, respectively. BAF and BCF values were in a similar range, indicating that, in this study, zooplankton did not accumulate POPs from phytoplankton grazing, in agreement with the BMF values obtained, where most of the analyzed compounds show values lower than 1, indicating no or low biomagnification. According to the results, an effective and significant transfer of OCPs and PCBs from water to phytoplankton and from water to zooplankton was obtained. However, there was no effective and significant transfer between phytoplankton and zooplankton.

Overall, the study highlights the importance of continued monitoring, regulating atmospheric sources, and understanding the environmental fate of POPs in Antarctica. Coordinated efforts are needed among countries with an Antarctic presence to establish monitoring networks similar to those in the Arctic to ensure comprehensive assessment and protection of the region's ecosystem.

Chapter 1

Persistent Organic Pollutants in the Antarctic Environment: State of the Art.

1. Persistent Organic Pollutants in the Environment

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) are diverse organic compounds introduced into the environment anthropogenically since the middle of the 20th century. Among their characteristics are that they are stable and resistant to degradation (Pennington, 2001), can bioaccumulate in organisms, and biomagnify through the trophic chain (Hop et al., 2002; Fisk et al., 2001a; 2001b; Borga & Di Guardo, 2005). However, due to their semi-volatile nature, they are subject to long-range atmospheric transport (LRAT) through the atmosphere or ocean currents (Blais et al., 2007; Brown & Wania, 2008; Bengtson-Nash, 2011). In addition, their toxicity levels harm wildlife and human health (Brown et al., 2014; Bourgeon et al., 2012). Due to these characteristics, POPs are currently regulated internationally by the Stockholm Convention to reduce and eliminate emissions into the atmosphere (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2001).

POPs include polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), such as hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCH) and hexachlorobenzene (HCB), dichloro diphenyl trichloroethane (DDTs), among others. The OCP have been widely produced and commercialized since the 1950s for agricultural use and vector control (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2006). The application of technical HCH in agriculture has been banned since the early 1980s, while DDT, Lindane (γ -HCH), and HCB were banned in the 1990s (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2006). OCPs were first reported in Antarctic marine biota in the late 60's by Sladen et al. (1966) and Taton & Ruzicka (1967). To date, their levels in different environmental compartments continue to be reported (e.g., Vergara et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020; Krasnobaev et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2022).

1.1.Sources of POPs to the Environment

In the last fifty years, the amount of studies investigating the sources and emissions of POPs has been increasing considerably at both regional and global scales (Nizzetto et al. 2010). Despite all this research effort, considerably discrepancy and uncertainty exist for the emissions and source type for POPs, even for those that have been studied for 50 years, such as PCBs. There are two main types of sources of POPs:

Primary sources. Primary sources for POPs include all the sources that involved intentional or unintentional release of POPs to the environment by humans or anthropogenic activities. Among them, we can mention industrial and agrochemical use for PCBs and Pesticides as a source to the environment due to intentional use. Conversely, during combustion processes at high temperature it is possible that there is the release of PCDD/Fs, which is unintentional. Other unintentional primary sources are, hazardous waste incineration (Thacker et al., 2013), waste landfills (Gioia et al., 2011; Breivik et al., 2011), by products of certain industrial processes or products (Lundin et al., 2013). The study of primary sources from a quantitative point of view has been very difficult due to the lack of information on production, types of use, waste procedures, etc, for the different organic chemicals used by humans. Even the estimated emissions of legacy POPs such as those for PCB (Breivik et al. 2002a, 2002b and 2004), the uncertainty is high, and current though is that the real emissions were higher than the higher end estimates given in that assessment. On the other hand, local sources of POPs have been detected in remote sites, such as Antarctica, from research stations and tourist access points, which can contribute to detectable and sometimes elevated concentrations of POPs. For example, PCBs have been reported in the vicinity of such local sources (Larsson et al., 1992; Risebrough et al. 1990; Hale et al., 2008).

Secondary sources: Secondary sources of POPs are those that involve remobilization of POPs from environmental compartments where they were accumulated or trapped after environmental release from primary sources. These reservoirs can be soils, sediments, vegetation, ice, surface waters... It is well known that due to international legislations the primary sources have clearly been reduced (Li et al., 2005; Breivik et al., 2007; Schenker et al., 2008; Hassanin et al., 2005) and the remobilization from the environmental compartments (secondary sources) become more important. In addition, changing environmental conditions due to human activities, or climatic change, are also increasing the secondary sources of POPs to the environment. (Dalla Valle et al., 2007; Nizzetto et al., 2010, Ma et al. 2011). The secondary sources of POPs are turning to be more relevant in remote regions where primary emissions have always being of limited magnitude (Bengtson-Nash et al., 2010)

2. *Relevant Physical-chemical properties for non-ionic POPs*

The physical chemical properties of POPs play a key role on the environmental partitioning of POPs, on the potential for long-range transport through the atmosphere and oceans, on their persistence, and on bioaccumulation processes. The relevant physico-chemical properties that need to be considered when studying the environmental partitioning and cycling of POPs are the vapour pressure (P_V), solubility in water (S_W), Polarity (S_O), hydrophobicity, air-water partition coefficients ($\text{Log}K_{AW}$), octanol-air partition coefficients ($\text{Log}K_{OA}$) and octanol-water partition coefficients ($\text{Log}K_{OW}$).

Vapor pressure (P_V): The vapour pressure is the atmospheric pressure exerted by a vapour in a closed system that is in thermodynamic equilibrium with its condensed pure phases (solid or liquid) at a given temperature. It informs about the tendency of the chemical to escape from the liquid (or a solid) phase and its units are Pascals (Pa). The organic compounds with higher P_V will have higher tendencies to partition to the atmosphere and undergo atmospheric transport. P_V for most legacy POPs range from 0.0001 to 0.01 Pa. P_V depends on temperature, so at higher temperatures, P_V is higher.

Solubility in water (S_W): The solubility in water is the maximum concentration of a chemical in water when it is in contact with the pure compound (solid, liquid, or gas). Non-ionic organic compounds tend to have low solubilities in water, and its value depends on the polarity of the solute and temperature. Its units in the international system are mol m^{-3} . For example compounds with high solubility will tend to be in the surface waters from the continent or oceans, while lower solubility compounds tend to be in sediments, bound to particles or in their depending on the vapour pressure. Legacy POPs have very low S_W values because they are either non-polar or have low polarities.

Solubility in organic matter and octanol (S_{Oct}): The solubility in organic matter is the saturated concentrations of the solute as dissolved in the organic matter (absorption) when it is in contact with the pure compound. Since most legacy POPs are highly hydrophobic (low S_W), they have high tendency to partition in organic matter and lipids of particles and organisms. However, the composition of organic matter pools in the environment can vary, and by tradition, octanol has been taken as a surrogate of organic matter. Therefore, physical

chemical properties for organic compounds are tabulated for the partition to octanol, and the environmental partitioning of chemicals is referred to the octanol-water and octanol-air partition coefficients.

2.1. *Octanol-water partition coefficients (K_{ow}) and estimation of partitioning between water and organic matter.*

Octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{ow}): K_{ow} is the ratio between S_{oct} and S_w

$$K_{OW} = \frac{S_{Oct}}{S_W} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Therefore, K_{ow} is dimensionless. K_{ow} has been tabulated for thousands of organic compounds and can also be predicted from chemical structure. K_{ow} depends on temperature, with lower values at higher temperatures. K_{ow} are usually tabulated at 298K and it can be temperature-corrected to environmental conditions by (Harner and Bidleman, 1996):

$$\frac{K_{OW T_0}}{K_{OW T_{298.15}}} = e^{\frac{-\Delta U_{OW}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{298.15} \right)} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where $K_{OW T_0}$ and $K_{OW T_{298.15}}$ are the octanol water partition coefficients at T_0 and at 298.15 K, $-\Delta U_{OW}$ is the enthalpy of phase change from octanol to water (kJ mol^{-1}), and R is the ideal gas constant ($\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$). Typical values of $-\Delta U_{OW}$ for hydrophobic organic pollutants are of 35 KJ mol^{-1} .

Characteristic values of K_{OW} for most legacy POPs, such as PCBs and HCH, range from $10^{3.5}$ to 10^8 at 298 K. These values are more than one order of magnitude higher in the polar oceans.

Dissolved organic carbon–water partition coefficient (K_{DOC}): Since the dissolved organic carbon (DOC, KgC m^{-3}) is the major pool of carbon in oceanic waters, it is important to assess how K_{DOC} is predicted. K_{DOC} is given by:

$$K_{DOC} = \frac{C_{WDOC}}{C_W} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Where C_{WDOC} and C_W are the concentrations of the selected compound associated to dissolved organic carbon (ng KgC^{-1}) and the concentration of the selected compound found in the truly dissolved phase (ng m^{-3}). DOC is an heterogeneous mixture of

organic compounds, and has a lower sorption capacity than octanol, particulate organic carbon, or lipids. Experimental measurements have reached experimental values for K_{DOC} , but with an important variability, but an average correlation between K_{DOC} and K_{OW} is usually used (Totten et al.,2001):

$$K_{DOC} = 0.1K_{OW} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

2.2. Henry's Law Constant (HLC) and Air-water partition coefficient (K_{AW}).

The partition coefficient between air and water (given by the Henry's Law Constant, HLC) is the ratio defined by

$$HLC = \frac{P_V}{S_W} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

HLC has units of $\text{Pa m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Usually, HLC constant is used as dimensionless (H')

$$H' = \frac{HLC}{RT} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Where H' is the dimensional Henry's law constant, R is the gas constant ($8.31 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and T is the sea surface temperature (K). This equation is analogous to the dimensionless calculated air water partition coefficients K_{AW} following:

$$H' = K_{AW} = \frac{C_G}{C_W} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

Where C_G and C_W are the concentrations in the air and water (ng m^{-3}) at equilibrium. HLC and H' depend on the environmental conditions and they should be corrected for temperature (Eq. 8) and salinity (Eq. 9) following:

$$\frac{HLC_{T_0}}{HLC_{298.15}} = e^{\frac{-\Delta U_{OW}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{298.15} \right)} \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

$$HLC = 1.3 HLC_{T_0} \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

Where HLC_{T_0} , $HLC_{298.15}$ and HLC_S are the HLC corrected by temperature, the HLC at 298.15 K, and the HLC corrected by temperature and salinity, respectively. $-\Delta U_{AW}$ is the enthalpy of phase change (kJ mol^{-1}), T_0 is the sea surface temperature (K), and 1.3 is the

correction factor for accounting the effect of salinity on POP solubility in seawater. Briefly, HLC increase at higher salinities and for higher temperatures (Rice et al., 1997).

2.3. Octanol-air partition coefficients (K_{OA})

The octanol air partition coefficient (K_{OA}) is defined by:

$$K_{OA} = \frac{C_{Oct}}{C_G} \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

Where C_{Oct} and C_G are the concentration of the chemical in the octanol phase and in the gas phase (ng m^{-3}) at equilibrium. Since there are very few measurements of K_{OA} , it is usually derived from HLC and K_{OW} following (Kömp and McLachlan, 1997; Harner and Bidleman, 1998; Shoeib and Harner, 2002):

$$K_{OA} = \frac{K_{OW}(RT)}{HLC} \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

However, there is a non-negligible uncertainty in the measurements and estimations of K_{OW} , HLC , K_{OA} , the influence of temperature on their values, and differences in the activity of dry and wet octanol used for the estimation of K_{OW} (Meylan and Howard, 2005).

2.4. Fugacity as a criterion for equilibrium between environmental media

Fugacity (f) is a concept widely used to investigate the environmental partitioning of non-ionic organic chemicals, including the air-water equilibrium or dis-equilibrium (Mackay et al. 1979). The word fugacity comes from the Latin word *fugere* that means *fly* or *run away* from a determined place. Fugacity is commonly defined as the escaping tendency of the studied compound from a phase (water, air, soil, biota, sediments). In environmental modelling, fugacity gives us information about the tendency for diffusion of a selected chemical compound from one phase to another phase (for example, air and water). At equilibrium, the fugacity of the chemical is equal in the different compartments. There is a net diffusion of chemicals from high to low fugacity phases until equilibrium is reached. Fugacity in the case of gases is equal to the partial pressure (Pa) and in consequence it is directly related with the concentration of the selected compound, in the gas phase. The fugacity of a chemical in a given environmental compartment or phase (f_X) is estimated by

$$f_X = \frac{C_X}{MWZ_X} \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

Where C_X is the concentration of a selected compound in the studied phase (g m^{-3}), MW is the molecular weight of a selected compound (g mol^{-1}) and Z_X is the fugacity capacity ($\text{mol m}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-1}$), which describes the capacity of the phase or environmental compartment to retain the selected compound. In the case of the air and water, Z_A and Z_W are:

$$Z_A = \frac{1}{RT} \quad (\text{Eq. 13})$$

$$Z_W = \frac{HLC}{RT} = HLC'. \quad (\text{Eq. 14})$$

The advantage of working with fugacities instead of concentrations is because the direct comparison of fugacities in the different compartments provide information on the direction of the net exchange or the occurrence of equilibrium conditions. The fugacity ratio between the air and water ($f_w f_A^{-1}$) is widely used in the literature on POPs cycling in the environment, and it is given by,

$$\frac{f_w}{f_A} = \frac{C_w H}{C_G} \quad (\text{Eq. 15})$$

When $f_w f_A^{-1}$ is close 1, it means that the compounds are close to equilibrium between air and water. $f_w f_A^{-1} < 1$ indicates that there is a net deposition from air to water, while for $f_w f_A^{-1} > 1$ there is a net volatilization from water to air. It is noteworthy that the ratio of fugacity has some critics (Hoff, 1994; Bruhn et al., 2003) because of the uncertainties associated to the fugacity estimations. It is assumed that uncertainties associated to values of R , T and MW are negligible compared to those associated to C_G , C_W and HLC (Bruhn et al., 2003). The uncertainty associated to C_G and C_W measurements for a single laboratory is of ≈ 0.15 . HLC uncertainty has been considered larger ≈ 1 (Bruhn et al., 2003), however Li and collaborators (2003) recently estimated a more appropriate value of ≈ 0.3 for the uncertainty of HLC . In light of the above uncertainty on the fugacity estimations, it was proposed a more appropriate range of fugacity ratios for assessment of the direction of exchange in which $f_w f_A^{-1} < 0.3$, $0.3 < f_w f_A^{-1} < 3.1$, and $f_w f_A^{-1} > 3.1$ points that there is net deposition, close to equilibrium conditions, and net volatilization between the air and water, respectively.

3. Environmental fate of POPs

The environmental fate of these organic substances depends on their physicochemical properties and the exchange processes between the different environmental compartments (water, air, solid surfaces, and organisms). According to the classification made by Wania (2003; 2006), based on the partitioning properties of these compounds, such as K_{OA} (octanol-air), K_{OW} (octanol-water), and K_{AW} (air-water) (see fig. 1.1A), PCBs and OCPs are in the category of multiple hoppers (See fig. 1.1B), subject to coupled transport in the atmosphere and aquatic systems except for HCHs which are considered swimmers, subject to meridional transport in the oceans. Once POPs reach the water column, they can follow different routes i) they can remain in the dissolved phase and revolatilize (as in the case of compounds with $\text{Log } K_{OW} < 3$ and $\text{Log } K_{AW} > 0$), or ii) they can bind to particles rich in organic matter (phytoplankton and organic matter-derived detritus in the case of compounds with $\text{Log } K_{OW}$ values > 3.5).

Figure 1.1. Primary environmental compartments (A) and major modes of transport (B) of perfectly persistent, hypothetical chemicals defined by their partitioning properties $\log K_{AW}$ and $\log K_{OA}$, when calculated with the Globo-POP model assuming 10 years of steady state

3.1. Influence of air-water diffusive exchange on the environmental fate of POPs

Diffusive air-water exchange is an important process that influences the levels of semi-volatile organic compounds in aquatic systems through atmospheric volatilization and deposition (Swackhamer et al., 1988; Achman et al., 1993; Jeremiasson et al., 1994 and 1999). In an equilibrium system, dissolved-phase POP concentrations depend directly on gas-phase concentrations through the equilibrium water-particle partition coefficient and Henry's constant. However, aquatic systems are often dynamic where equilibrium is rarely reached (Jeremiasson et al., 1999). Furthermore, it has been documented that the direction of the air-water exchange gradient is strongly influenced by temperature due to its influence on air-surface partitioning (Mackay & Wania, 1995), as well as the concentration of POPs present in the dissolved phase (Achman et al., 1993; Swackhamer & Skoglund, 1993; Stange & Swackhamer, 1994).

POPs are transported from net volatilization areas to net deposition areas (i.e., from higher temperature to lower temperature). In this context, several studies have shown that polar regions act as a net sink for many POPs due to the effect of low temperatures on air-water exchange processes, with atmospheric deposition of chemical compounds predominating (Mackay & Wania, 1995; Kallenborn et al., 1998; Dickhut et al., 2005; Giogia et al., 2008; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Baeck et al., 2011; Cabrerizo et al., 2012; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012; 2013a; 2013c; Montone et al., 2013). However, it has been suggested that climate change could reverse this behavior in the coming decades, increasing the volatilization of more volatile compounds (e.g., HCB and HCH), as well as contributing to the melting of sea ice leading to the release of pollutants from the water to the atmosphere through a water-air interface (Ma et al., 2011; Bigot et al., 2019; Wöhrnschimmel et al., 2013), affecting global efforts to moderate human and environmental exposure to these toxic compounds (Bigot et al., 2019).

4. Global transport of POPs and input to Antarctica

The atmospheric compartment is critical in the global distribution of POPs, even more for the remotest environments. Emissions from primary and secondary sources to the

atmosphere and the subsequent transport by atmospheric circulation (Barrie, 1992), provide a very efficient mechanism to distribute POPs globally, followed by deposition. Atmospheric deposition is the major process of POPs input to oceans especially in open sea and the remote oceans (Bidleman, 1988; Iwata et al., 1993; Macdonald et al., 2000, Jurado et al. 2004). Even though oceanic currents play a role on the long-range transport of non-volatile organic pollutants such as perfluorinated acids (Prevedouros et al., 2006), their role as a transport vector of semivolatile organic compounds is thought to be of minor magnitude when compared with the atmosphere. However, oceans also play a key role in the cycling of POPs globally. First, oceans are an important reservoir of POPs (Jurado et al. 2004), second in importance after soils if we consider the surface oceans (Dalla Valle et al. 2005), but it could be the main reservoir if the deep ocean was considered. In addition, the ocean is thought to be one of the main sinks for most POPs (Dachs et al., 2002, Lohmann et al. 2013). The other main global sink is degradation, and the main “chemical reactor” of planet Earth is the atmosphere.

POPs can reach Antarctica primarily through atmospheric transport, ocean currents, and, to a lesser extent, migratory animals (Fig. 1.2). The study of POPs in polar regions revealed that contaminants could indeed reach remote locations and with much higher concentrations than expected, considering the remoteness of these areas (Kallenborn et al., 2013; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012; 2013a; 2013b; 2013c and 2013d; Cabrerizo et al., 2013; 2014; and 2017; Wania & Mackay, 1996; Zhang et al., 2013). Furthermore, Wania and Mackay (1996) suggested that temperature plays an essential role in determining the transport and sinking of POPs in the oceans on a global scale through cold condensation, global distillation, and latitudinal fractionation. This would result in an inverted concentration gradient of POPs, with low concentrations in the tropics and high concentrations in the polar regions. This is because less volatile compounds are deposited close to their sources, while more volatile compounds travel towards the poles, where they are preferentially deposited due to lower temperatures. Therefore, it has been suggested that temperature could largely explain oceanic POP concentrations due to its influence on air-water exchange and other partitioning processes (Wania & Mackay, 1996). In addition, in early spring, seasonal melting of sea ice can increase the concentrations of POPs present in receiving water bodies and consequently increase exposure in aquatic systems. Thus, the presence of POPs in

Antarctica is ubiquitous. Levels reported to date suggest that concentrations in the Antarctic Peninsula are higher than in other areas due to its proximity to continental (South American) sources (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a and 2013d; Kallenborn et al. al., 2013; Wang et al., 2015) and higher human activities (Hale et al., 2008; Wild et al., 2015; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a and 2013d).

Figure 1. 2. SVOC transport from temperate and tropical regions in the northern and southern hemispheres to the Arctic and the Antarctic Continent (Egas et al., 2023)

5. Antarctic Ecosystem

Concerning polar ecosystems, the fauna of the Antarctic ecosystem is relatively ancient compared to similar ecosystems (Arctic). Therefore, endemism in these areas is high, with large populations of higher-order predators (Ekman, 1953; Lalli & Parson, 1997). The traditional approach to Southern Ocean trophic webs is that of a simple system dominated by Antarctic krill (*Euphausia superba*) linking primary production (phytoplankton) to higher trophic levels (Everson, 1977; Laws, 1984; Murphy et al., 2012; Figure 1.3). In contrast to the Arctic, Antarctic pollution reflects the chemical use of a hemisphere with relatively little land mass, human population, and historical industry. Combined with the shorter food chains characteristic of Antarctica and the absence of subsisting human populations, it has served to reduce the theoretical chemical risk category attributed to Antarctic biota and systems, and consequently, a reduction in the associated investment in Antarctic POPs research (Bengtson-Nash, 2011).

Figure 1. 3. A diagram of the Antarctic food web

6. POPs transfer through the trophic network and biological pump

Bioconcentration is the accumulation of waterborne chemicals by aquatic animals through non-food pathways. The term used to quantify the magnitude of bioconcentration is

the bioconcentration factor (BCF). The BCF is defined as the proportionality constant relating the concentration of a chemical in the aquatic animal to the concentration in the water under equilibrium conditions (e.g., [fish]/[water]). The BCF is an estimate of the propensity of a chemical to accumulate in an aquatic animal at equilibrium, with values between 0 and infinity. The bioaccumulation factor (BAF), on the other hand, represents the chemical concentration in the organism (ng chemical/g tissue) divided by the concentration present in the water (ng/L). Wet or dry weight can be used; dry weight can eliminate tissue or sediment hydration variability. BAF is a unitless number between 0 and infinity (Barron, 1995).

On the other hand, biomagnification is the increase of contaminant concentration in an organism above bioconcentration and is caused by the transfer of contaminant residues from lower trophic levels to higher trophic levels (trophic transfer). Bioconcentration of waterborne chemicals can explain the accumulation of contaminants in aquatic organisms. However, many persistent hydrophobic contaminants show increasing concentrations with trophic levels in aquatic-based food webs and piscivorous birds. In addition, observations of contaminant concentrations higher than predicted from BCFs argue for a significant role of biomagnification for chlorinated pesticides, PCBs, dioxins, and many other contaminants. BAF can be used to assess the magnitude of accumulation from multiple exposure pathways (e.g., trophic transfer, bioconcentration). BAF relates the concentration in an organism resulting from dietary and aqueous exposures to the concentration in water. To reduce variability, a lipid-normalized BAF can be calculated as $\mu\text{g contaminant/kg lipid}$ divided by $\mu\text{g contaminant/liter of water}$. The BAF is generally used to assess site- or study-specific bioaccumulation magnitude. A biomagnification factor (BMF; e.g., [fish]/[diet]) can also be calculated to assess an elevation of fish tissue concentrations above contaminant concentrations in prey species (Barron, 1995).

In aquatic systems, fractions of POPs taken up by phytoplankton can be effectively transferred to higher trophic levels through zooplankton grazing; this pathway will result in the retention of chemicals in the system and facilitate exposure and bioaccumulation to higher trophic levels. In the Antarctic ecosystem, krill are essential in the transfer of POPs into the Antarctic food web (Fig. 2), playing a significant role in the biogeochemical cycling of POPs in the water column (Chiuchiolo et al., 2004; Corsolini et al., 2006; Bengtson-Nash

et al., 2008; Goutte et al., 2013) and the way bioaccumulation occurs on this species is through diet and/or POPs concentrations present in the water. Several studies have reported occurrence and bioconcentration for lower trophic levels, such as phytoplankton (Chiuchiolo et al., 2004 and Galban- Malagon et al., 2013c) and zooplankton (Joiris & Overlook, 1991; Corsolini et al., 2003; Bengtson-Nash et al., 2008; Sanchis et al., 2015; Chiuchiolo et al., 2004; Goutte et al., 2013; Goerke et al., 2004). However, advances in bioaccumulation factors (BAFs) and biomagnification factors (BMFs) have yet to be made available. For example, to date, only one study reports an increase of these contaminants at trophic levels (Goerke et al., 2004), indicating that trophic biomagnification occurs on the Antarctic continent effectively. However, a period characterized by massive phytoplankton blooms occurs during the summer due to increased irradiation, reduced ice cover, and subsequent nutrient input (Smith Jr & Gordon, 1997; Arrigo et al., 2012), a time when dissolved PCB levels in water and phytoplankton have been described to be lower due to biodilution (Larson et al., 2000) and probably to higher particle sinking rates due to the biological pump. The concept of "biological pump" refers to the process in which organic matter, produced by photosynthesis in the ocean, descends vertically from the surface layer to depth by a combination of sinking particles, trophodynamics, advection, or vertical mixing of dissolved organic matter, and transport by animals. The particulate organic matter exported deep ward from the euphotic zone is composed of combinations of zooplankton and fish fecal pellets, organic aggregates known as "marine snow," and phytoplankton phytodetritus (Turner, 2015).

On the other hand, it has been documented that krill do not feed on bloom-causing phytoplankton species and prefer to feed on small patches of phytoplankton present in the water column (Haberman et al., 2003; Hamner and 1988). For example, Haberman et al. (2003) revealed that krill avoid feeding on *Phaeocystis* spp. in laboratory and field experiments. In this sense, increasing phytoplankton biomass will significantly reduce krill exposure to PCBs and increase sink fluxes. Therefore, the influence of phytoplankton on diet may be insufficient to increase PCB levels in krill relative to the chemical equilibrium between water and krill.

Hydrophobic POPs have been shown to follow the organic carbon cycle and mimicking its behavior (Nizzeto et al., 2010). Thus, a comparison between the magnitude of

carbon export to deep waters due to the biological pump and carbon ingested by krill would be feasible. Likewise, Galbán-Malagón et al. (2018) showed that in terms of organic carbon consumption, krill ingestion fluxes are considerably low relative to the flux of primary production export to deeper waters in Antarctica. However, the samples came from different sites making it difficult to guarantee the occurrence of this process.

7. *Effect of climate change on biogeochemical cycling of POPs*

Climate change and rising temperatures enhance glacial retreat in West Antarctica (Turner et al., 2005; Chapman et al., 2007; Rückamp et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2017; Dryac & Enderlin, 2020). Glacial meltwater transports micronutrients (e.g., iron) (Höfer et al., 2019; Hopwood et al., 2019) that are released to surface waters (Krause et al., 2021) while enhancing the stability of the water column within the bay (e.g., Höfer et al., 2019), such nutrient inputs and subsequent stratification of the water column due to glacial melt trigger massive algal blooms in Antarctic aquatic systems (Mitchell & Holm-Hansen, 1991; Jones et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020; Rozema et al., 2017), increasing primary productivity during spring and summer (e.g., Kim et al., 2018). In that period, it has been documented in marine areas that the biological pump plays an important role by removing POPs from ocean surface waters and transporting them to the ocean floor via sinking particles (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013), which in turn decreases the concentration of POPs throughout the water column. These nutrient inputs from snowmelt can also modify microbial communities and the degree of microbial degradation, as recently demonstrated for PAHs (Iriarte et al., 2023). However, this primary productivity is highly seasonal, as this process takes place mainly during spring-summer, and condensation and replenishment of organic compounds occur throughout the year by transport. On the other hand, thaws can exert a significant influence on POP concentrations in coastal waters because snow/ice acts as a reservoir of POPs that are released to the environment after snow/ice melt, amplifying these compounds in soils and mainly in aquatic systems (Burniston et al., 2007; Geisz et al., 2008; Casal et al., 2019).

Considering the collected background, the questions that will be attempted to be answered during this study are:

- Which process, volatilization or atmospheric deposition, dominates in the Southern Ocean?

- In the Antarctic trophic web, what process, bioaccumulation or biomagnification, explains the levels of POPs present in krill?
- How do blooms and the biological pump affect the levels of POPs in the water column, phytoplankton, and krill?

Figure 1. 4. Summary diagram of POPs inputs and biogeochemical cycles in the Antarctic.

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Hypothesis and objectives

Hypothesis

1. POPs compounds, such as PCBs and OCPs, present an air-water gradient direction, predominating the atmospheric deposition process in the Southern Ocean.
2. The phytoplankton biological pump prevents the transfer of POPs through the food web due to higher sedimentation fluxes from the surface to the sediment during periods of high productivity.

Objectives:

A. General objective

To assess the environmental fate of persistent organic pollutants during blooms in Antarctica.

B. Specific objectives

1. To compile published data on the levels of POPs in the air and estimate their half-life.
2. Determine PCB, HCH, and HCB concentrations in air, water, phytoplankton, and zooplankton.
3. Determine the direction of air-water exchange
4. To calculate the Bioconcentration, Bioaccumulation, and Biomagnification factors.

Chapter 2

Levels of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the Antarctic atmosphere over time (1980 to 2021) and estimation of their atmospheric half-lives

This chapter has been published in Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics

Luarte, T., Gómez-Aburto, V. A., Poblete-Castro, I., Castro-Nallar, E., Hunneus, N., Molina-Montenegro, M., Egas, C., Azcune, G., Pérez-Parada, A., Lohmann, R., Bohlin-Nizzetto, P., Dachs, J., Bengtson-Nash, S., Chiang, G., Pozo, K., and Galbán-Malagón, C.: Levels of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the Antarctic atmosphere over time (1980 to 2021) and estimation of their atmospheric half-lives., Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss. [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-2023-25>

Abstract

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs) are synthetic compounds that were intentionally produced in large quantities and have been distributed in the global environment, originating a threat due to their persistence, bioaccumulative potential and toxicity. POPs reach the Antarctic continent through long-range atmospheric transport. In these areas low temperatures play a significant role in the environmental fate of POPs, retaining them for a long-time due to cold trapping by diffusion and wet deposition, acting as net sink for many POPs. However, in the current context of climate change, remobilization of POPs trapped for decades in water, ice, and soil, is happening. Therefore, continuous monitoring of POPs in polar air is necessary to assess whether there is a recent re-release of historical pollutants back to the environment. We reviewed the scientific literature on atmospheric levels of several POPs families (polychlorinated biphenyls PCBs, hexachlorobenzene HCB, hexachlorocyclohexanes HCHs, and DDT) from 1988 to 2021. We estimated the atmospheric half-life using characteristic decreasing times (TD). We observed that HCB levels in the Antarctic atmosphere were higher than the other target OCs, but HCB also displayed higher fluctuations and did not show a significant decrease over time. Conversely, the atmospheric levels of HCHs, and some DDTs, and PCBs have decreased significantly. The estimated atmospheric half-lives for POPs decreased in the following order: 4,4' DDE (13.5 years) > 4,4' DDD (12.8 years) > 4,4' DDT (7.4 years) > 2,4' DDE (6.4 years) > 2,4' DDT (6.3 years) > α -HCH (6 years) > HCB (6 years) > γ -HCH (4.2 years), while for PCB congeners they decreased in the following order: PCB 153 (7.6 years) > PCB 138 (6.5 years) > PCB 101 (4.7 years) > PCB 180 (4.6 years) > PCB 28 (4 years) > PCB 52 (3.7 years) > PCB 118 (3.6 years). For HCH isomers and PCBs, the Stockholm Convention ban on POPs did have an impact on decreasing their levels during the last decades. Nevertheless, their ubiquity in the Antarctic atmosphere shows the problematic issues related to highly persistent synthetic chemicals.

1. Introduction

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) are a group of toxic chemicals primarily produced and used by the agricultural, industrial, and household applications during the third industrial revolution (Safe, 1994; Qiu et al., 2004; Jayaraj et al., 2016). In the last three decades, studies have reported that POPs levels have soared in the environment worldwide, as these chemicals are highly stable and resistant to degradation (Pennington, 2001). This persistence and their hydrophobicity result in POPs bioaccumulation within organisms and biomagnification along food webs (Hop et al., 2002; Fisk et al., 2001a; 2001b; Borga and Di Guardo, 2005), where they may elicit toxic effects, such as endocrine disruption, threatening the health of both wildlife and humans (Brown et al., 2014; Bourgeon et al., 2012). Given their detrimental effects, 31 substances/substance groups of POPs are currently regulated internationally by the Stockholm Convention (SC), which seeks to reduce and eliminate POPs production and use (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2006). However, despite regulatory action among SC signatory nations, considerable levels of POPs are still detected in water, atmosphere, biota, and sediments worldwide due to their persistence, potential for long range transport, as well as their current emission sources (e.g., Vergara et al., 2019; Vasseghian et al., 2021; Avila et al., 2021; Die et al., 2021; García-Cegarra et al., 2021). Of utmost concern, these toxic pollutants are present in the environmental compartments of regions far from emission sources that have previously been considered pristine areas, including polar regions (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a; 2013b; 2013c; Pozo et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2020; Azcune et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2022).

The Antarctic continent is the most remote region from primary sources of POPs (Von Waldow et al., 2010). POPs reach Antarctica mainly through long-range atmospheric transport (LRAT), which generally occurs by the process known as "grasshopping", consisting of successive atmospheric volatilizations and depositions (Blais et al., 2007; Brown and Wania, 2008; Bengtson-Nash, 2011; Jurado and Dachs, 2008). Ocean currents also contribute to their transport processes, albeit at longer timescales since the Antarctic Circumpolar Current acts as a barrier limiting oceanic transport of POPs to the Antarctic continent (Bengtson-Nash et al., 2010). The "barrier theory" has been questioned by Lozoya et al. (2022) for the South Shetland Islands, where the current experiences topographical forcing through the Drake Passage. Finally, another minor transport process is biological,

mediated by migratory biota (Braune et al., 2005; Wild et al., 2022). In addition, there may be local sources of POPs, such as research stations and tourist hotspots, that can contribute to detectable and sometimes elevated concentrations of POPs. For example, PCBs have been reported in the vicinity of such local sources (Larsson et al., 1992; Risebrough et al. 1990; Hale et al., 2008). The low temperatures of Antarctica play an important role in the environmental fate of POPs, repressing re-volatilization processes and favoring cold trapping (Wania and Mackay, 1996, Casal et al. 2019), limiting any potential degradation, and enhancing bioaccumulation. In this context, several studies show that polar regions act as a net sink for many POPs; Antarctica is a vast continent covered in ice surrounded by the southern ocean, hence chemicals deposited through LRAT will first deposit in these compartments (Mackay and Wania, 1995; Kallenborn et al., 1998; Dickhut et al., 2005; Giogia et al., 2008; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Baek et al., 2011; Cabrerizo et al., 2017; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012, 2013a, 2013c; Montone et al., 2013). For example, there is evidence supporting oceanic sequestration by the biological pump during blooms burying these compounds on the seafloor (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a, 2013c) or by biodegradation due to the microbial loop (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013d). In the context of rapid climate change experienced in polar regions, the remobilization of POPs previously trapped for decades in water, ice, and soil is expected (Nizzetto et al., 2010; Ma et al., 2011; Cabrerizo et al., 2013). The re-emission of POPs to the environment will affect global efforts to moderate human and environmental exposure to these toxic compounds (Bigot et al., 2016), therefore, continuous monitoring of POPs levels in polar abiotic matrices is necessary to assess to what extent such re-emissions to the atmosphere occur.

The detection of chemicals in remote regions serves as direct empirical evidence of a compound's persistence and potential for long-term environmental transport (Bengston-Nash et al., 2017). POPs were first reported in Antarctic biota in the 1960s (Sladen et al., 1966; Tatton and Ruzicka, 1967), sparking interest in studying the transport, fate, and levels present in different environmental compartments. Through the collation of decades of coordinated monitoring data of POPs in the Arctic atmosphere, studies have explored the fate, sources, and long-range transport of POPs in the Northern Hemisphere (Hung et al., 2010, 2016; Wu et al., 2010, 2011). A general downward trend of many airborne POPs has been demonstrated in the Arctic (Hung et al., 2010, 2016; Kong et al., 2014). However, continuous and consistent

atmospheric measurements on POPs in Antarctica are limited, due to the remote geographical location and complex climatic conditions of this continent, which put logistical constraints on any monitoring programme. These knowledge gaps make it difficult to understand the fundamental patterns of POPs in this area (Bengston-Nash, 2011), as well as to facilitate systematic comparison with studies conducted in the Arctic.

This paper presents the first systematic review of the most reported POPs in the Antarctic atmosphere, allowing to summarize the data collected by the different studies and compare the concentrations recorded over the years and at the different sampling sites. Such compilation allow to identify temporal trends and calculate the atmospheric half-lives of the predominant POPs being monitored to provide insights into expected impacts of environmental remobilization under changing Antarctic conditions.

2. Methods

2.1 Compilation of bibliographical data

We reviewed all published studies on atmospheric levels of the most reported POP families in the Antarctic atmosphere (polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), hexachlorobenzene (HCB), hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) and dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) and its degradation products) from 1988 to 2021. An exhaustive search was performed in the Web of Science and Scopus databases using the words "Persistent Organic Pollutants", "atmospheric" and "Antarctica", including only articles written in English; excluding from the analysis references that do not refer to a good quality assurance and quality control during the chemical analysis, or if the levels of field blanks were not reported. A total of 34 publications were found, from which we retrieved data on the levels reported, the year in which the samples were collected, and the sampling sites (Table 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3). We worked exclusively with the levels of the target compounds in the gas phase e, obtained from active and passive sampling. Furthermore, compounds scarcely reported in the Antarctic atmosphere, such as polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), per-and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), were excluded.

2.2 Statistical analysis

To evaluate the differences between the levels, present in West Antarctica and East Antarctica, a non-parametric U-Mann Whitney variance analysis was conducted. All the analyses were performed using the R statistical software. (R Core Team, 2022). To estimate the trend in the change of concentrations, a linear regression was performed between the natural logarithm of the concentrations for each year studied.

2.3 Estimation of characteristic decreasing times (T_D)

Atmospheric half-lives were estimated by deriving the e-folding or characteristic decreasing times (T_D), following the methodology of Galbán-Malagón et al. (2013a). The half-life is defined as the time needed to decrease the atmospheric concentration by 35% (e^{-1}) of its initial concentration, which is given by $0.69 T_D$. First, only the studies that reported all the values recorded for each sample were used (Table S1 and S2, Annex A). These studies were ordered by year of sampling, and their respective T_D was calculated by least squares adjusting the concentrations to Eq. (1):

$$\ln C_{Atm} = -k_d t + b \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where k_d is the inverse of the e-folding time T_D (in years), t is the time in years and b is the independent term. T_D was not calculated for β -HCH, due to the limited data available.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Organochlorine Pesticides (OCPs)

OCPs represent most of the POPs listed in the Stockholm Convention. These organic compounds have been widely produced and commercialized since the 1950s for agricultural use and vector control (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2006). The application of technical HCH in agriculture has been banned since the early 1980s, while DDT, Lindane (γ -HCH), and HCB were banned in the 1990s (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2001). OCPs were first reported in Antarctic marine biota in the late 60's by Sladen et al. (1966) and Taton & Ruzicka (1967). To date, their levels in different environmental compartments continue to be reported (e.g., Vergara et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020; Krasnobaev et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2022).

3.1.1 Atmospheric levels of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs)

In the Arctic atmosphere, HCB concentrations are the highest of any OCPs (De March et al., 1998). Similarly, atmospheric concentrations of HCB reported from the Antarctic have been observed to be higher than the other target OCPs (Table 2.1 and 2.2), being the most frequently detected and abundant POP in the Antarctic atmosphere (Kallenborn et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2018; Hao et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020). Temporal patterns of atmospheric HCB concentrations in the Antarctic show significant inter-annual fluctuations with low but significant decreasing trends ($p < 0.001$, See table 2.4), with a higher variability over time specially in the last decade (Fig. 2.1A). A clear decrease in concentrations is shown until about 2010, thereafter a large variability of data is shown where the trend seems to be changing, however there is a lack of sufficient data to be able to confirm this trend. The maximum values were reported by Hao et al. (2019), during the 2012-2018 sampling period on King George Island (Table 2.1). Such increases in HCB gaseous levels could be mainly associated with re-emission from environmental surfaces (water, soil, and snow) shifting from a reservoir to a secondary source of this compound on the Antarctic continent. HCB is the most persistent OCPs chemical assessed here, as suggested before (Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013). In addition, there may still be an important influence of transport from current primary sources (i.e., combustion and thermal processes) on a global scale and unintentional formation during thermal processing or combustion of chlorine-containing materials (Barber

et al., 2005). The trend shown in Fig 2.1A points that concentrations of HCB in the Antarctic atmosphere may be regionally dependent, and maybe highly in pace to the climate/environmental change processes occurring in different Antarctic regions.

Table 2. 1. HCB and HCHs levels (pg m^{-3}) in Antarctic atmosphere since 1980 to present.

Sampling area	Type of sampling	Year	HCB	α -HCH	γ -HCH	Σ HCHs	Σ n	Reference
Southern ocean	Active	1980-1981				90-170		Tanabe et al., 1982
Southern ocean	Active	1981-1982				44-170		Tanae et al., 1983
Cape town and Newmayer Station	Active	1999		0.36	0.15			Lakaschus et al., 2002
Ross Island	Passive	1988 - 1999			25.8 (0.5 - 118)			Larson et al., 1992
East Antarctica	Passive	1990	62.6 (40-78)	3.2 (2.8-3.6)	2.4 (1.1-5.6)	5.7	2	Bidleman et al., 1993
Signy Island	Active	1994 - 1995		2.8	21.8	26.97	3	Kallenborn et al., 1998
East Antarctica	Passive	1997 - 1998		1.06 (0.81 - 1.4)				Jantunen et al., 2004
Terranova bay	Passive	1993	21 (n.d - 28)			13 (5 - 20.0)	3	Kallenborn et al., 1998
Ross Island	Active	1995	(<0.6 - 25.3)			3.9-32.5	2	Montone et al., 2005
west of the Antarctic Peninsula and southwest of Adelaide Island	Active	2001 - 2002	19.4 (<5 - 32.1)	0.3 (<0.05-0.52)	0.755 (<0.02-2.98)			Duckhut et al. 2005
Terra Nova Bay	Active	2003-2004	11.4 (6.0 - 20)			0.8 (0.3 - 1.2)	2	Gambaro et al., 2005
Terra Nova Bay	Active	2003-2004	11.4 (5.93 - 20.4)			0.22 (0.1 - 0.35)	2	Cincinelli et al., 2009
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	Passive	2005-2009						Baek et al., 2011
South Scotia	Active	2008	8.1 (2.18 -15.82)	1.7(0.06-5.84)	4.6 (1.5-7.1)			Galbán-Malagón et a., 2013b
Wedell	Active	2009	19.5 (2.4 - 30.1)	0.16 (0.05-2.09)	0.84 (0.1-1.87)			Galbán-Malagón et a., 2013b
Bransfield sea	Active	2009	16.7 (3.3 - 34.24)	0.14 (0.04-0.46)	1.15 (0.2-3)			Galbán-Malagón et a., 2013b
Bellingshausen	Active	2009	42.9 (27.31 - 49.71)	0.26 (0.22-0.16)	0.14 (0.07-0.19)			Galbán-Malagón et a., 2013b
Palmer station	Active	2010	34 (26.2 – 37.7)	0.81 – 1.68	0.87 – 2.31			Khairy et al., 2016
Station troll / Queen Maud Land	Active	2010	22.9					Kallenborn et al. 2013
Ross Sea	Passive	2010-2011	22.8 (0.8 - 50)	0.5 (n.d-0.5)	n.d	0.5 (n.d-0.5)	2	Pozo et al., 2017
Antarctic Plateau	Active	2011	(0.67-2.7)		BD-2.7			Cabrerizo et al. 2016
Antarctic marginal seas	Active	2013-2014	2.6 (0.081 - 10)			(n.d - 6.8)	3	Wu et al., 2020
Southern Ocean between Australia and Antarctica	Active	2014	(<22 - 35)	<0.13-1.1	<0.70-4.3	n.d - 3.65	3	Bigot et al., 2016
King George Island	Passive	2012-2018	163 (99.2 - 252)	1.4 (0.5-13.6)	0.1-7.9	0.7 - 22.3	4	Hao et al., 2019

The reported atmospheric concentrations of ΣHCHs in Antarctica from 1980-2019 show a decreasing trend over time (Table 2.1; Fig. 2.1 B and C), with significant differences in inter-annual levels ($P < 0.05$). The maximum concentration of HCHs was 170 pg/m^3 , reported in 1980-1982 (Tanabe et al., 1982; 1983), and progressively lower concentrations reaching values under detection levels and below 1 pg/m^3 are reported from 2003 to 2019 (Gambaro et al., 2005; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Baek et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Kallenborn et al., 2013; Pozo et al., 2017; Cabrerizo et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2020; Bigot et al., 2016; Hao et al., 2019). The γ -HCH isomer was found at high concentrations in Antarctica between 1989 and 1990, with a maximum atmospheric concentration of 118 pg/m^3 in 1988 at Ross Island, by Larson et al. (1992) (Fig. 2.1C, Table S2.1, Annex A). Decreasing concentrations are then reported for γ -HCH in 2000, which is unsurprising if fresh sources have been removed, given the lower volatility and higher water solubility of this isomer. On the other hand, the α -HCH isomer, is found to increase since 2006 (Baek et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Hao et al., 2019), compared to the concentrations recorded during 2001-2004 by Dickhut et al. (2005) and Cincinelli et al. (2009).

Figure 2. 1. Atmospheric levels (pg/m^3) of HCB (A), α -HCH (B), and γ -HCH (C)

Published studies reporting gaseous levels for DDT and their isomers from 1988-2018 were lower than the rest of the target OCPs, and like HCHs, the DDTs showed a decreasing trend over the years (Table 2. 2, Fig. 2.2), with significant inter-annual differences ($p < 0.05$) for compounds 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE, 2,4'-DDT and 2,2'-DDE, and non-significant annual differences ($p > 0.05$) for compounds 4,4'-DDD and 2,4'-DDD.

Table 2. 2. DDT isomers levels (pg m^{-3}) in Antarctic atmosphere since 1988 to present.

Site	Type of sampling	Year	2,4'-DDE	4,4'-DDE	2,4'-DDD	4,4'-DDD	2,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDT	SumDDT	Σn	Reference
Ross Island	Passive	1988 - 1999		1				2			Larson et al., 1992
East Antarctica	Passive	1990		0.39 (0.17 - 0.64)				0.67 (n.d - 1.1)	0.81 (1.74 - 0.25)	2	Bidleman et al., 1993
Signy Island	Active	1994 - 1995	0.07	0.4	0.068	0.098	0.195	0.285			Kallenborn et al., 1998
Ross Island	Active	1995		9.2 (n.d-53.8)		11.65 (n.d-29.4)		8,1 (n.d-19.4)	(3.7-102.6)	3	Montone et al., 2005
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	Passive	2005-2009		n.d - 38.7		n.d-4.83		n.d - 12.7			Baek et al., 2011
Station troll / Queen Maud Land	Active	2010							0.03		Kallenborn et al. 2013
Palmer station	Active	2010		0.05 – 0.2	0.3 – 1.4			0.05 - 1			Khairy et al., 2016
Ross Sea	Passive	2010-2011		n.d-0.1		n.d		n.d-0.07			Pozo et all., 2017
Antarctic marginal seas	Active	2013-2014	0.097	0.35	0.043	0.034	0.17	0.12			Wu et al., 2020
Southern Ocean between Australia and Antarctica	Active	2014	<0.51	<0.15-0.44	<1,6	<1,8	<2,7	<7,8			Bigot et al., 2016
King George Island	Passive	2012-2018	n.d-1.1	0.1-3	0.02-0.5	0.02-3.2	n.d-0.6	0.02-1.5	1 (0.2-6.3)	6	Hao et al., 2019
King George Island and Ardley Island	Passive						0.008				Wang et al., 2015

Figure 2. 2. Atmospheric levels (pg/m³) of 2,4'-DDT (A), 4,4'-DDT (B), 2,4'- DDE (C), over time

To date, atmospheric concentrations of HCB, α -HCH, β -HCH, and γ -HCH isomers have been studied over much of the Antarctic continent, both in West Antarctica (Kallenborn et al., 1998; Montone et al., 2005; Dickhut et al., 2005; Baek et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c; Khairy et al., 2016; Hao et al., 2019), and in East Antarctica (Tanabe et al., 1982, 1983; Lakaschus et al., 2002; Larsson et al., 1992; Jantunen et al., 2004; Bidleman et al., 1993; Gambaro et al., 2005; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Kallenborn et al., 2013; Pozo et al., 2017; Cabrerizo et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2020; Bigot et al., 2016). The detected concentrations of HCB and α -HCHs indicate significant spatial differences ($P < 0.05$), with higher atmospheric concentrations in West Antarctica than in East Antarctica (Table S2.4, Annex A). The γ -HCH isomer did not show spatial differences between the two zones ($P > 0.05$) (Table S2.4, Annex A). The U-Mann Whitney variance analysis was not performed for the β -HCH isomer, because all levels reported in East Antarctica were below the detection limit.

3.1.2. Atmospheric half-lives of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs)

The estimated Atmospheric half-lives for OCPs were estimated for the compounds that showed a significant trend in relation to the sampling time ($p < 0.05$ or lower). The estimated half lives decreased in the following order trend decreased in the following order: 4,4'-DDT (17.2 years) > 2,4'-DDT (14.4 years) > α -HCH (14.3 years) > HCB (14.0 years) > γ -HCH (10.1 years) (more details are given in Table 2.4). The higher atmospheric half-life values estimated in this study for DDTs isomers, compared to the values estimated for HCHs and HCB might be related to the years in which these compounds were banned, since DDTs were banned approximately 10 years after HCHs isomers. It may also be due to continuous production and use of DDTs in some parts of the world due to exemptions to the Stockholm Convention. The estimated values are higher than the atmospheric half-lives reported by other authors, such as Atkinson (1986); Howard (1991); Mortimer & Connel (1995); and Kelly et al. (1994), whose estimated and published values do not exceed one year. However, the methodologies employed differ from the one used in the present study, where Atkinson (1986); Howard (1991); and Mortimer & Connel (1995), were based on rate constant of gas-phase reaction with OH radical for trichlorobiphenyls, while Kelly et al. (1994), were based on atmospheric transformation lifetime. Meanwhile, the estimated atmospheric half-lives in

the Great Lakes (United States and Canada) are in a similar range for DDT, DDE, γ -HCH and HCB compounds (Cortes & Hites 2000). In similar environments, such as the Arctic, the atmospheric half-lives estimated by Hung et al. (2002) for γ -HCH was 4.9 years and which was much lower than our estimations, while for α -HCH they were 10 years (Hung et al., 2002), which are comparable to our estimations in Antarctica. (See table 2.4)

Polar areas are often considered to be a net sink for POPs. Studies have documented that α -HCH and γ -HCH exchanges preferentially from air to water, with this diffusion being the predominant atmospheric deposition mechanism (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a,c; Dickhut et al., 2005; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Jantunen et al., 2004; Lohmann et al., 2009; Xie et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2013). Once deposited onto surface waters, they are susceptible to sequestration by the biological pump (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a,c), as well as to degradation driven by hydrolysis and biodegradation to a minor extent (Harner et al., 2000; Helm et al., 2002; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c). These processes minimize the opportunity for re-entry to the atmosphere through volatilization. The lower half-lives values for HCHs may be related to their lower Henry's law constant when compared to other POPs. On the contrary, to our knowledge, no degradation processes have been documented for HCB in surface water and furthermore, conditions close to air-water equilibrium have been reported for this compound (Cincinelli et al., 2009; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c). Similarly, DDTs are more hydrophobic with much higher K_{ow} values than HCHs (Table S2.3, Annex A), so they are rapidly removed from seawater as particles sink (Lohmann et al., 2007). Thus, it is possible that the high half-lives estimated for DDTs and their metabolites DDD and DDE may be due to unknown current primary and secondary sources (Voldner and Li, 1995; Channa et al., 2012, Li et al., 2020).

3.2 Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs)

Like OCPs, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) were among the first groups of POPs to be listed under the Stockholm Convention and are characterized by their high chemical stability. Prior to their regulatory control in the 1970s, commercial mixtures of PCBs were widely used in many industrial applications, such as fluids in transformers and capacitors, hydraulic fluids, lubricating oils, and as additives in pesticides, inks and paints, flame

retardants, plasticizers, sealants for wood and cement surfaces, among others (Kennish, 1997; FAO/UNEP 1992).

PCBs were first reported in Antarctica in the 1960s and 1970s (Risebrough et al., 1968, 1976), and since then, numerous studies have reported their levels in air, water, sediments, snow, and biota on the Antarctic continent (e.g., Kallenborn et al., 1998; Fuoco et al., 1995; Gupta et al., 1996; Weber et al., 2003; Kim et al., 2015). Here, we selected 7 indicator PCB congeners (28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180) considering that they are the most reported PCB congeners worldwide, including Antarctica.

3.2.1 Atmospheric levels of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)

The atmospheric concentrations of Σ_7 PCBs reported by the reviewed studies were below those of the target OCPs (Table 2.3). Overall, the levels of Σ_7 PCBs reported from 1988 to 2018 showed a decreasing trend over time (Table 2.3 and 4, Fig. 2.3), with significant differences in their levels ($p < 0.05$). Congeners 28 and 52 recorded the highest concentrations on King George Island, with values of 69.9 pg m^{-3} in 1995, and 33.2 pg m^{-3} in 1996, reported by Montone et al. (2005; 2003) (Fig. 2.3A and 2.3B; Table S2.2, Annex A). In contrast, the lowest concentrations of all target PCBs were reported for congener 180, ranging from not detected (n.d) to 3.4 pg/m^3 (Fig. 2.3G; Table S2.2, Annex A).

Figure 2. 3. Atmospheric levels (pg/m³) of PCB-28 (A), PCB-52 (B), PCB-101 (C), PCB-118 (D), PCB-138 (E), PCB-153 (F) and PCB-180 (G), over time.

Table 2. 3. PCBs levels ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in Antarctic atmosphere since 1980 to present

Sampling area	Type of sampling	Year	ΣPCBs	Σn	Reference
Ross Island	Passive	1988 - 1990	15.2	6	Larson et al. 1992
King George Island	Active	1993 - 1994	20.8 (12.09 - 42.8)	10	Montone et al., 2001
Signy Island	Active	1994 - 1995	(0.01-17.2)	22	Kallenborn et al., 1998
Ross Island	Active	1995	62.4	11	Montone et al., 2005
King George Island	Active	1996-1996	37.4 (12.1 - 92.6)	10	Montone et al., 2003
Terra Nova Bay	Active	2003-2004	1.06 (0.61-1.78)	61	Gambaro et al., 2005
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	Passive	2005-2009	60.3(22.8 - 87.1)	11	Baek et al., 2011
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	Passive	2005-2009	19.8 (11.1-31.9)	205	Baek et al., 2011
ICEPOS	Active	2005	16.84 (7.12- 25.65)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
South Scotia sea	Active	2008	45.13 (6.2 - 78.9)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
Antarctic peninsula	Active	2009	12.13 (1.8- 38.1)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
Polish beach	Active	2009	(2.1 - 3.1)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
Livingston Island	Active	2009	7.23 (3.5 12.9)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
King George Island	Passive	2009 - 2010	1.142	7	Li et al 2012
King George Island	Passive	2009 - 2010	36.837	19	Li et al 2012
King George Island, Antarctica.	Passive	2009 - 2010	4.34	7	Li et al. 2012/2
Station troll / Queen Maud Land	Active	2010	0.5	32	Kallenborn et al., 2013
Palmer station	Active	2010	12	29	Khairy et al., 2016
Ross Sea	Passive	2010-2011	0.46 (0.14-1.13)	7	Pozo et al. 2017
Antarctic Plateau	Active	2011	(0.8-27)	26	Cabrerizo et al. 2016
King George Island	Active	2011-2014	5.39 (0.91-35.9)	7	Wang et al. 2017
King George Island	Active	2011-2014	5.87- 72.7 (26.1)	20	Wang et al. 2017
King George Island	Passive	2010-2018	10.4 (1.5 - 29.7)	19	Hao et al., 2019
Antarctic marginal seas	Active	2013-2014	1.1 (nd-6.7)	14	Wu et al. 2020
King George Island and Ardley Island	Passive		0.078 (nd - 0.137)	6	Wang et al. 2015

Like OCPs, atmospheric concentrations of the seven PCB congeners have been reported over most of the Antarctic zone, covering the West Antarctic zone (Montone et al., 2003; 2005; Kallenborn et al., 1998; Baek et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c; Li et al., 2012; Khairy et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2017; Hao et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020) and eastern Antarctica (Larson et al., 1992; Gambaro et al., 2005; Kallenborn et al., 2013; Pozo et al., 2017; Cabrerizo et al., 2017). Significant spatial differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the atmospheric concentrations of congeners 28, 52, 101 and 138, with higher concentrations in West Antarctica than East Antarctica, while there was no significant difference among sites for congeners 101, 118 and 153 ($p > 0.05$). These differences are consistent with the different atmospheric patterns over the Antarctic peninsula regions, with entrance of air-masses from the north, and more permanent wet deposition events by snow and rain, increasing the regional concentrations of POPs (Casal et al. 2019; Casas et al. 2021).

3.2.2. Atmospheric half-lives of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)

The estimated atmospheric half-lives for target PCBs decreased in the following order: PCB 153 (7.6 years) > PCB 138 (6.5 years) > PCB 101 (4.7 years) > PCB 180 (4.6 years) > PCB 28 (3.9 years) > PCB 52 (3.7 years) > PCB 118 (3.6 years) (Table 2.4). The estimated half-lives were directly proportional to the congener's Henry's law constant (HLC) values. (Table S2.3, Annex A). Studies by Atkinson (1986) and Sinkkonen & Paasivirta (2000) reported half-lives lower than those estimated in the present work, where none of the estimated half-lives for these compounds exceeded 1 year. However, the methodology of both studies differs from that of the present study, calculating the half-lives of the compounds by means of the rate constant of gas-phase reaction with the OH. On the other hand, the estimated atmospheric half-lives for Σ PCBs in the Great Lakes (United States and Canada) were much higher compared to the results obtained in the present work (Venier & Hites, 2010) and also their results were comparable to those published in the Arctic with data from the AMAP monitoring program (Wong et al., 2021) for PCBs 52, 101, 118. On the other hands the results obtained in the present work were in the same range an comparable to the reports for the Great Lakes and the Arctic for PCBs 138, 153 and 180; being the results obtained for PCB 180 much lower in the present work than the reported ofr the Great Lakes.

Studies have documented that the biological pump is highly efficient for PCBs with high hydrophobicity, i.e., high K_{ow} values (Table S2.3, Annex A) (Dachs et al., 2002, Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a), thus reducing their revolatilization. The estimated atmospheric half-lives, however, do not reflect lower values for the compounds with higher K_{ow} (e.g. PCB 138, 153 and 180), so other factors may be influencing the high estimated half-lives of the more hydrophobic PCBs. One of these factors could be the presence of local sources of certain PCB congeners, since it has been reported that near the research stations higher PCB concentrations are monitored, compared to sites farther away from these stations, specifically PCB congeners 28, 52, 56 and 101 (Li et al., 2012b; Montone et al., 2003). Furthermore, remobilization of PCBs stored in soils and ice (Cabrerizo et al. 2013, Casal et al. 2019) could be another factor modulating the surface, and thus atmospheric, concentrations of POPs.

Table 2. 4. Estimated atmospheric half-lives of examined compounds POPs.

Compounds	T _D (Years)	95% Confident Interval	R ²	p-value	Equation
HCB	14.0	10.6-20.7	12.03	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.04931*year + 100.2
a-HCH	14.3	12.4-17.0	32.55	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.04817*year + 96.17
y-HCH	10.1	8.6-12.3	44.63	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.06837*year + 136.9
4,4' DDT	17.2	11.8-31.7	23.54	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.04015*year + 79.50
2,4 DDT	14.4	9.8-27.3	37.55	<0.001	LnCg = -0.04794*year + 94.99
2,4 DDE	17.6	9.2-232	15.44	<0.05	LnCg = -0.03916*year + 77.93
PCB 28	3.9	3.2-5.2	43.08	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.1748*year + 351.2
PCB 52	3.7	3.2-4.3	63.53	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.1887*year + 378.7
PCB 101	4.7	4.0-5.6	67.42	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.1480*year + 295.8
PCB 118	3.6	3.0-4.3	55.91	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.1930*year + 385.8
PCB 138	6.5	5.3-8.3	40.7	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.1066*year + 212.7
PCB 153	7.6	6.0-10.4	31.59	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.09071*year + 181.2
PCB 180	4.6	3.3-8.0	24.64	<0,0001	LnCg = -0.1486*year + 296.2

3.3 Influence of global climate change on the dynamics of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the Antarctic continent.

Over the past decades, global climate changes and the effects of increasing temperatures have been observed in the northern and southern hemispheres (Hung et al., 2022). Increases in ambient temperature can influence physical and chemical processes and ecosystem changes. For example, it has been reported that increasing ambient temperature will affect the dynamics and exchange of POPs between different environmental matrices. Some studies have exposed the relationship between climate change and POPs concentrations (Vorkamp et al., 2022; Potapowicz et al., 2018), describing that POPs are temporarily stored in sediments/soils and can be released into the environment with thawing permafrost (Potapowicz et al., 2018) and that an increase in POPs availability following iceberg calving (NIC, 2014) or increased soil remobilization by up to 45% (Cabrerizo et al., 2013). In addition, several studies show that seawater, snow, and presumably Antarctic soil are becoming critical secondary sources for POP remobilization (Cabrerizo et al., 2012, 2013; Klanová et al., 2008; Casal et al., 2019).

On the other hand, the mean annual air temperature along the western Antarctic Peninsula has been reported to have increased by as much as 3.4 °C. In addition, the mid-winter temperature increased by 6.0 °C over the past 50 years, making the region one of the most critically affected by climate warming (Vaughan et al., 2003; Turner et al., 2005). However, evidence from field sampling indicated that, to date, there is no relationship between atmospheric ambient temperature and atmospheric concentrations of HCH and HCB in East Antarctica (Bengtson-Nash, 2017). On the other hand, increasing ambient temperature leads to decreased snow cover, nutrient runoff from land to sea, and increased bioavailability of nutrients on land, causing an increase in primary producers on land and sea (Wasley et al., 2006). In this context, it has been demonstrated in aquatic systems that an increase in primary productivity is vital in the sedimentation processes of POPs from the surface to the aquatic bottom through the biological pump (Larson et al., 2000; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2018), this process contributes mainly to the removal of POPs from the environment, despite the adverse effects of an increase in primary productivity in ecosystems (e.g., increase in organic matter). Thus, global warming in Antarctica not only implies a temperature change but also leads to multiple processes that can affect the biogeochemical dynamics of POPs, which plays an

essential role in the environmental fate of POPs. Because depending on the future effects of climate change, Antarctica can act as a secondary source of POPs through the re-volatilization of these compounds or as a sink, contributing to the decrease of their environmental levels. Therefore, future exploration of the impact of climate change is necessary and establishes the importance of establishing long-term monitoring networks.

3.4 Potential sources of bias

As presented here, several factors can be considered as sources of bias from historical data analysis. First, in the time frame of this study (1980-2021), analytical instrumentation and laboratory techniques exhibited dramatic change, particularly with the advent of advanced mass spectrometry (MS) over electron capture detection (ECD) or novel calibration techniques based on isotopically labeled standards (Azcune et al., 2022). Therefore, recent data are generated by more sophisticated techniques and modern laboratory QA/QC criteria, which need to be included in data reported before 2000. On the other hand, we also included studies using active and passive sampling, but no major differences in the values obtained were observed (See Tables 2.1 and 2.2).

The published information from Antarctica is reduced to a group of individual experiences in different geographical locations of international teams working in the field under different conditions and levels of competence that are difficult to obtain and analyze. One might expect that studies that show a strong track record in Antarctic research, reporting POP levels over a time series, might have greater validity due to constancy and consistency in both sampling and the types of analyses used (e.g., Larson et al., 1992; Baek et al., 2011; Hao et al., 2019).

In summary, the source of bias, related to the technological advancement of the analyses of the collected samples, could have relevance in the observed variability of the historical trends of HCB and HCH (see Fig. 2.1 A to C). In these cases, it is suggested to continue with dedicated monitoring of these POPs in the coming years to obtain robust observations and conclusions on the degradation of POPs in the Antarctic atmosphere.

4. Conclusion

In the present review, a clear trend of decreasing concentrations of PCBs and most targeted OCPs in the Antarctic atmosphere from 1980 to 2018 is documented. In response to the hypothesis raised historically about the decrease in atmospheric levels of historical POPs (Vecchiato et al., 2015). However, it opens the door to study new families of pollutants for which there is already analytical capacity not available in previous decades. In the case of HCH isomers, DDT and PCB congeners, high atmospheric concentrations were reported during 1990-1999 decade but these compounds were highly restricted since 1970s. After that date, a strong decrease was observed in the Antarctic atmosphere, which shows that the Stockholm Convention ban on POPs did have the intended impact on the (atmospheric) concentrations over time. However, these compounds are still ubiquitous in the Antarctic atmosphere with atmospheric half-lives of more than 3 years. On the other hand, the revised atmospheric levels of HCB show a decrease in the decade of its prohibition (1990), however, from the year 2000 onwards, they show strong fluctuations in literature, with values even higher than those reported in 1990. It is noteworthy to take into account, that a decrease of the atmospheric concentrations does not imply neither a decrease of the total POPs in Antarctica, an issue that will require future work. In fact, a re-emission of HCB and other POPs from environmental surfaces, such as water, soil, and snow, product of its high stability in the environment, potential sources of bias. Studies to date in Antarctica do not allow conclusions to be drawn about the influence of temperature on the environmental fate of POPs on the Antarctic continent. This is due to the lack of consistent time series data as historically conducted in the Arctic. Moreover, our results point to the importance of periodic monitoring and the need to establish monitoring networks with continuous sampling campaigns, not only with aim to monitor the legacy POPs, as well as to identify new pollutants that have the potential to reach Antarctica (e.g., new flame retardants, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), among others). There is increasing evidence of the presence of emerging compounds in different environmental matrices in Antarctica, however, the current surveillance of atmospheric pollutants is related to specific research groups, instead of coordinated efforts between countries with Antarctic presence, where continuous monitoring networks could be generated with the inclusion of various persistent toxic chemicals, as analogous to the efforts done by

the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program (AMAP), or the Integrated Atmospheric Deposition Network (IADN) in the Great Lakes.

Figure 2. 4. Atmospheric levels (pg/m³) of PCB-28 (A), PCB-52 (B), PCB-101 (C), PCB-118 (D), PCB-138 (E), PCB-153 (F) and PCB-180 (G), over time.

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Chapter 3

Occurrence and diffusive air-seawater exchanges of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica.

This chapter has been submitted for publication in Science of Total Environment (Ref Number STOTEN-D-22-32446).

Luarte, T., Hirmas-Olivares, A., Höfer, J., Giesecke, R., Mestre, M., Guajardo-Leiva, S., ... & Galbán-Malagón, C. Occurrence and Diffusive Air-Seawater Exchanges of Organochlorine Pesticides (Ocps) and Polychlorinated Biphenyls (Pcbs) in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica.

Abstract

We report the the levels of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in seawater and air, and the air-sea dynamics through diffusive exchange analysis from Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica, between November 2019 and January 30, 2020. Hexachlorobenzene (HCB) was the most abundant compound in both air and water with concentrations around $39 \pm 2.1 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$ and $3.2 \pm 2.4 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$ respectively. The most abundant PCB congener was PCB 11, with a mean of $3.16 \pm 3.7 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$ in air and $2.0 \pm 1.1 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$ in seawater. The fugacity gradient estimated for the OCP compounds indicate a predominance of net atmospheric deposition for HCB, α -HCH, γ -HCH, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE and close to equilibrium for the PeCB compound. The observed deposition of some OCs may be driven by the high biodegradation rates and/or settling fluxes contributing to the decrease of these compounds in surface water, supported by measured capacity of microbial consortium to degrade some of these compounds. The estimated fugacity gradients for PCBs showed differences between congeners, with net volatilization predominating for PCB-9, a trend close to equilibrium for PCB congeners 11, 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, and 153, and deposition for PCB 180. Snow amplification may play an important role for less hydrophobic PCBs, with volatilization predominating after snow/glacier melting. As hydrophobicity increases, the biological pump decreases the concentration of PCBs in seawater, reversing the fugacity gradient to atmospheric deposition. The study highlights the impact of climate change on the retreat of glaciers, which may affect the biogeochemistry of POPs, remobilizing those compounds previously deposited and turning the Antarctic continent into a secondary source of the more volatile POPs in coastal areas influenced by snow melting.

1. Introduction

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs) are compounds of anthropogenic origin, characterized by their low environmental degradation (Pennington, 2001) and their capacity to bioaccumulate in organisms and biomagnify through food webs (Fisk et al., 2001a; 2001b; Hop et al., 2002; Borga & Di Guardo, 2005). Due to their semi-volatile nature, they are subject to long-range transport (LRAT) through atmospheric transport and oceanic currents (Blais et al., 2007; Brown & Wania, 2008; Bengtson-Nash, 2011). In addition, due to their toxicity, they are harmful to wildlife and human health (Bourgeon et al., 2012; Brown et al., 2014). Some POPs are currently regulated internationally by the Stockholm Convention that aims to reduce and eliminate emissions to the atmosphere (UNECE, 1998; UNEP 2001; Denison, 2013).

Studies on POPs reveal that these compounds reach the Antarctic continent mainly through LRAT (Blais et al., 2007; Brown and Wania, 2008; Bengtson-Nash, 2011; Jurado and Dachs, 2008). However, other vectors of these substances have been described, such as ocean currents despite that the Antarctic Circumpolar Current that acts as a barrier limiting their transport (Bengtson-Nash et al., 2010), and to a lesser extent migratory biota (Braune et al., 2005; Wild et al., 2022). In addition, local sources of POPs (e.g., PCBs and HCB) have also been reported from research stations and tourist access points (Risebrough et al., 1990; Larsson et al., 1992; Hale et al., 2008; Corsolini et al., 2021), although these levels tend to have a limited impact, mainly contributing during summer season to an increase in ambient levels of POPs.

Low ambient temperatures in Antarctica play an essential role in the biogeochemical cycles of POPs, generating an increased partitioning of POPs from the atmosphere to seawater, soils, and snow, a process known as "cold trapping" (Wania & Mackay, 1996; Casal et al., 2019) favoring the exchange direction from the atmospheric compartment to others (Luarte et al., 2023). In this context, polar regions act as a net sink for most of the compounds under study, as an imbalance has been documented in estimates of diffusive air-seawater exchanges in which net deposition predominates over volatilization (Mackay & Wania & Mackay, 1995; Kallenborn et al., 1998; Dickhut et al., 2005; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Baek et al., 2011; Cabrerizo et al., 2017; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012, 2013a, 2013c; Montone et al., 2013). The direction of the air-seawater exchange gradient depends mainly on sea-water temperature (Mackay & Wania, 1995) and dissolved-phase POP concentration (Achman et al., 1993; Swackhamer & Skoglund,

1993; Stange & Swackhamer, 1994; Dachs et al., 1999). Sea-water concentration of POPs is strongly influenced by biogeochemical processes, which affect POPs cycles and thus their occurrence in aquatic systems (Dachs et al., 1999; Nizzetto et al., 2010; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012; Lammel et al., 2016; Tao et al., 2018). In this sense, Galbán-Malagón et al. (2013c) showed that organic matter sedimentation fluxes, hereinafter biological pump, decrease the concentrations of more hydrophobic POPs (i.e., $\text{Log } K_{ow} > 6.5$) from surface waters with high primary productivity. Whereas, for those compounds with lower hydrophobicity (i.e., lower $\text{Log } K_{ow} < 6.5$), microbial degradation may play an essential role in the depletion of POPs in aquatic environments and to the biological pump in a lesser extent (Berrojalbiz et al., 2011; & Luarte et al., 2022). However, the recorded patterns may likely be reversed due to rising temperatures caused by climate change; in this scenario, POPs that were trapped for decades in water, ice, and soil will start to volatilize, generating a secondary source of these compounds (Nizzetto et al., 2010; Ma et al., 2011; Cabrerizo et al., 2013), highlighting the importance of updated studies documenting the behavior of legacy POPs in polar areas.

Among legacy POPs, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine compounds, such as hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs) and hexachlorobenzene (HCB), among others, have often been studied as model compounds to understand the environmental fate, as well as the biogeochemical cycling of POPs in polar regions (Bengtson Nash, 2011; Galbán Malagón et al., 2013 b, c, d; Bigot et al., 2016; Wagner et al., 2019; Casal et al., 2019). The main objectives of the present study were i) determine the levels of POPs present in seawater and air, ii) elucidate the air-seawater dynamics using the fugacity ratio between the air and water iii) evaluate the different biogeochemical processes that may influence the behavior of the studied compounds.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Air and seawater sampling

We collected 25 air samples and 12 seawater samples periodically from November 30th (2019), to January 30th (2020) at Fildes Bay (“Base Escudero” 62°20’S, 58°23’W), in King George Island, South Shetlands Archipelago, Antarctica (Fig. 3.1; Table S3.1, Annex B). Atmospheric samples were collected using a high-volume air sampler (device model: MCV: CAV-A/HF, Collbató, Spain), with an approximate volume of 1000 m³ per sample. The high-volume sampler separates aerosol by filtering the air through a quartz microfiber filter (QMA 203×254 mm, 1- μ m nominal pore size, Whatman International Ltd., Maidstone, England), while gas-phase POPs are retained on polyurethane foam (PUF, 100 mm diameter×120 mm, Klaus Ziemer GmbH, Germany). This sampling methodology has been previously described and widely used in remote and pristine environments (Nizzetto et al., 2012; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012; Cabrerizo et al., 2014; Tuca et al., 2020; Luarte et al., 2022), presenting adequate performance. In parallel, seawater samples were obtained directly from the bay at a depth of 5 meters using a water pumping system. For each sample, a volume of approximately 200 L (see table S2 of Annex B for details) passed through a filter holder equipped with a GF/F filter (142 mm diameter, 0.7 μ m pore size (Whatman), and then into a stainless-steel column containing XAD-2 resin (SUPELCO). This procedure was carried out at a speed of 0.4 L min⁻¹, which has been shown to prevent the breakthrough of POPs in the dissolved phase (Berrojalbiz et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Luarte et al., 2022). After sampling, the air and seawater samples collected were kept at 4°C and -20 °C, respectively, until their subsequent extraction and instrumental analysis.

Figure 3. 1. map of the air-water sampling points used in this study in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica.

2.2 Sample preparation and instrumental analysis

Before chemical analysis, samples were spiked with PCBs and OCPs surrogate (internal) standards (13C6: γ -HCH, PeCB, HCB, 13C12: p,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDD, p,p'-DDE, PCB28, PCB52, PCB101, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180, Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, MA, USA). Subsequently, air and water samples were extracted using a soxhlet system (Büchi System B-811 automatic extractor) PUF, QMA and GF/F samples for 40 minutes with 150 mL of DCM. XAD-2 samples were air-dried first, then extracted 3x15 minutes with 3x120 mL of DCM. All extracts were preconcentrated to 10 mL under gentle stream of nitrogen, using a LabEva concentrator and then divided into fractions (10 % and 90 %) by weighing on KERN weighing scales. A total of 90 % fractions of extracts for PCBs and OCPs analysis were cleaned using destructive acidic-silica gel glass column, containing 1 g of activated silica gel, 8 g of 44% H₂SO₄ silica gel, 1 g of deactivated silica gel and 1 cm of anhydrous Na₂SO₄, eluted with 40 mL of hexane/dichloromethane 1:1. A volume of 50 μ L of nonane was added to eluates as a keeper solvent and samples were concentrated in LabEva to final volume of 50 μ L. instrumental analysis samples were spiked with 13C12-PCB95 syringe standard for determination of % recovery of surrogate (internal) standards.

PCBs and OCPs were analyzed on 8890 GC (Agilent Technologies, USA) equipped with a 60 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m Rxi-5Sil-MS column (Restek, FR) coupled

to a 7000D tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS; Agilent, USA) operated in electron ionization mode at 70 eV. The GC temperature program was 80 °C (1.5 min hold), then 40 °C min⁻¹ to 200 °C (18 min hold), and finally 5 °C min⁻¹ to 305 °C. Inlet temperature was 280 °C. Injection volume was 3 µl in splitless mode. Carrier gas was helium with flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. Temperature of the transfer line was 310 °C and 250 °C of the ion source. Mass spectrometer was operating in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode with nitrogen as collision gas with flow rate of 1.5 mL min⁻¹.

The target compounds were PCBs (PCB9, PCB11, PCB28, PCB52, PCB101, PCB118, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180), HCHs (α -HCH, β -HCH, and γ -HCH), DDTs (p,p' -DDE, p,p' -DDD, p,p' - DDT, o,p' -DDE, o,p' -DDD, o,p' -DDE), hexachlorobenzene (HCB) and pentachlorobenzene (PeCB). PCBs and OCPs were quantified with an external calibration of eight points with concentration from 1 ngmL⁻¹ to 1000 ngmL⁻¹ and linearity was maintained in the whole range. Native PCBs and OCPs were quantified using surrogate (internal) standards (isotope-dilution method).

2.3. Quality Assurance and Quality Control (QA/QC)

To avoid traces of POPs, prior to sampling, the PUFs were extracted with hexane:acetone (1:1) for 48 hours, packed in aluminum foil and dried under vacuum in desiccators, and finally stored in double sealed plastic bags, until their subsequent use in the field. The QMA filters were packed in aluminum foil, burned at 450°C for 4 hours, and kept in sealed plastic bags. Nitrile gloves and tweezers previously cleaned with acetone were used to handle the PUFs and QMA filters. Meanwhile, the XAD inside the column was pre-cleaned with dichloromethane:hexane (3:1) and subsequently kept cold (-4°C) with 200 mL of methanol.

For blank collection, the QMA filter was placed on the head of the high-volume sampler used for sampling for one minute. A GFF filter was also used for water filtration. Subsequently, one blank per 10 samples was extracted and analyzed using the methodology described above. All blanks analyzed yielded levels below the detection limit for all compounds. Instrumental limits of quantification (iLOQ) were calculated from the lowest calibration point as a quantity yielding signal to noise S S/N = 10 (iLOQ) (Table S3.6, Annex B).

2.4. Diffusive air-seawater exchange

To calculate the air-seawater diffusive exchange, first we estimated the freely dissolved concentration (C_{TD}) in water following the methodology used in previous studies (Totten et al., 2001; Rowe et al., 2007; García-Flores et al., 2005; Nizzetto et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Luarte et al., 2022), with the equation (1):

$$C_{TD} = \frac{C_W}{1+10^{-9} \cdot K_{OW} DOC} \quad (1)$$

Where C_W is the POP concentration measured in water (pg L^{-1}) and K_{OW} is the octanol-water partition constant, dissolved organic carbon (DOC) in mg L^{-1} and the octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{OW}) corrected for temperature (see text S1; García-Flores et al., 2005). For DOC we used a concentration of 0.7 mg L^{-1} , following previous studies in the same area (e.g. Doval et al., 2002 and Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b), the 10^{-9} correction factor is for transforming units from mg to pg . When concentrations were over LOD and below LOQ we divided the value of LOQ by 2 to estimate the fugacity gradient.

The net direction of air-seawater exchange was determined using the air-seawater fugacity ratio ($f_w f_a^{-1}$) as follows:

$$\frac{f_w}{f_a} = \frac{C_{TD} H'}{C_G} \quad (2)$$

Where C_{TD} is the concentration of freely dissolved POPs in seawater (pg m^{-3} , see below), C_G is the gas-phase POP concentration (pg m^{-3}), and H' is Henry's law constant, dimensionless and corrected for salinity and temperature, for the latter the enthalpy of phase change (ΔU_{AW}) was used for each POP. In contrast, for the salinity correction the constant 1.3 was used as a correction factor to account for the effect of salinity on the solubility of POPs in seawater (for more details, see text S2, Annex B). In the case of C_G concentrations lower than LOQ but higher than LOD we used the LOQ divided by two to estimate fugacity gradient using a similar approach C_{TD} Haga clic aquí para escribir texto.

Due to uncertainty in air-seawater partition coefficients such as C_G , C_{TD} and H' (Bruhn et al., 2003), logarithm-transformed $f_w f_a^{-1}$ was used to indicate that the compounds are close to air-seawater equilibrium (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b). Values of fugacity ratios higher than 0.5 and lower than -0.5 indicate that the net direction of air-seawater exchange are net volatilization and net deposition, respectively, the values

falling within the range -0.5 and 0.5 are in the range of uncertainty that implies that the exchange is close to equilibrium between the air and water.

2.5. Microbial degradation

To evaluate the effect of microorganisms in the water column on the concentration of POPs, biodegradation losses (F_{DegM} , $\text{ng m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) were estimated following the equation used by Galban-Malagón et al. (2013c) and Luarte et al. (2022):

$$F_{DegM} = h \times k_{DegM} \times C_{TD} \quad (3)$$

where, h is the depth within the water column (~ 5 m), k_{DegM} is the degradation constant rate in water (d^{-1}), which was calculated from the half-life in seawater for each POP (see Table S3.5, Annex B).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Atmospheric levels of target OCPs and PCBs

The atmospheric levels for OCPs (HCB, α -HCH, γ -HCH, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE and PeCB) in this study ranged from 0.07 to 42.3 pg m^{-3} . The mean concentrations of the target OCP isomers decreased in the following order: HCB ($39 \pm 2.1 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PeCB ($7.2 \pm 1 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > γ -HCH ($0.6 \pm 0.6 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > 4,4'-DDT ($0.3 \pm 0.6 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > 4,4'-DDE ($0.2 \pm 0.7 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > α -HCH ($0.1 \pm 0.03 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) (Fig. 3.2). The high atmospheric levels of HCB accounted for 82% of total OCPs and 74% of total target POPs in the present study. Similarly, HCB has been reported by other authors as the most abundant OCP, and even the most abundant POP. In Antarctic regions, HCB has been detected most frequently in the atmosphere (Kallenborn et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2018; Hao et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020). The HCB levels detected in this study are lower than those reported by Bidleman et al. (1993) in East Antarctica and Hao et al. (2019) on King George Island and higher than the concentrations reported by Montone et al. (2005) on Ross Island, Gambaro et al. (2005) and Cincinelli et al. (2009) in Terra Nova Bay, Dickhut et al. (2005), Cabrerizo et al. (2016) in Antarctic Plateau and Wu et al. 2020 in Antarctica marginal seas (Table 3.1) and within a similar range to the atmospheric levels reported by Kallenborn et al. (1998) in Signy Island (South Orkney Islands), Galbán-Malagón et al. (2013b) in Bellinghousen Sea, Kallenborn et al. (2013) in Troll Station and Queen Maud Land and Pozo et al. (2017) in the Ross Sea (Table 3.1).

On the other hand, the levels of Σ_2 HCHs are well below the levels previously reported by Tanabe et al. (1982) in the Southern Ocean and Kallenborn et al. (1998) in Newfoundland Bay (Table 3.1) and are within the range reported by more recent studies conducted in the Southern Ocean, Ross Sea, King George Island, and in the Antarctic marginal seas (Bigot et al., 2016; Pozo et al., 2017; Hao et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020) (Table 3.1). This could be interpreted as a decreasing trend in the levels of these compounds compared with previous decades (1980-2018; Tanabe et al., 1982; 1983; Bidleman et al., 1993; Kallenborn et al., 1998; Jantunen et al., 2004; Montone et al., 2005; Dickhut et al., 2005; Gambaro et al., 2005; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Baek et al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Khairy et al., 2016; Kallenborn et al., 2013; Pozo et al., 2017; Cabrerizo et al., 2016; Bigot et al., 2016; Hao et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020) (Luarte et al. 2023). The recorded levels of the 4,4'-DDT and 4,4'-DDE isomers are in the same

range of those reported by Bidleman et al. (1993), Kallenborn et al. (1998), Pozo et al. (2017), Wu et al. (2020) and Hao et al. (2019) (Table 3.1).

Figure 3. 2. Air concentration of OCs (pg m^{-3}).

Table 3. 1. HCB and HCHs levels (pg m⁻³) in Antarctic atmosphere. Σn indicates the number of isomers included in the study.

Sampling area	Year	HCB	a-HCH	γ -HCH	Σ HCHs	4,4-DDE	4,4 DDT	Reference
Queen Maud land	1980-1981				90-170			Tanabe et al., 1982
Queen Maud land	1981-1982				44-170			Tanabe et al., 1983
Cape town and Newmayer Station	1999		0.36	0.15				Lakaschus et al., 2002
Ross Island	1988 - 1999			25.8 (0.5 - 118)		1	2	Larson et al., 1992
East Antarctica	1990	62.6 (40-78)	3.2 (2.8-3.6)	2.4 (1.1-5.6)	5.7			Bidleman et al., 1993
Signy Island	1994 - 1995		2.8	21.8	26.97	0.4	0.2	Kallenborn et al., 1998
East Antarctica	1997 - 1998		1.06 (0.81 - 1.4)					Jantunen et al., 2004
Terranova bay	1993	21 (n.d - 28)			13 (5 - 20.0)			Kallenborn et al., 1998
Ross Island	1995	(<0.6 - 25.3)			3.9-32.5	9.2	8.1	Montone et al., 2005
west of the Antarctic Peninsula and southwest of Adelaide Island	2001 - 2002	19.4 (<5 - 32.1)	0.3 (<0.05-0.52)	0.755 (<0.02-2.98)				Dickhut et al. 2005
Terra Nova Bay	2003-2004	11.4 (6.0 - 20)			0.8 (0.3 - 1.2)			Gambaro et al., 2005
Terra Nova Bay	2003-2004	11.4 (5.93 - 20.4)			0.22 (0.1 - 0.35)			Cincinelli et al., 2009
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	2005-2009							Baek et al., 2011
South Scotia Sea	2008	8.1 (2.18 -15.82)	1.7(0.06-5.84)	4.6 (1.5-7.1)				et a., 2013b
Wedell	2009	19.5 (2.4 - 30.1)	0.16 (0.05-2.09)	0.84 (0.1-1.87)				et a., 2013b
Bransfield sea	2009	16.7 (3.3 - 34.24)	0.14 (0.04-0.46)	1.15 (0.2-3)				et a., 2013b
Bellingshausen	2009	42.9 (27.31 - 49.71)	0.26 (0.22-0.16)	0.14 (0.07-0.19)				et a., 2013b
Palmer station	2010	34 (26.2 – 37.7)	0.81 – 1.68	0.87 – 2.31				Khairy et al., 2016
Station troll / Queen Maud Land	2010	22.9						Kallenborn et al. 2013
Ross Sea	2010-2011	22.8 (0.8 - 50)	0.5 (n.d-0.5)	n.d	0.5 (n.d-0.5)			Pozo et al., 2017
Antarctic Plateau	2011	(0.67-2.7)		BD-2.7				Cabrerizo et al. 2016
Antarctic marginal seas	2013-2014	2.6 (0.081 - 10)			(n.d - 6.8)	0.35	0.12	Wu et al., 2020
Southern Ocean between Australia and Antarctica	2014	(<22 - 35)	<0.13-1.1	<0.70-4.3	n.d - 3.65	<0.15-0.44	<7,8	Bigot et al., 2016
King George Island	2012-2018	163 (99.2 - 252)	1.4 (0.5-13.6)	0.1-7.9	0.7 - 22.3	0.6	0.24	Hao et al., 2019
Fildes Bay	2019-2020	39 (34.5-42.3)	0.12 (0.08-0.2)	0.6 (0.3-3.4)	0.7 (0.4-3.5)	0.2 (0.07-3.4)	0.3 (<LOQ-2.8)	This study

Air concentrations of Σ_9 PCBs (PCBs 9, 11, 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180) ranged from 1.6 to 20.7 pg m^{-3} ; mean concentrations decreased following the order: PCB 11 ($3.16 \pm 3.7 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 28 ($0.44 \pm 0.6 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 52 ($0.37 \pm 0.5 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 101 ($0.18 \pm 0.2 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 153 ($0.16 \pm 1.1 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 138 ($0.1 \pm 0.1 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 9 ($0.1 \pm 0.06 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 118 ($0.08 \pm 0.09 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) > PCB 180 ($0.05 \pm 0.04 \text{ pg m}^{-3}$) (Fig. 3.3). The most abundant congener in the air was PCB 11 representing 68% of the total atmospheric PCBs in the study site. Our results agree with previous data (Choi et al., 2008; Baek et al., 2011; Li et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2017), showing high levels of PCB-11 as the most abundant congener present in the atmosphere over King George Island. This compound's primary source is from pigments, especially diarylide yellow (Rodenburg et al., 2010; Shang et al., 2014). Considering the high values of the PCB-11 congener reported in this and other studies, further studies are required to report its source and toxicity. Nevertheless, the more volatile POPs are those showing higher snow-melt air fugacity ratios (Casal et al. 2019), and thus the higher predominance of PCB11 is consistent with re-mobilization of historical reservoirs (see below). On the other hand, the concentrations of 7 indicator PCBs (PCB-28, -52, 101, 118, 138, 153, and -180) ranged from 0.4 to 9.9 pg m^{-3} , which are within a similar range previously reported in the Antarctic atmosphere by Kallenborn et al. (1998), Li et al. (2012a,b), Pozo et al. (2017) and Wang et al. (2015; 2017), and lower for the levels reported by Larson et al. (1992), Montone et al. (2001; 2003), Baek et al. (2011), Khairy et al. (2016), Galbán-Malagón et al. (2013c), Wang et al. (2017), and Hao et al. (2019) (Table 3.2).

Figure 3. 3. Air concentration of PCBs (pg m^{-3}).

Table 3. 2. PCBs levels ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in Antarctic atmosphere. Σn indicates the number of congeners included in the study.

Sampling area	Year	ΣPCBs	Σn	Reference
Ross Island	1988 - 1990	15.2	6	Larson et al. 1992
King George Island	1993 - 1994	20.8 (12.09 - 42.8)	10	Montone et al., 2001
Signy Island	1994 - 1995	(0.01-17.2)	22	Kallenborn et al., 1998
Ross Island	1995	62.4	11	Montone et al., 2005
King George Island	1996-1996	37.4 (12.1 - 92.6)	10	Montone et al., 2003
Terra Nova Bay	2003-2004	1.06 (0.61-1.78)	61	Gambaro et al., 2005
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	2005-2009	60.3(22.8 - 87.1)	11	Baek et al., 2011
Ny-Ålesund, King George Island, and Chuuk	2005-2009	19.8 (11.1-31.9)	205	Baek et al., 2011
ICEPOS	2005	16.84 (7.12- 25.65)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
South Scotia Sea	2008	45.13 (6.2 - 78.9)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
Antarctic peninsula	2009	12.13 (1.8- 38.1)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
Polish beach	2009	(2.1 - 3.1)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
Livingston Island	2009	7.23 (3.5 12.9)	25	Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013c
King George Island	2009 - 2010	1.142	7	Li et al 2012
King George Island	2009 - 2010	36.837	19	Li et al 2012
King George Island, Antarctica.	2009 - 2010	4.34	7	Li et al. 2012/2
Station troll / Queen Maud Land	2010	0.5	32	Kallenborn et al., 2013
Palmer station	2010	12	29	Khairy et al., 2016
Ross Sea	2010-2011	0.46 (0.14-1.13)	7	Pozo et al. 2017
Antarctic Plateau	2011	(0.8-27)	26	Cabrerizo et al. 2016
King George Island	2011-2014	5.39 (0.91-35.9)	7	Wang et al. 2017
King George Island	2011-2014	5.87- 72.7 (26.1)	20	Wang et al. 2017
King George Island	2010-2018	10.4 (1.5 - 29.7)	19	Hao et al., 2019
Antarctic marginal seas	2013-2014	1.1 (nd-6.7)	14	Wu et al. 2020
King George Island and Ardley Island		0.078 (nd - 0.137)	6	Wang et al. 2015
Fildes Bay	2019-2020	1.3 (0.4-9.6)	7	This study
Fildes Bay	2019-2020	4.6 (1.6-30.7)	9	This study

3.2. Concentrations of target OCPs and PCBs in seawater

The levels recorded in surface waters of OCPs (HCB, α -HCH, γ -HCH, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE and PeCB) ranged from 0.2-8.33 pg L^{-1} , where the HCB isomer showed the highest concentrations ($3.2 \pm 2.4 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$) followed by PeCB ($3.1 \pm 2.7 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$), and γ -HCH ($1.5 \pm 1.0 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$) (Fig 3.2C), which represented 28%, 27% and, 13% of the total OCPs in seawater, respectively. The seawater levels reported for the α -HCH, 4,4'-DDT and 4,4'-DDE isomers in this study did not exceed 0.6 pg L^{-1} (Fig. 3.4). HCB concentrations are in the range reported in Antarctic seawater by other studies conducted in the Wedell Sea, Bransfield Strait, Bellingshausen Sea, South Scotia Sea (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b), and relatively lower than those reported near Ross Island (Cincinelli et al., 2009), and the Queen Maud land (Bigot et al., 2016) (Table 3.3). The levels of HCHs and DDTs isomers are in a similar range to those reported in different areas of Antarctica (see Table 3.3).

Figure 3. 4. Sea-water concentration of OCPs (pg L^{-1}).

The Σ_9 PCBs concentrations (PCBs 9, 11, 28, 52, 138, 153 and 180) ranged 0.09-1.6 pg L^{-1} . The highest mean concentration recorded in surface water was $2.0 \pm 1.1 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$ for PCB 11, followed by $1.3 \pm 1.0 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$ for PCB 9 and $0.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$ for PCB 28 (Fig. 3.5), which represented, respectively, 45%, 29% and 15% of the total PCBs present in surface seawater. PCB congeners 52 and 153 displayed lower mean concentrations of 0.06 ± 0.04 and, $0.04 \pm 0.0004 \text{ pg L}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 3.2D). The other target PCB concentrations in this study (PCBs 101, 118, 138 and 180) were below the quantification limit (Table S3.7). The values of Σ_9 PCBs in surface seawater were similar to the values reported in Wedell Sea, Bransfield Strait, Bellinghausen Sea, and South Scotia Sea by Galbán-Malagón et al. (2013c) and well below the levels reported in Terranova Bay (Fuoco et al., 2005), Ross Sea (Fuoco et al., 2009) and Fildes peninsula (Zhang et al., 2016, and Gao et al., 2018) (Table 3.3).

It is important to note that PCB-11 was the congener with the highest concentrations in the atmosphere and seawater. However, to our knowledge, prior studies on this compound only analyzed air samples (see above), and there are no records of PCB-11 levels in aquatic systems, but as noted above, this is consistent with the amplification potential of snow reservoirs of POPs.

Figure 3. 5. Sea-water concentration of PCBs (pg L^{-1}).

Table 3. 3. OCP and PCBs levels (pg L⁻¹) in Antarctic water. Σn indicates the number of congeners included in the study.

Sampling area	Year	HCB	α -HCH	γ -HCH	Σ HCHs	4,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDE	Σ PCBs	Reference
Terranova Bay	1997-1998							(30-120)	Fuoco et al., 2005
Ross Sea	1997-2003							50	Fuoco et al., 2009
Ross Sea	2003-2004	11.4 (5.9-20.4)	0.2 (0.1-0.4)	0.56 (0.2-1.1)					Cincinelli et al., 2009
Wedell	2009	0.97 (0.4-1.6)	0.26 (0.2-0.3)	1.0 (0.4-1.7)	6.3 (1.3-11.5)			1.4 (1.3-1.5)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b
Bransfiel	2009	0.4 (0.2-0.6)	0.2 (0.09-0.3)	0.4 (0.3-0.8)	1.5 (1.3-12.3)			1.2 (1.2-1.5)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b
Bellinghausen	2009	0.3 (0.2-0.3)	0.2 (0.1-0.3)	0.8 (0.5-1.3)	1.3 (1.2-2.2)			2.2 (1.8-3.2)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b
South Scotia	2009	0.4 (0.3-0.6)	0.2 (0.1-0.4)	0.8 (0.6-1.2)	1.4 (1.2-2.1)			1.4 (0.7-1.9)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b
Fides peninsula	2013-2014							810-3160	Zhang et al., 2016
Southern Ocean, Australia and Antarctica	2014	(2.6-4.1)	(2-4.4)	(0.7-1.9)		(0.3-3.2)	0.6-1.8)		Bigot et al., 2016
Fides peninsula	2015-2016							(390-1500)	Xhiazon et al., 2018
Coast of Antarctica			0.06 (ND-0.28)	0.01 (ND-0.01)	0.25				Vudamala et al., 2023
Fildes Bay	2019-2020	3.1 (0.9-6.9)	0.6 (<LOQ- 1.3)	1.5 (0.2 - 3.3)	2.1 (0.47 -4.6)	0.6 (<LOQ-0.9)	0.4 (<LOQ-0.7)	3.7 (0.8-8.1)	This study

3.3. Diffusive air-sea exchanges

Estimation of fugacity ratios ($\log f_w f_a^{-1}$) performed for OCP isomers revealed a predominance of net atmospheric deposition for HCB, α -HCH, γ -HCH, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE isomers (Fig. 3.6A). In contrast, PeCB was close to equilibrium between atmospheric and surface water levels (Fig. 3.6A). The air-seawater imbalance reported in this study for HCHs has been widely reported in other studies conducted in the Southern Ocean, which in agreement with our study, atmospheric deposition of α -HCH and γ -HCH (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Dickhut et al., 2005; Xie et al., 2011; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Bigot et al., 2016; Casal et al., 2019). On the other hand, we found net deposition for HCB similarly to what was reported in previous studies (Galbán-Malagón et al. 2013b; Dickhut et al. 2005). However, it was also found that this compound was close to equilibrium in other areas like the Ross Sea (Cincinelli et al. (2009). To our knowledge, no air-seawater fugacity relationships have been reported for DDT and PeCB in the Southern Ocean. However, for DDT isomers, atmospheric deposition has been reported from Izmir Bay, Turkey (Odabasi et al., 2008), the Great Lakes, Canada and the United States (Khairy et al., 2014) and the Yangtze River estuary, China (Li et al., 2017), concurring with our results.

The estimated $\log f_w f_a^{-1}$ for PCBs showed differences between congeners, with a predominance of net volatilization from surface waters to the atmosphere for PCBs 9 (Fig. 3.6B). Whereas a trend close to equilibrium was observed for PCB congeners 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, and 153 (Fig. 3.6B). Finally, PCB-180 showed a predominance of net deposition (Fig. 3.6B). Previous studies in Antarctica reported that atmospheric deposition dominates PCB volatilization in open waters of the Southern Ocean (Galbán Malagón et al., 2013c), while in coastal areas, volatilization is the dominant process (Casal et al., 2019). The air-seawater imbalances documented in this study can be related to biotic and abiotic factors interaction with snow-melt sources, as described below.

Figure 3. 6. Estimated air-to-water fugacity ratios ($\text{Log } f_{w/a}^{-1}$) for OCs (A) and PCBs (B)

3.4. Factors associated with air-water disequilibrium.

The predominance of atmospheric deposition for most OCs vs. sea water concentrations may be due to the degradation processes and/or settling fluxes of these pollutants in the surface waters of the Southern Ocean. Degradation processes included the basic hydrolysis degradation, since Antarctic coastal waters present a pH range of 7.9-8.3 that could favor and enhance the hydrolytic degradation pathway (Kapsenberg et al., 2015). However, this pathway has been proven to represent a minor degradation pathway in Antarctic waters (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b, d) and in the great lakes (Biddleman et al., 2021). Another relevant degradation pathway is the one conducted by microbial communities which could significantly affect the levels of HCHs in the waters. Degradation by microbes may result in relatively low levels of OCs in seawater (Bigot et al., 2016), and this has been suggested as an important pathway in the case of HCHs in Antarctic and Arctic surface waters (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b and d) and great lakes (Bidleman et al., 2021). Our estimations of biodegradation fluxes due to microbial activity in Fildes Bay ranged from 5.9 to 0.3 ng m⁻² d⁻¹ (Table S3.9). Our estimated biodegradation fluxes could be significantly affecting water concentrations, which would consequently increase the air-to-water fugacity gradient. This suggests that biodegradation processes may be playing a key role in the net deposition recorded for the analyzed HCHs, in fact the degradation fluxes estimated for γ -HCH were on average 2.39 ngm⁻²d⁻¹, and for α -HCH 5.91 ng m⁻²d⁻¹. However, to verify this, it is important to know if the bacterial consortia present in the water column has the functional potential to degrade these compounds. Thus, we searched for genes from the metabolic pathways involved in the HCHs degradation in metagenomic and metatranscriptomic data available in the area (See Annex Text S3, Annex B). The enzymatic breakdown of HCHs involves four genes *linA*, *linB*, *linC*, and *linD* (Nagata et al., 1999; Tabata et al., 2011; Shrivastava et al., 2015). We focused on the *linA* and *linB* genes involved in the two initial and key steps of the degradation pathway. Additionally, the protein encoded by *linA* catalyzes a stereoselective dehydrochlorination of hexachlorocyclohexanes, only being able to degrade the alpha and gamma stereoisomers. The gene *linA* encodes a Gamma-hexachlorocyclohexane dehydrochlorinase that dechlorinates the HCH molecule into 1,3,4,6-tetrachloro-1,4-cyclohexadiene, while *linB* encodes for a haloalkane dehalogenase that metabolizes the 1,3,4,6-tetrachloro-1,4-cyclohexadiene into 2,5-dichloro-2,5-cyclohexadiene-1,4-diol. To determine if these genes were active in the

microbial community, we used metatranscriptomes obtained from sea water in the same area during summer 2020-2021 (publicly available at European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), accession number PRJEB6240). The results from the examined metatranscriptomes showed that both genes, *linA* and *linB* were active in the studied area (Fig. 3.7). Transcripts found for *linA* were an order of magnitude more abundant than those of *linB*. The narrow substrate specificity of *linA* suggests that the microbial degradation of HCHs is active during the summer in the studied area and could play a role in the environmental fate of HCHs (Nagata et al., 1993, 2001). All this agrees with previous works suggesting the role of bacterial communities in the fate of HCHs in the water column in polar areas (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a; 2013d; Bigot et al., 2016). However, this metabolic pathway could be different depending on the racemic mixture of HCHs as suggested for α -HCH (Harner et al., 1999, 2000; Law et al., 2004).

Figure 3. 7. The heatmap shows the relative abundance of transcripts for the *linA* and *linB* genes in the different samples. The samples are arranged in rows and the genes are arranged in columns. The color of each cell represents the logarithmic transformation of the gene relative abundance in Counts Per Million (CPM) in logarithm scale. The dendrograms show the hierarchical clustering of the samples or gene replicates according to their distance based on the relative abundance of gene transcripts.

On the other hand, for compounds that show low or no microbial degradation, such as PCBs, the estimated imbalance for PCBs 9 and 180 can be due to various and different processes. The net deposition of PCB 180 could be due to the transfer through the food web, or by the direct removal through the biological carbon pump that might be actively sequestering pollutants from surface waters and transporting them to the seafloor, lowering their concentrations in surface waters, due to the relatively high hydrophobicity of these pollutants ($\log K_{OW} > 6$; Table S3.5) (Cincinelli et al., 2009; Dachs et al., 2002; and Galbán Malagón et al., 2012; 2013). However, the role of the biological pump could also prevent the trophic transfer of these compounds through the food web, as suggested in previous studies conducted in Antarctic waters where the rate of the settling fluxes could exceed significantly the transfer from primary producers to consumers (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2018) for dioxin-like PCBs and dioxins. Further, the influence of the biological pump can be evidenced by plotting $\log f_w f_a^{-1}$ versus the temperature-corrected octanol-water partition constant ($\log K_{OW}$) (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c). The more hydrophobic compounds are prone to uptake by the organic matter production by primary producers that settles through the water column because of low solubility of these compounds which also is lower in Antarctic cold waters increasing $\log K_{OW}$ by a factor of two in average. As shown above there is an imbalance between the concentrations in the gas phase and the dissolved phase for some compounds and this also was illustrated in previous works for OC and PCBs (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c) thus we performed a piecewise linear regression analysis between the two variables that showed a slight negative but not significant ($p > 0.05$) relationship for compounds with a $\log K_{OW} < 6.5$, whereas for compounds with a $\log K_{OW} > 6.5$ (more hydrophobic congeners) the decrease in $\log f_w f_a^{-1}$ was steeper (Fig. 3.8). However, we have a low number of compounds compared to other studies, so the statistical power of the regression is low but agrees with previous studies showing that in the case of compounds with $\log K_{OW}$ higher than 6.5 there is a significant settling flux of these compounds (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013c). This suggests that the biological pump may remove efficiently PCBs with high hydrophobicity values from surface water and then exporting them to the seafloor, which in turn increases the air-seawater fugacity gradient for PCB-180, the congener with the highest atmospheric deposition trend recorded in this study.

Figure 3. 8. Estimated air-to-water fugacity ratios ($\text{Log } f_w f_a^{-1}$) vs $\text{Log } K_{OW}$

The net volatilization of the highly volatile PCB 9 may be related to remobilization processes. Climate change and rising temperatures are enhancing glacier retreat in West Antarctica (Turner et al., 2005; Chapman et al., 2007; Rückamp et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2017; Dryac & Enderlin, 2020). This situation may exert a significant influence on POPs concentrations in coastal waters due to snow/ice acting as reservoirs of POPs that are released into the environment after snow/ice melt, amplifying these compounds in soils and mainly in aquatic systems. (Burniston et al., 2007; Geisz et al., 2008; Casal et al., 2019). In this context, Fildes Bay receives significant ice inputs from Collins Glacier (see Figure 3.1), which may respond to the increased concentrations reported for PCB 9 in surface seawater, causing an increase in air-seawater fugacity, with a predominance of volatilization. The fugacity amplification potential is higher for the more volatile chemicals (Casal et al. 2019).

Moreover, glacial meltwater carries micro-nutrients (e.g., iron) (Höfer et al., 2019; Hopwood et al., 2019) that are released into Fildes Bay surface waters (Krause et al., 2021), while enhancing water column stability within the bay (e.g., Höfer et al., 2019). Nutrient inputs and water column stratification due to glacial melting trigger massive algal blooms in Antarctic coastal waters (Mitchell & Holm-Hansen, 1991; Jones et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020; Rozema et al., 2017; Brown et al., 2019) including King George Island and Fildes Bay (Höfer et al., 2019; Wasilowska et al., 2022; Schloss et al., 2014). This enhances primary productivity of Antarctic coastal waters during spring and summer (e.g., Kim et al., 2018) and thus increases the role of the biological carbon pump that removes POPs from surface waters and transport them to the seafloor through sinking

particles (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013), which in turn decreases the concentration of POPs across the water column. Such nutrient inputs from ice/snow melting, can also modify the microbial communities, and the extend of microbial degradation, as shown recently for PAHs (Iriarte et al. 2023). However, this primary productivity is highly seasonal since this process occurs primarily during spring-summer and the condensation and resupply of organic compounds occurs during the whole year by means of transport. Thus, the action of the biodegradation coupled to biological pump and the snow amplification may explain the air sea water exchange of this compounds registered for most OCs, and the low levels of PCBs in surface waters that did not exceed the limit of quantification (PCB 101, 118, 138, and 180).

4. Conclusions

We determined the air and seawater concentrations of POPs simultaneously assessing air-sea fugacity ratios ($\text{Log } f_w f_a^{-1}$) in King George Island. The air-seawater fugacity dynamics recorded in this study reveal the importance of certain biotic and abiotic factors on the biogeochemistry and environmental fate of POPs. For example, the deposition documented for some studied OCs is likely due to the possible biodegradation of these compounds in surface waters. This was also supported by the metatranscriptomic data reporting the presence and activity of genes involved in key steps of the enzymatic degradation of HCHs. This evidence in turn revealed the importance of this process and the coupling between the biological pump and a degradative pump. Concerning $\text{Log } f_w f_a^{-1}$ results for PCBs, these showed differences between congeners. For example, for less hydrophobic compounds, such as PCB-9, extending compounds to snow and ice melt from receding glaciers is essential in increasing air-seawater fugacity, with volatilization predominating over deposition. On the other hand, as hydrophobicity increases, the biological component of the carbon pump begins to act by decreasing the concentrations of PCBs present in seawater, with a substantial effect on PCBs exceeding a $\text{Log } K_{ow} > 6.5$, as evidenced in this study with the atmospheric deposition of PCB-180. This study highlights the effect that glacial melting has on the biogeochemistry of POPs, where snow/ice melting may likely cause the re-emission of compounds previously kept in the ice. This might turn Antarctica into a (seasonal) secondary source of POPs with lower hydrophobicity. Therefore, continuous monitoring is needed to assess the environmental fate of these compounds, as well as to investigate and regulate their current atmospheric sources in Antarctica.

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Chapter 4

Levels of Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and Organochlorine Pesticides (OCPs) in phytoplankton and zooplankton and estimation of bioconcentration, bioaccumulation and biomagnification factors in Fildes Bay, Antarctica

This chapter is under preparation for submission to Environmental Pollution

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Abstract

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs), such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), are a group of toxic compounds of anthropogenic origin, which were widely used in the agricultural and industrial sectors, and even in domestic activities during the third industrial revolution. In this study, we report the levels of PCBs and OCPs present in phytoplankton and zooplankton from samples obtained in Fildes Bay, Antarctica, from December 2019 to the end of January 2020, and then use the CTD values obtained in the previous chapter, to estimate BCF, BAF, and BMF, to evaluate the accumulation processes, performing a nonparametric linear regression between BCF, BAF and BMF and the temperature-corrected Log KOW values of each compound, since Log KOW has been described as a good predictor of accumulation processes. Regarding the levels detected in plankton, we recorded high concentrations of HCB in phytoplankton (0.6 ± 0.5 ng g⁻¹) and of the PCB 11 congener in zooplankton (1.7 ± 1.3 ng g⁻¹), elucidating for the first time the presence of this congener in Antarctic biota and high concentrations. On the other hand, BCF and BAF estimates of OCP and PCB show a direct and significant linear relationship with Log KOW ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 5A), evidencing a trend of equilibrium or near equilibrium between water and phytoplankton and between water and zooplankton, respectively. The BAF and BCF values were in a similar range, indicating that, in this study, zooplankton did not accumulate POPs from phytoplankton grazing, in agreement with the BMF values obtained, where most of the analyzed compounds show values less than 1, indicating no or low biomagnification. According to the results, we obtained an effective and significant transfer of OCP and PCB from water to phytoplankton and from water to zooplankton, but no effective and significant transfer between phytoplankton and zooplankton.

1. Introduction

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs), such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), are a group of toxic compounds of anthropogenic origin, which were widely used in the agricultural and industrial sectors, and even in domestic activities during the third industrial revolution (Safe, 1994; Qiu et al., 2004; Jayaraj et al., 2016). Currently, POPs are internationally regulated by the Stockholm Convention of the United Nations Environment Program (UNECE, 1998; UNEP, 2001; Denison, 2013), mainly for presenting long environmental residence times (Pennington, 2001), for bioaccumulating and biomagnifying through trophic webs (Fisk et al., 2001a; 2001b; Hop et al., 2002; Borga & Di Guardo, 2005), and due their high potential for long-range transport (Blais et al., 2007; Brown & Wania, 2008). This led to a worldwide dispersion of these compounds, even reaching areas far from their primary sources, such as polar areas. In this context, it has been described that POPs can reach Antarctica mainly through long-range atmospheric transport (Blais et al., 2007; Brown & Wania, 2008; Bengtson-Nash, 2011; Jurado & Dachs, 2008), as well as through ocean currents (Bengtson-Nash et al., 2010) and migratory biota (Braune et al., 2005; Wild et al., 2022) to a considerably lesser extent. On the other hand, local sources of POPs from research stations and activities associated with tourism have been reported (Risebrough et al., 1990; Larsson et al., 1992; Hale et al., 2008; Corsolini et al., 2021), as well as a re-emission of these compounds due to glacier melting, generating a secondary source that increases POP concentrations in aquatic systems and soils, known as "snow amplification" (Casal et al., 2019).

POPs in aquatic systems follow various routes, such as volatilizing or depositing via air-water exchange (Mackay & Wania & Mackay, 1995; Kallenborn et al., 1998; Dickhut et al., 2005; Cincinelli et al., 2009; Baek et al., 2011; Cabrerizo et al., 2017; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012, 2013a, 2013c; Montone et al., 2013), biodegrade in the water column (Berrojalbiz et al., 2011; & Luarte et al., 2022), or due to their hydrophobic nature can associate with organic matter due their hydrophobicity (Swackhamer and Skoglund, 1991, 1993; Bard, 1999), such as phytoplankton. This last-named pathway is of great importance as it strongly influences the fate of POPs in different environmental matrices. First, after the consumption of phytoplankton by zooplankton, contaminants accumulate in lipid-rich organelles and tissues (Hargrave et al., 1988; Bard, 1999), resulting in the bioaccumulation

of contaminants. POPs are transferred with high efficiency between trophic levels, leading to biomagnification as the trophic level increases (Larsson et al., 2000), expressed as an increase in contaminant concentration on a lipid basis. In this context, several studies have reported the occurrence and bioconcentration for lower trophic levels, such as phytoplankton (Chiuchiolo et al., 2004 and Galbán-Malagán et al., 2013c) and zooplankton (Joiris and overlook 1991; Corsolini et al., 2003; Bengtson-Nash et al., 2008; Sanchis et al., 2015; Chiuchiolo et al., 2004; Goutte et al., 2013; Goerke et al., 2004; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2018). However, information on bioaccumulation factors (BAFs) and biomagnification factors (BMFs) in Antarctic trophic web have been limited. For example, to date, there is only one study in which an increase of these contaminants in trophic levels is reported (Goerke et al., 2004) in the Antarctic environment, indicating that trophic biomagnification occurs in the Antarctic continent effectively. In this sense, it is essential to highlight that in the Antarctic ecosystem, the krill may play an important role in the transfer of POPs linking primary productivity with higher trophic levels (Chiuchiolo et al., 2004; Corsolini et al., 2006; Bengtson-Nash et al., 2008; Goutte et al., 2013). This is because it forms an essential part of the diet of seabirds, seals, and penguins, making Antarctic krill a keystone species in the western region of the Antarctic Peninsula (Ross & Quentin, 1986; Ross et al., 1996). To date, POP concentrations in krill have been reported for some regions of the Southern Ocean (Kumar et al., 2002; Goutte et al., 2013; Bengtson-Nash et al., 2008; Corsolini, 2009; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2018), showing that POPs do bioaccumulate in these organisms and could be a route of entry for these compounds to higher trophic levels.

Secondly, the fractions of POPs absorbed by phytoplankton can be transported from the surface to the bottom by the biological pump, contributing to a permanent burial of POPs. In this context, a period characterized by massive phytoplankton blooms occurs during the summer season due to increased irradiation, reduction of the ice cover, and subsequent nutrient inputs (Smith et al., 1997; Arrigo et al., 2012). It has been reported that during periods of high primary productivity the levels of dissolved PCBs in water and phytoplankton decrease compared to non high productive periods due to biodilution (Larson et al., 2000; Berrojalbiz et al. 2009) this also is coupled to the POPs biological pump which also dominates during this periods since sequesters POPs from the upper water column lowering the concentration of POPs and enhancing the exchange between the air and water. and thus

enhancing the air-to-water fluxes. This fact was also demonstrated by previous reports from the Arctic and Antarctic ocean (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2012, 2013a and 2013y). However, these processes may be affected due to climate change and the accelerated retreat of glaciers (Turner et al., 2005; Chapman et al., 2007; Rückamp et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2017; Dryac & Enderlin, 2020). Thus assessing the concentrations of POPs present in phytoplankton is of utmost importance to elucidate the fate and environmental behavior of these compounds in the Antarctic. In this sense, Galbán-Malagón et al. (2018) estimated PCBs bioaccumulation and biomagnification factors in krill as well as biological pump sedimentation fluxes, evidencing PCB sedimentation fluxes due to the biological pump of several orders of magnitude higher than the estimated fluxes of PCBs transferred from phytoplankton to krill, thus suggesting that the biological pump dominates over the trophic transfer of POPs. However, the samples came from several sites with significant differences observed, thus introducing differences due to sample location and also all the samples were collected in open sea waters, thus presenting high geographical variability. Therefore, we believe that in order to check if the biological pump is effective, it is important to eliminate the geographical variability factor and introduce the time variable to have an idea of how this process occurs over time. Therefore, the objective of this work is to evaluate the concentrations of OCPs and PCBs present in phytoplankton and zooplankton and subsequently estimate the bioconcentration, bioaccumulation, and biomagnification factors with sampling at fixed points in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. *Phytoplankton and zooplankton sampling*

We sampled phytoplankton (n=12) and zooplankton (n=11) from November 30th, 2019 to January 30th, 2020) at Fildes Bay (“Base Escudero” 62°20’S, 58°23’W; Table S4.1, Annex C), on King George Island, South Shetlands Archipelago, Antarctica.

Water samples were obtained directly from the bay at a depth of 5 meters using a water pumping system. For each sample, a volume of approximately 200 L (see table S4.2 of Annex C for details) passed through a filter holder equipped with a GF/F filter (142 mm diameter, 0.7 µm pore size (Whatman), and then into a stainless-steel column containing XAD, where the sample was kept. This procedure was carried out at a speed of 0.4 L min⁻¹, which has been shown to prevent the breakthrough of the dissolved phase details on the water sampling are given Duarte et al., under review). Phytoplankton and zooplankton were sampled using a phytoplankton net with a 65 µm mesh size and 2 bongo nets with a 300 µm mesh size, respectively. Once transported to the laboratory, the phytoplankton biomass and zooplankton were filtered using GF-5 quartz filters (47 mm diameter, 0.7 µm pore size, Whatman). After sampling, the water, phytoplankton and zooplankton samples collected were kept at four °C and -20 °C, respectively, until their subsequent extraction and analysis.

2.2 *Chemical extraction and analysis*

Before chemical analysis samples were spiked with PCB surrogate standards (d6-γ-HCH, d8-p,p'-DDT, and ¹³CPCB105, Cambridge Isotopes, Cambridge, UK). Subsequently, water and plankton samples were extracted using a soxhlet system (Büchi System B-811 automatic extractor) for 24 hours, with hexane for the water samples in the dissolved phase (XAD), and with 150 mL of dichloromethane for the plankton samples. After extraction, the volumes of the resulting extract were reduced to 2 mL under a gentle stream of nitrogen. The cleanup was performed using a glass column containing 3 g of deactivated neutral alumina and 1 g of anhydrous sodium sulfate, where the extracts previously obtained, were eluted with a first fraction of 5 ml and a second fraction with 12 ml of dichloromethane: hexane (2:1), this last fraction, which contained the PCBs and OCPs was finally concentrated in a rotary evaporator to a volume of 1 ml; finally the sample obtained was concentrated to 100 µL in a nitrogen stream, using the solvent isooctane.

Chemical analysis of water and plankton samples was performed using a gas chromatograph (GC) (instrument 6890 GC, Agilent, USA) coupled to a mass spectrometer (MS) equipped with a 30 m by 0.25 mm i.d., DB-5 (5 % diphenyl dimethyl polysiloxane) capillary column with a film thickness of 0.25 μm . Before injection, PCB121 was added to all samples as an internal standard for proper PCB/OCP analysis. The target compounds were PCBs (PCB-9, PCB-11, PCB-28, PCB-52, PCB-101, PCB-118, PCB-138, PCB-153 and PCB-180), HCHs (α -HCH, β -HCH, and γ -HCH), DDTs: p,p' -DDE, p,p' -DDD, p,p' - DDT, o,p' -DDE, o,p' -DDD, o,p' -DDE, hexachlorobenzene (HCB), γ pentachlorobenzene (PeCB). PCBs and OCPs were quantified with an external calibration of eight points with concentration from 1 ngmL^{-1} to 1000 ngmL^{-1} and linearity was maintained in the whole range. Native PCBs and OCPs were quantified using surrogate (internal) standards (isotope-dilution method).

2.3. *Quality Assurance and Quality Control (QA/QC)*

To avoid traces of POPs, prior to sampling the GF/F and GF5 filters were packed in aluminum foil, burned at 450°C for 4 hours, and kept in sealed plastic bags. Nitrile gloves and tweezers previously cleaned with acetone were used to handle the GFF and GF5 filters.

For blank collection the GF5 filters was also used for water filtration. Subsequently, one blank per 10 samples was extracted and analyzed using the methodology described above. The recoveries ranged between 76 and 100 % for PCB/OCP. All blanks analyzed yielded levels below the detection limit for all compounds. Instrumental limits of quantification (LOQ) were calculated from the lowest calibration point as a quantity yielding signal to noise $S/N = 10$ (LOQ) (Table S4.3).

2.4 *Estimation of Bioconcentration, Bioaccumulation and Biomagnification Factors*

Bioconcentration (BCF), biomagnification (BMF) and bioaccumulation (BAF) factors were calculated using the following equations:

$$BCF = C_{phyto}/C_{TD} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

$$BAF = C_{Zoo}/C_{TD} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

$$BMF = C_{phyto}/C_{Zoo} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Where, C_{Phyto} , C_{Zoo} and C_{TD} , are the concentrations of PCBs and OCPs present in phytoplankton, zooplankton (ng g^{-1}) and water (ng L^{-1}), respectively. For purpose of the estimations we also used the concentrations reported higher than LOD as the half of the LOQ, since we are able to detect the compounds at low levels.

2.5 Statistical analysis

Log KOW has been described as a good predictor of accumulation processes (Mackay and Fraser, 2000; Voutsas et al, 2002). Therefore, to evaluate accumulation processes, a Kendall-Theil Sen Siegel nonparametric linear regression was performed between BCF, BAF and BMF and the temperature-corrected Log KOW values of each compound using Rstudio software.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Phytoplankton and zooplankton levels of target OCPs and PCBs

Target OCP levels recorded in phytoplankton in the present study were dominated by HCB ($0.6 \pm 0.5 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$) followed by PeCB ($0.4 \pm 0.3 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$), γ -HCH (0.4 ng g^{-1} , registered in a unique sample) and 4,4'-DDE ($0.29 \pm 0.08 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$). Whereas the levels of α -HCH and 4,4'-DDT recorded values below the limit of quantification (Fig. 4.1A; Table S4.6, Annex C). These levels are in the same range to those reported by other studies in different Antarctic stations (see Table 4.1). As exposed HCB contributed to 44% of the target OCP present in phytoplankton, representing the most abundant compound in all the samples analyzed (see Figure 4.1B), similarly to results from other Antarctic areas (Chiuchiolo et al., 2004; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013; Table 4.1).

The mean Σ_9 PCBs evaluated in phytoplankton was 1.1 ng g^{-1} with a range between 0.6 - 2 ng g^{-1} , where the highest concentrations were recorded for PCB 11 ($0.9 \pm 0.3 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$), followed by PCB 28 ($0.2 \pm 0.03 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$), PCBs 9 ($0.1 \pm 0.04 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$) and PCB 52 ($0.1 \pm 0.04 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$). Finally, PCBs 101, 118, 138, 153, and 180 recorded were below the limit of quantification (Fig 4.1C; Table S4.6, Annex C). The levels documented in this study are within a similar range of those published by Galbán-Malagón et al. (2013a) in the South Scotia Sea and well below those reported in Antarctic open sea areas around the Antarctic peninsula (Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013), and coastal areas Anvers Island (Chiuchiolo et al., 2004) and Livingstone Island (Casal et al., 2019, see Table 4.1). The most abundant congener recorded in phytoplankton was PCB-11, accounting for 83% of all target PCBs (Fig. 4.1D). PCB-11 was first recorded in Antarctic biota, and its levels were extremely high, not only in biota but also in other abiotic environmental matrices, such as air and water (Choi et al., 2008; Baek et al., 2011; Li et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2017; Luarte et al., 2023, chapter 2, paper under review).

Figure 4. 1. A and B. Levels of OCPs and PCBs detected in phytoplankton (ng g⁻¹), respectively; C and D. Percentage of OCPs and PCBs levels detected in phytoplankton per sample.

Table 4. 1. OCP and PCBs levels (ng g⁻¹) in phytoplankton

Sampling area	Year	HCB	α -HCH	γ -HCH	Σ HCH	PeCB	4,4'-DDE	Σ PCB	Reference
Palmer station	2002	2.9	0.45	1.24					Chiuchiolo et al., 2004
Wedell	2008-2009	1.64	0.18 (0.6-0.84)	1.81 (0.084-4.89)	2 (0.12-5.7)			14.07 (0.51-33.5)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a
Bransfielg	2008-2009	2.29	0.3 (0.08-0.608)	1.03 (0.14-4.28)	1.2 (0.16-4.5)			10.47 (0.36-58.725)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a
Bellinghausen	2008-2009	4.34	0.16 (0.008-0.439)	0.41 (0.05-0.57)	0.9 (0.09-1.34)			11.41 (0.48-24.32)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a
South Scotia Sea	2008-2009	3.68	0.34 (0.198-0.565)	0.79 (0.21-2.37)	1.4 (0.7-3.2)			2.67 (1.46-3.77)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013a
Livingston Island	2014-2015	0.3 (0.02-0.61)	0.5 (0.2-1.1)	0.6 (0.3-1.4)	1.5 (0.3-2.87)			14.5 (3.08-111.8)	Casal et al., 2019
Fildes Bay	2019-2020	0.6 (0.3-2.2)	<LOQ	0.35 (<LOQ-0.35)	0.35 (<LOQ-0.35)	0.38 (0.15-1.41)	0.29 (0.21-0.44)	1.1 (0.6-2)	This study

In zooplankton, OCP levels ranged from <LOQ to 1.5 ng g⁻¹, with the highest concentrations recorded for the γ -HCH isomer (1.15 ng g⁻¹, registered in a unique sample), followed by 4,4'-DDE (0.6 ± 0.4 ng g⁻¹), HCB (0.6±0,4 ng g⁻¹), PeCB (0.4 ± 0.3 ng g⁻¹) and below the limit of quantification for the α -HCH and 4,4'-DDT isomers (Figure 4.2A; Table S4.7, Annex C). The OCP values recorded in this study are slightly higher than other studies conducted at different Antarctic sites (Table 4.2). In this study, 4,4'-DDDT was the most abundant isomer recorded in zooplankton, representing 34% of the total target OCPs and recorded in all samples analyzed (Fig. 4.2C). To date, few studies have documented the levels of DDTs in plankton and the studies that report this compound are in low concentrations. Therefore, it is not the most abundant isomer of OCPs (Corsolini et al., 2003; 2016; Bengtson-Nash et al., 2008; Table 4.2).

On the other hand, the Σ_9 PCBs presented a range between 0.3 and 6.7 ng g⁻¹, with the highest values recorded for the congener PCB 11 (1.7 ± 1.3 ng g⁻¹) followed by PCB 28, 52, and 9 with an average of 0.9 ng g⁻¹, 0.71 ng g⁻¹ and 0.4 ng g⁻¹ (Fig. 4.2B; Table S4.7, Annex C). The PCB values are within a similar range to those reported in coastal areas from the Ross Sea (Corsolini et al., 2002; 2003 and Cincinelli et al., 2009), and lower than the levels reported by Cipro et al. (2010) and Galbán-Malagón et al. (2018) in coastal and oceanic areas in Antarctica, respectively (Table 2). Obtained results pointed to high presence of PCB-11, similarly to what was found for phytoplankton, representing 96% of the total PCBs burden (Fig. 4.2D).

Figure 4. 2. (A) Levels of OCPs detected in zooplankton (ng g⁻¹); (B) Percentage of OCPs levels in zooplankton per sample; (C) Levels of PCBs detected in zooplankton (ng g⁻¹); (D) Percentage of PCBs levels in zooplankton per sample.

Table 4. 2. OCP and PCBs levels (ng g⁻¹) in zooplankton

Sampling area	Year	HCB	α-HCH	γ-HCH	ΣHCH	PeCB	4,4'-DDE	ΣDDT	ΣPCB	Reference
Dakshin Gangotri	1987-1988				(0.141-0.15)			(0.031-0.044)	(0.15-0.16)	Gupta et al., 1995
Ross Sea	1994/95-1995/96	0.2							1.9	Corsolini et al., 2002
Ross Sea	1999-2000	0.37 (0.2-0.6)					0.01 (n.d-0.02)		1.67 (0.85-2.82)	Corsolini et al., 2003
Ross Sea	2000-2002	0.23	<MDL	0.28	0.28		0.1			Corsolini et al., 2016
Ross Sea	2001-2004							0.18	1.67	Corsolini et al., 2017
Ross Sea	2003-2004	0.02 (0.006-0.06)	0.03 (0.001-0.16)	0.04 (0.01-0.07)	0.11 (0.05-0.32)					Cincinelli et al., 2009
King George Island	2004-2006	0.06 (n.s-0.06)			0.25 (0.14-0.35)			0.41 (0.05-0.79)	12.3 (4.66-13.6)	Cipro et al., 2010
Sampling stations between 30 and 80°E	2005-2006	0.2 (0.05-0.32)	0.014 (0.0004-0.033)				0.13 (<LOQ-0.35)		0.26 (<LOQ-0.72)	Bengtson-Nash et al., 2008
Bellingshausen, South Scotia, and Weddell Seas	2008-2009								8.6 (6.9-10.3)	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2018
Fildes Bay	2019-2020	1.54 (0.12-1.54)	<LOQ	1.15 (<LOQ-1.15)		1.22 (0.07-1.22)	1.42 (0.15-1.4)		2.03 (0.28-6.67)	This study

3.2 *Bioconcentration (BCF), bioaccumulation (BAF) and biomagnification (BMF) factors*

We estimated BCF, BAF, and BMF using previously published CTD data (Table S5; Luarte et al., in review; Chapter 3), and compounds with concentrations less than half the LOQ and greater than the LOD were used (See Table S6, Annex C). The estimated accumulation factors did not show large variations throughout the sampling campaign, but a temporal trend was observed during the sampling period (see below). Regarding BCF estimation, Figure 4.3A shows that the most chlorinated PCBs (i.e., $\log KOW > 6$) were the compounds with the highest BCFs in most of the samples analyzed. A similar study by Nizzetto et al. (2012) in Lake Maggiore showed that PCBs with $\log KOW > 6.3$ had the highest BCFs after the bloom and the lowest values during the maximum phytoplankton bloom. On the other hand, our estimated BCFs of OCPs and PCBs show a direct and significant linear relationship with Log KOW ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 4.4A), evidencing a trend of equilibrium or near equilibrium between water and phytoplankton. This result agrees with that reported by Nizzetto et al. (2012) in Lake Maggiore, Italy, in which a significant linear relationship ($p < 0.05$) is observed in pre-blooms, during blooms, and post-blooms periods. However, our result differs from estimates made by Galbán-Malagón et al., 2018 in Antarctic oceanic areas. These differences observed in studies conducted in Antarctica may be due to the different biotic and abiotic variables present in marine and coastal areas. For example, coastal areas, such as Fildes Bay, are influenced by the Collins Glacier, for which a retreat associated with temperature increase due to climate change has been documented (Turner et al., 2005; Chapman et al., 2007; Rückamp et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2017; Dryac & Enderlin, 2020). Consequently, ice melt has been shown to generate an amplification of POP compounds present in water (Burniston et al., 2007; Geisz et al., 2008; Casal et al., 2019; Luarte et al., In review and Chapter 3). In addition, glacial meltwater transports micronutrients (e.g., iron) (Höfer et al., 2019; Hopwood et al., 2019) that are released into the surface waters of Fildes Bay (Krause et al., 2021), potentially triggering massive algal blooms in Antarctic coastal waters (Mitchell & Holm-Hansen, 1991; Jones et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020; Rozema et al., 2017; Brown et al. al., 2019), thus altering the biogeochemical cycle of POPs.

On the other hand, accumulation in zooplankton followed a similar temporal trend to that observed in the BCF, where PCB congeners with $\log KOW > 6$ presented the highest log BAF values (Figure 4.3B). Likewise, BAF results show a direct significant linear relationship with LogKOW values ($p < 0.05$, fig. 4.4B), indicating that OCP and PCB concentrations in zooplankton and water are close to equilibrium equilibrium equilibrium. Similar results were published by Galbán-Malagón et al. (2018), which evidenced near-equilibrium conditions for PCB partitioning between krill and water in Antarctic open ocean areas.

BAF and BCF values remained in a similar range throughout the sampling time (Figure S1, Annex C), indicating that, in this study, zooplankton did not accumulate POPs from phytoplankton grazing. This can be seen in Figure 4.3C, where most compounds show values less than 1 of log BMF, and only a few compounds with $\log KOW > 6$ exceed that value. Finally, BMF did not show a significant linear relationship with log KOW ($p > 0.05$, Fig 4.4C), possibly because BMF is not correlated with KOW. Concluding with this information, an effective and significant transfer of OCP and PCB from water to phytoplankton and from water to zooplankton.

Figure 4. 3. (A) bioconcentration (BCFs), (B) bioaccumulation (BAFs), and (C) biomagnification (BMFs) factors obtained from concentrations in, phytoplankton, zooplankton and the truly dissolved seawater (Chapter 3). Figure 4. 4. (A) Log BCF, (B) Log BAF, (C) Log BMF versus sampling time. The Log K_{OW} values are represented in color scale.

Figure 4. 5. (A) Log bioconcentration (BCFs), (B) Log bioaccumulation (BAFs), and (C) Log biomagnification (BMFs) factors obtained from concentrations in, phytoplankton, zooplankton and the truly dissolved seawater (Chapter 3).

3.3 Temporal Variation of BCFs, BAFs and BMFs

We observed a similar temporal trend in BCFs, BAFs, and BMFs, with an increase in these three variables during late December and early January and then progressively decreasing (Fig. 4.5). In order to understand these temporal variations, we evaluated the influence of chlorophyll-a concentration on the three study factors. Comparing the slopes of BCF and BAF with the amount of chlorophyll-a existing during the different sampling dates, we observed a positive and significant ($p < 0.05$) relationship between BCF slope with chlorophyll-a (Fig. 4.6A; Fig. S4.4A, Annex C). This could be explained by the local seasonal upwelling that affects the primary production and phytoplankton dynamics due the impact of local upwelling due to wind intensity and direction provoking an the mixing of the water column and the loss of water column stratification consequent renewal of surface waters. This also was pointed during similar periods on previous years that points periods of one to two days of intense upwelling events which also affects to phytoplanktonic composition (Egas et al., 2017). During our study period we found that upwelling was apparent (See Figure S4.5, Annex C). We show that the chlorophyll-a peaks occur before periods of blowing wind coming from S-SW with high mixing rates and followed by increase of chlorophyll-a and when wind blowing direction coming from N-NW we see the opposite we see water subduction and chlorophyll-a concentrations lowers in the studied area. In contrast, there is no significant relationship between slope BAF and chlorophyll-a concentration (Figure 4.7B; Figure S4.4B, Annex C). This shows that the BAF is strongly influenced by the existing phytoplankton biomass in the coastal areas, presenting an increase in log BAF slopes with increasing chlorophyll-a between December and early January and a decrease in levels with decreasing chlorophyll-a concentration in mid-January (Fig. 4.6). The observed seasonal changes in chlorophyll-a are strongly influenced by changes in wind direction and intensity, whereby low-intensity S or SE winds cause upwelling, while N and NW winds cause downwelling and sinking of chlorophyll-a (Figure S4.5), thus influencing the documented BCF values. However, this coupling between BCF and chlorophyll-a does not significantly influence the recorded BAF and BMF.

Figure 4. 6. Slope values of the linear regressions of Log BCF (A) and BAF (B) versus sampling dates and BMF values versus sampling dates (C).

Figure 4. 7. (A) Sampling time versus log BCF in blue and chlorophyll-a (mg/m3) in blue. (B) Sampling time versus log BAF in blue and chlorophyll-a (mg/m3) in blue.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we recorded the concentrations in phytoplankton and zooplankton, revealing high concentrations of HCB in phytoplankton and PCB-11 for zooplankton. PCB-11 was first recorded in the Antarctic biota, and its levels were extremely high, in agreement with the high values of this congener recorded in water. On the other hand, BCF, BAF, and BMF estimates reveal an effective and significant transfer of OCP and PCB from water to phytoplankton and from water to zooplankton, but no effective and significant transfer between phytoplankton and zooplankton, revealing low or no biomagnification of the analyzed compounds. This study highlights the differences in the concentrations of POPs in biota and the BCF, BAF, and BMF factors between oceanic and coastal zones, since in the latter, abiotic conditions, such as wind direction and speed, as well as glacier retreat, are of great importance in the levels of POPs present in water and biota, and consequently in the accumulation and biomagnification factors.

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General conclusion

This thesis contributes to knowledge of the biogeochemical cycles of POPs and, therefore, to understanding their environmental fate in polar coastal areas such as Antarctica.

First, the study evaluated historical POP concentrations in the Antarctic atmosphere. A decrease in polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) was evident between 1980 and 2018. The decrease in atmospheric levels of these pollutants is attributed to the impact of the Stockholm Convention, which restricted their use since the 1970s. However, despite the decrease, these compounds remain ubiquitous in the Antarctic atmosphere with prolonged atmospheric half-lives. These results highlight the need for continuous monitoring and the establishment of monitoring networks in Antarctica not only to track legacy POPs but also to identify new pollutants that have the potential to reach the region. Emerging compounds, such as new flame retardants, perfluoroalkylated and polyfluoroalkylated substances (PFASs), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), are of concern and should be included in monitoring efforts.

Secondly, to understand the dynamics of atmospheric and seawater levels present in the study area, the air-water diffusive exchange was estimated, where the air-sea fugacity ratios ($\log f_{w/a}-1$) of POPs in King George Island highlight the importance of biotic and abiotic factors in the biogeochemistry and environmental fate of these compounds. The deposition of some organic compounds in surface waters is likely due to biodegradation, such as HCHs, supported by the presence and activity of genes involved in enzymatic degradation. This study also reveals the influence of glacier melting on the re-emission of POPs previously trapped in ice, making Antarctica a possible secondary source of POPs during melt seasons.

Finally, to elucidate whether the levels of POPs present in seawater could bioconcentrate in phytoplankton and subsequently transfer to higher trophic levels, causing biomagnification of these compounds, POP concentrations in phytoplankton and zooplankton were recorded, elucidating high levels of HCB in phytoplankton and PCB-11 in zooplankton. In addition, an effective transfer of OCPs and PCBs from water to phytoplankton and zooplankton was evident. However, no significant transfer between

phytoplankton and zooplankton indicates low or no biomagnification of the analyzed compounds.

According to the results described in this thesis, the hypothesis that "POPs compounds, such as PCBs and OCPs, present an air-water gradient direction, predominating the atmospheric deposition process in the Southern Ocean " is accepted. The results indicate a predominance of atmospheric deposition compared to seawater concentrations for several persistent organic compounds (POPs) studied, such as HCB, α -HCH, γ -HCH, 4,4'-DDDT, 4,4'-DDE, and PCB-180. This suggests that POPs tend to be deposited from the atmosphere to the ocean in the Southern Ocean region.

For the second hypothesis formulated, which states that "The phytoplankton biological pump prevents the transfer of POPs through the food web due to higher sedimentation fluxes from the surface to the sediment during periods of high productivity," our results do not support its acceptance in a generalized manner because the compounds analyzed in this research have exhibited diverse behaviors in the water column.

First, the segmented linear regression analysis performed between $\log fw_{fa-1}$ and $\log KOW$ in Chapter 3 presents conclusive evidence, which supports that the more hydrophobic PCBs (with $\log KOW >6$), such as PCB 180, experience effective removal due to the "biological pump." This dynamic, in turn, limits their availability at higher trophic levels, which aligns with the results described in Chapter 4, where low to virtually non-existent biomagnification is documented. However, this interaction is not extensible to POPs of lower hydrophobicity ($\log KOW <6$), as they do not exhibit efficient "biological pump" mediated transport. Therefore, the applicability of this hypothesis is restricted to highly hydrophobic compounds. On the other hand, low or no biomagnification has also been observed for OCP isomers at higher trophic levels. However, as discussed in Chapter 3, this lower bioavailability of OCPs, particularly HCHs isomers, is associated more with a high rate of biological degradation mediated by specific genes (lin and lin b) than the influence of the "biological pump." Consequently, the application of the second hypothesis is rejected for these compounds since the low biomagnification is influenced to a greater extent by biodegradation processes than by sedimentation generated by the phytoplankton "biological pump."

Figure 5. 1. Graphic diagram of general conclusions

Annexes

Annex A

Supporting information to Chapter 2

Levels of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the Antarctic atmosphere over time (1988 to 2021) and estimation of their atmospheric half-lives.

This chapter has been published in *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* Luarte, T., Gómez-Aburto, V. A., Poblete-Castro, I., Castro-Nallar, E., Hunneus, N., Molina-Montenegro, M., Egas, C., Azcune, G., Pérez-Parada, A., Lohmann, R., Bohlin-Nizzetto, P., Dachs, J., Bengtson-Nash, S., Chiang, G., Pozo, K., and Galbán-Malagón, C.: Levels of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the Antarctic atmosphere over time (1980 to 2021) and estimation of their atmospheric half-lives., *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-2023-25>

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Table S2. 1. Reported atmospheric levels for the OCPs isomers reviewed.

Year	HCB	α -HCH	β -HCH	γ -HCH	4,4'-DDT	2,4'- DDT	4,4'- DDE	2,4- DDE	4,4'- DDD	2,4'- DDD	Reference
2005	-	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.29	ND	Baek et al. 2011
2006	-	2.5	0.12	1.03	ND	ND	0.4	ND	ND	ND	Baek et al. 2011
2006	-	1.98	ND	0.72	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Baek et al. 2011
2006	-	2.36	ND	0.7	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Baek et al. 2011
2007	-	1.72	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Baek et al. 2011
1990	NR	4.8	-	5	NA	-	NA	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	NR	4	-	1.7	1.1	-	0.64	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	NR	4.7	-	6	0.089	-	0.43	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	40	3.3	-	1.4	0.38	-	0.17	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	78	3.3	-	1.1	<0.2	-	0.25	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	NR	2.7	-	1.6	NA	-	NA	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	70	3.6	-	5.6	0.35	-	0.17	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	NR	4.4	-	16.9	0.58	-	0.51	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
1990	NR	6.7	-	13	0.72	-	0.54	-	-	-	Bidleman et al. 1993
2014	-	<0.13	<0.065	2.23	ND	<0.91	<0.15	ND	ND	<0.72	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.23	<0.032	2.8	<0.61	<0.91	0.44	<0.099	<0.49	<0.39	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.33	<0.059	3.15	ND	<2.73	0.15	<0.15	<0.38	<0.41	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.80	<0.37	4.34	<7.79	<0.99	<0.78	<0.51	<1.77	<1.62	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	0.93*	<0.76	2.48	<5.30	ND	<0.15	<0.15	<0.67	<0.62	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.31	<0.030	3.36	NR	NR	<0.15	ND	NR	<0.60	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.15	<0.079	<0.70	<0.67	<1.04	nd	<0.15	nd	<0.39	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.44	<0.23	2.88*	<3.44	nd	<0.15	<0.30	<0.54	<1.22	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<1.11	<0.69	1.93	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	<0.39	Bigot et al., 2016
2014	-	<0.30	<0.10	2.35	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Bigot et al., 2016
2003	-	0.21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2003	-	0.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2003	-	0.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2003	-	0.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2003	-	0.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2004	-	0.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2004	-	0.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2004	-	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2004	-	0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Cincinelli et al., 2009
2001	19.5	0.2	-	2.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	12.2	0.49	-	2.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005

Continue

2001	22.4	0.46	-	0.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	23.1	0.52	-	0.48	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	12.6	0.35	-	0.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	28.1	0.38	-	0.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	24	0.39	-	2.41	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	24.7	0.16	-	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	15.3	0.41	-	0.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	11.9	0.26	-	1.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	<5	0.28	-	2.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001	21.2	0.33	-	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2001		0.37	-	0.28	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		<0.05	-	0.91	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.39	-	0.45	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.32	-	0.45	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.24	-	2.98	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.34	-	0.31	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.19	-	<0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.1	-	0.45	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.2	-	0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.3	-	0.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.47	-	0.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.39	-	0.32	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.35	-	0.47	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.18	-	0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.31	-	<0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.24	-	0.41	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.25	-	<0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.34	-	0.43	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2002		0.32	-	0.34	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dickhut et al. 2005
2008	9.33	0.87	-	3.89	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013

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2008	13.54	5.84	-	5.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2008	2.18	0.06	-	3.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2008	3.28	0.18	-	5.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2008	5.01	1.2	-	7.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2008	15.82	2.09	-	1.47	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	2.35	0.31	-	0.54	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	30.13	0.14	-	1.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	25.98	0.05	-	0.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	3.31	0.04	-	0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	34.24	0.23	-	0.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	12.62	0.46	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	51.82	0.22	-	0.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	27.31	0.16	-	0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2009	49.71	0.1	-	0.16	-	-	-	-	-	-	Galban-Malagon et al., 2013
2010-2011	179	5	1.5	2.7	0.8	0.2	1.5	0.4	0.9	0.3	Hao et al. 2019
2011-2012	167	1.9	0.9	0.5	0.2	0.09	0.3	0.14	0.16	0.06	Hao et al. 2019
2012-2013	190	2.2	1.2	1.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.19	0.17	0.1	Hao et al. 2019
2013-2014	222	2.5	0.9	1	0.2	0.2	1	0.5	0.14	0.1	Hao et al. 2019
2014-2015	167	1.1	0.3	0.2	0.15	0.07	0.6	0.12	0.05	0.07	Hao et al. 2019
2015-2017	129	1	0.12	0.2	0.07	0.04	0.2	0.04	0.03	0.039	Hao et al. 2019
2017-2018	148	0.8	0.1	0.13	0.1	0.04	0.17	0.04	0.05	0.3	Hao et al. 2019
1994	-	2.1	-	-	0.48*	-	0.28*	<0.03	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	-	1.6	-	-	0.41*	0.19*	0.21*	<0.03	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	-	2.1	-	-	<0.08	0.17*	0.56	<0.03	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	-	2.3	-	-	0.52*	0.13*	2.6	<0.03	0.38	0.09*	Kallenborn et al., 1998

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1994	-	1.6	-		0.12 [*]	0.17 [*]	<0.2	<0.03	0.05 [*]	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	-	0.7	-		0.24 [*]	0.06 [*]	<0.2	<0.03	0.06 [*]	0.04 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	-	2	-		0.12 [*]	0.09 [*]	<0.2	<0.03	0.05 [*]	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	1.6	-		<0.08	0.06 [*]	<0.2	<0.03	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	4.6	-		1.1	0.07 [*]	0.39 [*]	0.04 [*]	0.10 [*]	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	<0.9	-		0.38 [*]	0.34 [*]	<0.2	0.9	0.57	0.73	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	4.2	-		0.48 [*]	0.49	0.29 [*]	<0.03	<0.01	0.05 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	3.7	-		0.43 [*]	0.27 [*]	0.28 [*]	0.04 [*]	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	4.6	-		0.42 [*]	0.21 [*]	0.39 [*]	<0.03	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	5.2	-		<0.08	0.25 [*]	0.40 [*]	<0.03	<0.01	0.05 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	<0.9	-		<0.08	<0.01	0.85	<0.03	0.57	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	8.4	-		<0.08	0.49	<0.2	<0.03	0.06 [*]	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	<0.93	-		<0.08	0.14 [*]	<0.2	0.02 [*]	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	3	-		0.18 [*]	0.78	0.23 [*]	0.04 [*]	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	2.5	-		0.30 [*]	0.13 [*]	0.20 [*]	<0.03	0.05 [*]	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	2.7	-		0.25 [*]	0.14 [*]	0.24 [*]	0.04 [*]	0.06 [*]	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	-	2.7	-		<0.08	<0.01	<0.2	0.03 [*]	<0.01	<0.03	Kallenborn et al., 1998
2007	19.9	0.25	-	0.2	0.15	0.07 [*]	0.2	-	0.04	0.01	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	24	0.21	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	0.42	-	0.2	0.05	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	23.9	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.16	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	20.1	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	21.6	0.27	-	<LOQ	0.05	<LOQ	0.17	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

Continue

2007	17.4	0.35	-	0.1	0.03	<LOQ	0.09	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	20	0.22	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.05	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	25.5	0.3	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	26.1	0.3	-	0.1	0.03	<LOQ	0.05	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	25.2	0.2	-	<LOQ	0.03	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	21.2	0.31	-	0.09	0.03	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	23.6	0.19	-	<LOQ	0.04	<LOQ	0.13	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	18.9	0.34	-	0.12	0.04	<LOQ	0.1	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	19	0.27	-	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.1	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	23.7	0.25	-	0.1	0.09	0.03	0.09	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	21.7	0.28	-	0.15	0.03	0.03	0.08	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	20.4	0.23	-	0.1	0.03	0.03	0.1	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	24.2	0.24	-	0.11	0.12	0.03	0.18	-	0.04	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	25.1	0.2	-	<LOQ	0.1	0.05	0.55	-	0.07	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	24.4	0.2	-	<LOQ	0.11	0.04	0.1	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	29.2	0.22	-	<LOQ	0.16	0.03	0.16	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	24.1	0.23	-	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.11	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	28.6	0.5	-	0.23	0.05	0.03	0.08	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	26.5	0.18	-	<LOQ	0.05	0.06	0.07	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	24.6	0.3	-	0.12	0.03	<LOQ	0.07	-	0.07	0.04	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	<LOQ	0.76	-	0.27	0.05	0.07	0.24	-	0.06	0.03	Kallenborn et al., 2013

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2007	24.4	0.27	-	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.1	-	0.02	0.02	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	23.9	0.34	-	0.14	0.03	0.03	0.09	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	27.6	0.25	-	<LOQ	0.03	<LOQ	0.04	-	0.02	0.02	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	27.7	0.2	-	<LOQ	0.03	<LOQ	0.14	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	30.2	0.22	-	<LOQ	0.03	<LOQ	0.14	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	30.4	0.29	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.12	-	0.03	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	29.4	0.34	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	22	0.36	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.06	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	25.1	0.29	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	12.3	0.26	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	16.7	0.24	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	9.87	0.3	-	0.13	0.09	<LOQ	0.1	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	14.6	0.21	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	18.7	0.24	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2007	16.5	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	15.6	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	13.2	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	16.5	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	11.6	0.18	-	<LOQ	0.04	<LOQ	0.03	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	17	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	14.8	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

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2008	20.2	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	13.8	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	16	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	16.4	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	19.1	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	17.7	0.21	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	20.5	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	19.5	0.2	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	18.9	0.37	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	18.7	0.44	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	18.5	0.25	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	19.5	0.22	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	22.1	0.27	-	0.11	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.06	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	25.3	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	15.9	0.24	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	18.7	0.21	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	28.7	0.21	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	27.5	0.41	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	23.7	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	23.7	0.25	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	20.5	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

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2008	24.3	0.25	-	0.1	<LOQ	0.03	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	26.5	0.13	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	22.7	0.19	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	25.7	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	22.3	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.05	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	24.8	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.05	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	26.4	0.25	-	0.22	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.06	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	25.3	0.12	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	26.7	0.14	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	25.2	0.28	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	24.7	0.25	-		<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	27.3	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	22.6	0.27	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	25.9	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	26.2	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	28.1	0.34	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	25.7	0.24	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	21	0.29	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	26.7	0.43	-	0.11	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	27.2	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	19.1	0.46	-	0.12	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	18.9	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.06	0.05	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	22.1	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

Continue

2008	21.4	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	16.1	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	28.3	0.13	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	12.4	0.14	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	14.8	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	14.2	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	12.2	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	15.9	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	13.2	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	12.4	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	14.9	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	16.4	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	21.1	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	19.1	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	20.1	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	15	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	19.4	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	30.9	0.35	-	0.09	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	24.2	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	<LOQ		-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	<LOQ		-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	<LOQ		-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	17.1	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

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2008	17.6	0.29	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	16.4	0.3	-	0.13	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	21.4	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	18.6	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	19.3	0.25	-	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	25.2	0.22	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	24.6	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	22.7	0.22	-	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	22.1	0.23	-	0.09	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	22.8	0.38	-	0.45	0.08	<LOQ	0.22	-	0.07	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	24.6	0.21	-	0.15	0.05	<LOQ	0.12	-	0.05	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	27	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	25.5	0.21	-	0.26	0.04	<LOQ	0.15	-	0.05	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	24.8	0.36	-	0.31	0.05	<LOQ	0.17	-	0.06	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	25.8	0.22	-	0.17	0.03	<LOQ	0.1	-	0.04	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	28.1	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	28.8	0.24	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	27	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	-	0.1	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	27.8	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	-	0.1	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	26.5	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	23.6	0.25	-	0.09	0.08	<LOQ	0.1	-	0.14	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	26.2	0.24	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	27.8	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

Continue

2009	29.8	0.23	-	<LOQ	0.05	<LOQ	0.1	-	0.1	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	21.4	0.24	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	22.8	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	21	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	19.8	0.19	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	16.2	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	22.3	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	18	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	15.4	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	12.3	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	12.3	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	14.9	0.14	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	11.6	0.17	-	<LOQ	0.04	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	0.06	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	12.94	0.17	-	<LOQ	0.02	0.04	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	<LOQ	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	11.8	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	15.9	0.15	-	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	0.09	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	12.7	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	16	0.22	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	18.25	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	21	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	21.5	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	19.8	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

Continue

2009	20.8	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	25.5	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	18.91	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	25.31	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	19.8	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	23.4	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	20.2	0.25	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	23.5	0.25	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	28.1	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	25.53	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	24.69	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	26.3	0.13	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	27.63	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	27.35	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	29.98	0.28	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	27.71	0.15	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	27	0.13	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	18.02	0.17	-	0.15	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	<LOQ	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	23	0.21	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	25.02	0.14	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	29.8	0.26	-	0.26	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	26.7	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.03	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013

Continue

2010	<LOQ		-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	30.2	0.14	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	30.3	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	22.3	0.36	-	0.14	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	22.6	0.23	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	31.5	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	29.8	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	23.22	0.24	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	23.84	0.2	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	25.72	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	16.6	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	20	0.17	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	16.2	0.14	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	23.5	0.16	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	29.5	0.13	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	26.9	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-	0.02	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	11.8	0.18	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.04	<LOQ	-	<LOQ	<LOQ	Kallenborn et al., 2013
1988			-	49	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	19	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	28	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	23	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992

Continue

1988			-	21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	65	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1988			-	118	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	47	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	108	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	96	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	ND	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1989			-	58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992

Continue

1990			-	72	-	-	-	-	-	-	Larson et al., 1992
1995	3.3	4.7	-	17.6	19.4	-	53.8	-	29.4	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	<0.6	14.1	-	18.4	9.7	-	8.9	-	6.8	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	9.2	14.2	-	10.1	3.6	-	7.1	-	6.1	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	8	14.2	-	13.8	5.6	-	9.8	-	4.4	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	7.3	6	-	13.4	2.4	-	4.7	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	8.8	5.9	-	12.4	<2.7	-	5.3	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	10.9	10.7	-	10.3	<2.7	-	2	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	4	3.1	-	5.6	<2.7	-	2.8	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	<0.6	2.4	-	<2.7	<2.7	-	6.1	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	11.5	7.3	-	5.1	<2.7	-	2.2	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	17.4	5.3	-	6.3	<2.7	-	<2.0	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	24.6	3.3	-	3	<2.7	-	5.2	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	25.3	3.5	-	4.6	<2.7	-	<2.0	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1995	21.9	4.5	-	<2.7	<2.7	-	2.2	-	<2.7	-	Montone et al., 2005
1997	-	0.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	0.92	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	0.49	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	0.81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	0.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	0.94	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	1.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	1.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	1.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	1.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
1997	-	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Jantunen et al., 2004
2011	23.4		-	BDL	0.04	-	BDL	-	BDL	-	Pozo et al., 2017
2011	18.4		-	BDL	0.07	-	0.1	-	BDL	-	Pozo et al., 2017
2011	30.6	0.05	-	BDL	BDL	-	BDL	-	BDL	-	Pozo et al., 2017
2011	17.1	-	-	BDL	BDL	-	BDL	-	BDL	-	Pozo et al., 2017

Continue

2011	0.8	-	-	BDL	BDL	-	BDL	-	BDL	-	Pozo et al., 2017
2011	47	-	-	BDL	0.03	-	BDL	-	BDL	-	Pozo et al., 2017
2013	0.17	1.4	2	1.6	ND	ND	0.15	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2013	0.45	4	ND	6.1	ND	ND	ND	0.028	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2013	6.4	ND ^a	ND	1.6	ND	ND	0.62	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2013	3.1	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.37	0.16	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2013	0.79	4.7	ND	6.1	0.89	ND	ND	0.062	0.069	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2013	4.4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.37	0.17	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2013	0.13	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.041	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.21	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.28	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	4.1	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.41	ND	0.59	Wu et al., 2020
2014	3.6	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	7.1	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.27	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	1.2	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.77	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	2.9	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.2	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	2.4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.88	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	1.4	ND	ND	ND	ND	3.2	1.7	0.63	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	1.2	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.5	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.42	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.036	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	2	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.27	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.46	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.081	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	4.4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	6.8	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	10	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.3	0.41	0.21	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.28	0.1	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.22	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	0.13	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020
2014	4.8	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al., 2020

NR= Not Reported

ND= Not Detected

BDL= Below Detection Level

LOQ= Limit of Quantification

Table S2. 2. Reported atmospheric levels for the 7 PCB congeners reviewed.

Year	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 118	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180	Reference
2009	0.576	1.775	-	0.082	0.281	1.359	0.187	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.29	1.325	-	0.048	0.227	1.38	0.196	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.216	0.863	-	0.02	0.126	1.119	0.153	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.238	0.672	-	0.048	0.174	1.175	0.185	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.633	1.977	-	0.124	0.609	1.27	0.215	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.315	0.494	-	0.108	0.454	1.139	0.2	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.781	2.133	-	0.405	0.881	1.211	0.188	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.281	1.29	-	0.064	0.34	0.819	0.13	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.6	1.296	-	0.339	0.581	1.107	0.221	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.133	0.88	-	0.022	0.144	0.854	0.144	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.186	0.505	-	0.034	0.212	0.729	0.143	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.224	0.534	-	0.02	0.159	0.718	0.108	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.259	0.691	-	0.058	0.359	0.783	0.142	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.144		-	0.035	0.231	0.565	0.108	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2009	0.247	3.86	-	0.036	0.262	0.628	0.129	Cabrerizo et al., 2013
2005	1.41	4.84	-	0.68	0.88	1.02	0.51	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	1.07	5.01	-	1.97	1.91	2.38	0.35	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	2.62	3.73	-	0.51	2.59	2.8	0.18	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	2.02	1.53	-	0.62	0.94	1.06	0.13	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	0.88		-	0.57	0.59	0.71	0.52	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	0.53	2.38	-	0.25	0.42	0.49	0.2	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	2.59	5.1	-	1.39	1.92	2.28	0.3	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	0.6	5.35	-	0.38	0.65	0.69	0.34	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	1.56	6.1	-	0.51	1.01	0.93	0.17	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	2.71	0.56	-	0.79	1.1	1.08	NR	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2005	1.82	0.09	-	0.58	0.56	0.56	NR	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2008	3.89	0.09	-	2.27	4.39	2.87	1.9	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2008	5.11	1.77	-	4.07	2.75	2.68	0.03	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2008	0.39	4.56	-	0.59	0.17	0.22	0.12	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013

Continue

2008	0.58	1.29	-	0.26	0.37	0.48	0.75	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2008	12.96	0.78	-	1.8	1.94	1.75	1.41	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2008	2.93	2.92	-	0.89	2.17	11.21	0.39	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	1.05	0.29	-	0.43	1.22	1.55	0.13	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	1.97	0.1	-	0.14	0.53	0.71	0.89	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	5.1	1.15	-	1.19	2.01	2.57	0.26	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	2	0.36	-	0.33	0.74	0.91	0.18	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	1.18	0.23	-	0.38	0.21	0.55	0.23	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	1.5	0.43	-	1	0.72	0.71	0.27	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	3.14	1.3	-	0.33	0.7	0.75	0.32	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	1.58	0.6	-	0.15	0.41	0.87	0.17	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	0.89	NR	-	0.17	0.23	0.45	0.04	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	0.16	NR	-	0.02	0.05	0.12	0.01	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	0.21	NR	-	0.02	0.01	0.07	0.02	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2009	0.2	NR	-	0.02	0.02	0.08	NR	Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013
2003-2004	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	Gambaro et al., 2005
2010-2011	4.7	1.1	0.3	0.14	0.3	0.5	0.1	Hao et al. 2019
2011-2012	2.3	0.5	0.3	0.17	0.2	0.3	0.07	Hao et al. 2019
2012-2013	4.4	0.69	0.3	0.2	0.16	0.21	0.05	Hao et al. 2019
2013-2014	3.3	0.4	0.3	0.13	0.12	0.14	0.03	Hao et al. 2019
2014-2015	1.3	0.3	0.3	0.14	0.2	0.2	0.05	Hao et al. 2019
2015-2017	0.7	0.15	0.07	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.02	Hao et al. 2019
2017-2018	0.5	0.11	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.01	Hao et al. 2019
1994	3.9	1.1	0.53 [*]	0.53	0.51 [*]	0.45 [*]	0.17 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	0.84 [*]	0.31 [*]	0.26 [*]	0.32 [*]	0.24 [*]	0.30 [*]	0.12 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	1.0 [*]	0.44 [*]	0.27 [*]	0.39 [*]	0.34 [*]	0.48	0.18 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	1.8 [*]	0.98 [*]	0.59 [*]	1.1	1.4	2.7	1.11	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	2.8 [*]	0.93 [*]	0.29 [*]	0.23 [*]	0.22 [*]	<0.2	0.09 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1994	<0.8	0.12 [*]	0.06 [*]	0.07 [*]	0.06 [*]	<0.2	0.03 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	1.2 [*]	0.46 [*]	0.13 [*]	0.16 [*]	<0.1	<0.2	0.09 [*]	Kallenborn et al., 1998

Continue

1995	16	9.5	3.9	0.6	0.57	0.94	0.13 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	25	13	4.5	0.95	0.83	1.2	0.2	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	15	12	5	0.79	0.63	1.1	0.06 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	22	12	4.5	0.85	0.77	1.3	0.22	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	16	8.8	3.4	0.68	0.71	0.98	0.18 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	21	13	4.8	0.79	0.79	1.4	0.22	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	24	15	5.7	0.95	1.1	1.6	0.29	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	9.4	6	2.3	0.33 ^x	0.27	0.53	0.09 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	<0.8	<0.4	3.6	0.61	1.1	1.1	0.24	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	4.7	1.1	0.26	0.12 ^x	<0.1	<0.2	0.02 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	16	9.5	3.9	0.6	0.57	0.94	0.13 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	13	7.5	2.9	0.49	0.45 ^x	0.73	0.11 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	14	8.4	3.4	0.54	0.52 ^x	0.84	3.4	Kallenborn et al., 1998
1995	7.4	4.6	1.7	0.27 ^x	0.28 ^x	0.43 ^x	0.06 ^x	Kallenborn et al., 1998
2008	0.25	-	<LOQ	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2008	0.16	-	<LOQ	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	0.13	-	0.1	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2009	0.21	-	0.07	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	0.18	-	0.07	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	0.45	-	0.24	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
2010	0.15	-	0.09	-	-	-	-	Kallenborn et al., 2013
1988	-	-	4	-	2	4	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	ND	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	14	-	14	10	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	ND	-	1	0.5	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	1	-	0.3	0.3	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	4	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	2	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	ND	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999

Continue

1988		-	1	-	0.4	0.3	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	ND	-	13	10	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	444	-	1810	1280	-	Larson et al., 1999
1988	-	-	2	-	9	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	2	-	2	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	3	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	ND	-	ND	ND	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	7	-	5	15	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	7	-	2	2	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	ND	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	4	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	1	-	ND	0	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	ND	-	ND	ND	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	2	-	1	0	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	ND	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	3	-	2	2	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	0.5	-	0.2	0.3	-	Larson et al., 1999
1989	-	-	1	-	0.3	0.4	-	Larson et al., 1999
1990	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	Larson et al., 1999
2009-2010	3.46	0.67	0.1	0.197	0.18	0.26	0.039	Li et al. 2012
2009-2010	5.53	0.62	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.009	Li et al. 2012
2009-2010	1.7	0.24	0.16	0.042	0.03	0.04	0.006	Li et al. 2012
2009-2010	5.1	0.78	0.05	0.148	0.11	0.17	0.029	Li et al. 2012
2009-2010	1.17	0.2	0.19	0.064	0.06	0.1	0.019	Li et al. 2012
2009-2010	0.57	0.068	0.086	0.034	0.032	0.028	0.01	Li et al. 2012b
2009-2010	1.08	0.056	0.14	0.026	0.048	0.04	0.008	Li et al. 2012b
2009-2010	1.1	0.13	0.32	0.024	0.03	0.032	0.01	Li et al. 2012b
2009-2010	0.28	0.21	0.084	0.036	0.036	0.04	0.012	Li et al. 2012b
1993	-	8	6.8	5.9	3.8	7.3	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001

Continue

1993	-	4.7	<4.00	2.4	<2.30	3.7	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1993	-	7.8	<4.00	3.6	<2.30	4.7	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1994	-	<4.57	<4.00	6.1	3.4	4.8	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1994	-	<4.57	<4.00	<2.40	<2.30	<3.56	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1994	-	<4.57	<4.00	<2.40	<2.30	<3.56	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1994	-	<4.57	<4.00	<2.40	<2.30	<3.56	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1994	-	<4.57	<4.00	<2.40	<2.30	<3.56	<0.64	Montone et al., 2001
1995	-	7.3	5.2	4.9	2.7	3.8	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1995	-	8.7	7.2	17	10.4	18.5	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1995	-	2.3	4	4.4	2.5	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	19.1	12	8.5	5.2	4.1	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	33.2	10.7	8.7	4.3	6.4	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	6.6	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	-4.6	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	-4.6	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	10.5	5.4	4.5	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	9	9.5	11.5	4.6	8.2	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	17	8.2	6.7	-2.3	4.5	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	-4.6	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	-4.6	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	-4.6	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	6.8	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	5.7	<4	<2.4	-2.3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1996	-	8.6	150.8	207.8		<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2003
1995	14.9	6.9	4.6	<2.4	3	<3.6	<0.6	Montone et al., 2005
1995	14.7	9.6	9.3	6	4	7.1	<0.6	Montone et al., 2005
1995	23.8	11.4	7	2.8	2.3	4.1	<0.6	Montone et al., 2005
1995	9.3	9.3	6	2.9	2.6	3.9	<0.6	Montone et al., 2005
2011	BDL	0.1	0.03	0.07	0.11	0.04	0.06	Pozo et al. 2017
2011	0.03	0.08	0.03	BDL	0.07	0.04	BDL	Pozo et al. 2017

Continue

2011	BDL	0.25	0.1	BDL	0.06	BDL	BDL	Pozo et al. 2017
2011	BDL	0.09	0.09	0.22	0.27	0.19	0.27	Pozo et al. 2017
2011	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	Pozo et al. 2017
2011	BDL	BDL	0.04	0.05	BDL	0.02	BDL	Pozo et al. 2017
2011	9.8	0.7	0.17	0.08	0.07	0.14	0.02	Wang et al., 2017
2012	2.76	0.33	0.12	0.03	0.03	0.07	0.01	Wang et al., 2017
2013	2.2	0.42	0.35	0.041	0.04	0.09	0.009	Wang et al., 2017
2014	1.42	0.18	0.13	0.025	0.03	0.05	0.007	Wang et al., 2017
2013	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2013	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2013	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2013	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2013	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2013	ND	ND	0.088	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2013	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	1.4	2.4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	1.6	1	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	0.15	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	0.14	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020

Continue

2014	ND	ND	0.12	ND	ND	0.094	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	0.12	0.34	0.2	0.3	0.27	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	0.14	ND	0.14	0.083	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.1	ND	Wu et al. 2020
2014	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.097	ND	Wu et al. 2020

NR= Not Reported

ND= Not Detected

BDL= Below Detection Level

LOQ= Limit of Quantification

Table S2. 3. Physical-chemical properties of POPs reported in the Antarctic atmosphere. Data shown are the molecular weight (MW), Henry's law constant (H), octanol-water partition coefficient (log K_{OW}), octanol-air partition coefficient (log K_{OA}) and estimated atmospheric decrementing times (T_D) and half-lives reported by other studies.

Compound	MW (g mol ⁻¹)	H (Pa m ³ mol ⁻¹ at 25°C)	log K_{OW}	log K_{OA}	T_D (Years)	Half-life (Years)
HCB	285	53 ^a	5.7 ^a	7.2 ^a	12.3	0.4 - 4.3 ^k
α-hch	291	0.74 ^b	3.8 ^d	7.5 ^b	14.3	0.06 ^k
γ-hch	291	0.31 ^b	3.6 ^e	3.8 ^b	10.1	0.006 ^m - 0.019 ^k
2,4 DDE	319	4.2	5.43 ^g	9.7	17.6	0.002 ⁿ
4,4-DDE	319	4.2 ^a	6.96 ^d	9.7 ^a	13.47	0.002 ⁿ
4,4 DDD	321	0.5 ^a	6.22 ^d	10a	12.76	0.002-0.02 ^m
2,4 DDT	354	1.1	8.3 ^h	9.6 ^j	14.4	0.002-0.02 ^m
4,4 DDT	354	1.1 ^a	6.39 ⁱ	9.8 ^a	17.2	0.002-0.02 ^m
PCB 28	257	37 ^c	5.7 ^f	7.9 ^c	3.9	0.038 - 0.08 ^k ; 0.008 ^l
PCB 52	292	31 ^c	5.9 ^f	8.2 ^c	3.7	0.06-0.16 ^k ; 0.17 ^l
PCB 101	326	43 ^c	6.3 ^f	8.2 ^c	4.7	0.16-0.32 ^k ; 0.34 ^l
PCB 118	326	37 ^c	6.7 ^f	9.4 ^c	3.6	0.16-0.32 ^k ; 0.34 ^l
PCB 138	361	45 ^c	7 ^f	9.7 ^c	6.5	0.07-0.2 ^k ; 0.68 ^l
PCB 153	361	50 ^c	6.9 ^f	10.4 ^c	7.6	0.07-0.2 ^k ; 0.68 ^l
PCB 180	395	37 ^c	7.2 ^f	10.2 ^c	4.6	1.36 ^k

References: ^aShen and Wania (2005); ^bXiao et al. (2004); ^cBamford et al. (2002); ^dHansch et al. (1995); ^eSangster (1993); ^fLi et al. (2003); ^gFinzio (1993); ^hChen et al. (1993); ⁱXiao et al. (2004); ^jShoeib & Harner (2002); ^kAtkinson (1987); ^lSinkonen & Parsivita (2000); ^mHoward (1991); ⁿKelly et al. (1994)

Table S2. 4. Results of U-Mann Whitney test performed to evaluate differences in POPs levels between East and West Antarctica.

Compound	p-value
α -HCH	2.20E-14
γ -HCH	0.4
HCB	2.80E-06
2,4'-DDT	0.01085
4,4'-DDT	3.06E-06
PCB-28	0.00003
PCB-52	0.00007
PCB-101	0.5
PCB-118	0.06
PCB-138	0.01
PCB-153	0.8
PCB-180	0.8

Table S2. 5. Results of the generalized linear model (GLM) performed to evaluate the differences between POPs levels and sampling type (active - passive) and sampling years.

Compound	Estimate		Std. Error		t-value		Pr(> t)		Degrees of freedom	
	Type of sampling	Year	Type of sampling	Year	Type of sampling	Year	Type of sampling	Year	Total	Residual
HCB	73.593	0.429	4.8644	0.8741	15.129	1.55	0.122	<2E-16	274	272
α-HCH	0.26466	0.2015	0.31841	0.01721	0.831	-11.705	0.407	<2E-16	308	306
γ-HCH	12	0.8932	34	0.1809	3.4100	-4.931	0.825	2.01E-06	159	157
4,4'-DDT	0.9211	0.1623	0.7691	0.04827	1.1980	-3.363	0.235	0.00137	60	58
2,4'-DDT	0.347485	-0.0415	0.0375	0.00339	9.2470	-12.229	0.0201	2.14E-13	33	31
PCB 28	1.908	-0.460	0.8039	0.0446	2.3740	-10.324	0.0196	2.00E-16	99	97
PCB 52	0.15494	-0.4443	0,47127	0,03672	0,329	-12,099	0.743	2.00E-16	81	79
PCB 101	-0.17331	-0.31225	0.79115	0.07183	-0.219	-7.464	0.827	1.09E-10	79	77
PCB 118	-0.05292	-0.09772	0.17731	0.02922	-3.344	-3.344	0.7662	1.32E-03	73	71
PCB 138	-0.51004	-0.11716	0.39035	0.02058	-1.307	-5.692	0.194	9.76E-08	117	115
PCB 153	-1.21889	-0.11698	0.43786	0.0224	-2.784	-5.212	0.0621	7.51E-07	127	125
PCB 180	0.2057	-0.15018	0.39893	0.02904	0.516	-5.171	0.608	1.92E-06	76	74

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Annex B

Supporting information to Chapter 3

Occurrence and diffusive air-seawater exchanges of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica.

This chapter has been submitted for publication in Science of Total Environment (Ref Number STOTEN-D-22-32446).

Luarte, T., Hirmas-Olivares, A., Höfer, J., Giesecke, R., Mestre, M., Guajardo-Leiva, S., ... & Galbán-Malagón, C. Occurrence and Diffusive Air-Seawater Exchanges of Organochlorine Pesticides (Ocps) and Polychlorinated Biphenyls (Pcbs) in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica.

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Table S3. 1. Details of distribution, temporal and volume of air samples

Sample	Sampling location		Sampling period		Volume (m ³)
	Latitude (S)	Longitude (W)	Start date	End date	
S1	-62.202325	-58.962658	30-11-19	01-12-19	999.4
S2	-62.202325	-58.962658	02-12-19	03-12-19	999.6
S3	-62.202325	-58.962658	03-12-19	04-12-19	1039.5
S4	-62.202325	-58.962658	07-12-19	08-12-19	1039
S5	-62.202325	-58.962658	11-12-19	12-12-19	1039.3
S6	-62.202325	-58.962658	14-12-19	15-12-19	1039.4
S7	-62.202325	-58.962658	18-12-19	19-12-19	1039.4
S8	-62.202325	-58.962658	19-12-19	20-12-19	1039.5
S9	-62.202325	-58.962658	23-12-19	24-12-19	1030
S10	-62.202325	-58.962658	24-12-19	25-12-19	1039.2
S11	-62.202325	-58.962658	28-12-19	29-12-19	1047.6
S12	-62.202325	-58.962658	29-12-19	30-12-19	1079.4
S13	-62.202325	-58.962658	02-01-20	03-01-20	1079.3
S14	-62.202325	-58.962658	06-01-20	07-01-20	1079.6
S15	-62.202325	-58.962658	07-01-20	08-01-20	1059.2
S16	-62.202325	-58.962658	10-01-20	11-01-20	1073.6
S17	-62.202325	-58.962658	11-01-20	12-01-20	1079.5
S18	-62.202325	-58.962658	13-01-20	14-01-20	1079.6
S19	-62.202325	-58.962658	14-01-20	15-01-20	1079.3
S20	-62.202325	-58.962658	15-01-20	16-01-20	1079.3
S21	-62.202325	-58.962658	19-01-20	20-01-20	1071.5
S22	-62.202325	-58.962658	20-01-20	21-01-20	1079.6
S23	-62.202325	-58.962658	23-01-20	24-01-20	1064.8
S24	-62.202325	-58.962658	24-01-20	25-01-20	1025.1
S25	-62.202325	-58.962658	27-01-20	28-01-20	1079.6

Table S3. 2. Details of distribution, temporal and volume of water samples

<i>Sample</i>	Sampling location		Sampling period		Volume
	<i>Latitude (S)</i>	<i>Longitude (W)</i>	<i>Start date</i>	<i>End date</i>	<i>(L)</i>
S1	-62.202325	-58.962658	03-12-19	04-12-19	209.0
S2	-62.202325	-58.962658	14-12-19	16-12-19	254.6
S3	-62.202325	-58.962658	18-12-19	20-12-19	202.7
S4	-62.202325	-58.962658	23-12-19	26-12-19	201.0
S5	-62.202325	-58.962658	29-12-19	30-12-19	200.3
S6	-62.202325	-58.962658	02-01-20	04-12-20	213.8
S7	-62.202325	-58.962658	06-01-20	09-01-20	204.4
S8	-62.202325	-58.962658	10-01-20	12-01-20	213.3
S9	-62.202325	-58.962658	14-01-20	17-01-20	190.9
S10	-62.202325	-58.962658	19-01-20	21-01-20	243.5
S11	-62.202325	-58.962658	23-01-20	25-01-20	208.7
S12	-62.202325	-58.962658	27-01-20	30-01-20	108.4

Table S3. 3. Atmospheric conditions during sampling in the study area.

Sample	Date	Wind speed			Wind direction			Air temperature		
	2019 - 2020	(m s ⁻¹) ^a			(Degrees) ^a			(^o C) ^b		
	mm/dd	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max
S1	30-11-19	7.66	0.8	20.2	232.93	1	331	-1.07	-1.9	0.1
S2	02-12-19	12.49	0.2	19.8	274.96	1	360	-1.35	-2.3	0
S3	03-12-19	10.72	0.6	19.6	110.67	1	360	-0.43	-1	0.5
S4	07-12-19	7.25	0.4	17.5	144.46	71	310	0.17	-1.4	2.1
S5	11-12-19	14.78	2.5	33.4	92.38	65	143	-2.25	-3.1	-1.3
S6	14-12-19	4.24	0.2	9.7	267.53	3	360	-0.31	-1.7	1.7
S7	18-12-19	9.05	0.4	23.7	119.09	1	360	0.23	-1	2
S8	19-12-19	21.33	5.6	31.7	89.55	52	108	0.41	-1.6	1.4
S9	23-12-19	19.92	5.6	36.9	88.78	2	114	0.56	0.8	3.2
S10	24-12-19	14.55	0.4	26.2	223.65	1	360	0.57	-1.2	3
S11	28-12-19	17.88	7.2	29.6	149.99	1	360	2.37	1.1	4.7
S12	29-12-19	12.86	4.9	25.3	145.20	1	360	2.41	0.6	5.1
S13	02-01-20	14.17	5	29.2	305.70	1	360	2.38	1.3	4.4
S14	06-01-20	14.90	5.4	23.3	311.84	1	360	2.53	1.5	4
S15	07-01-20	18.27	5.8	32.1	254.25	1	360	3.09	0.9	5.6
S16	10-01-20	5.38	1	11.5	279.73	2	360	2.55	1	4.6
S17	11-01-20	12.52	6.6	19.1	320.95	1	360	1.48	0.2	2.5
S18	13-01-20	11.00	2.1	20	275.68	217	328	1.71	0.4	2.8
S19	14-01-20	6.20	0	12.6	316.79	0	360	2.35	1.6	4
S20	15-01-20	14.57	0.6	29.2	115.55	77	356	2.08	0.1	3.4
S21	19-01-20	12.78	2.7	23.5	72.35	1	359	0.47	-1.7	2.9
S22	20-01-20	11.54	2.3	23.5	210.55	75	283	0.99	-0.5	2.7
S23	23-01-20	9.59	2.7	21	272.52	1	360	2.48	0.9	3.8
S24	24-01-20	4.70	0.4	11.5	172.26	1	360	2.71	1.5	3.8
S25	27-01-20	14.40	0.2	36.2	133.34	1	360	2.62	1.4	4.5

Table S3. 4. Mean and ranges (min-max) of the surface water temperature (SWT) in the study area.

Sample	Date	°C			K		
	mm/dd/yyyy	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max
S1	03-12-19	0.26	0.20	0.31	273.41	273.349	273.461
S2	14-12-19	0.12	0.03	0.20	273.27	273.182	273.349
S3	18-12-19	0.22	0.05	0.33	273.37	273.201	273.479
S4	23-12-19	0.34	0.16	0.55	273.49	273.313	273.7
S5	29-12-19	0.14	0.05	0.22	273.29	273.201	273.368
S6	02-01-20	0.36	0.27	0.44	273.51	273.423	273.589
S7	06-01-20	0.67	0.36	1.24	273.82	273.506	274.385
S8	10-01-20	0.95	0.91	1.04	274.10	274.057	274.194
S9	14-01-20	0.95	0.83	1.13	274.10	273.975	274.276
S10	19-01-20	1.36	1.18	1.53	274.51	274.33	274.684
S11	23-01-20	1.07	0.96	1.21	274.22	274.112	274.358
S12	27-01-20	1.04	0.99	1.10	274.19	274.139	274.249

Table S3. 5. Physical-chemical properties of objective POPs. Data shown are the molecular weight (MW), Henry's law constant (H), octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log K_{OW}$), octanol-air partition coefficient ($\log K_{OA}$), half-life in water ($t_{1/2-w}$), atmospheric half-life in Antarctica ($t_{1/2-air}$) and the enthalpy of phase change for each POP (ΔU_{AW}).

Compound	MW	H	$\log K_{OW}$	$\log K_{OA}$	$t_{1/2-water}$	$t_{1/2-air}$	DU_{AW}
	(g mol ⁻¹)	(Pa m ³ mol ⁻¹ at 25°C)			(days)	(days)	(KJ mol ⁻¹)
HCB	285	53 ^a	5.7 ^d	7.2 ^a	969 ^h	5110 ^l	51 ^a
α -HCH	291	0.74 ^b	3.8 ^d	7.5 ^b	140 ⁱ	5219 ^l	57 ^b
γ -HCH	291	0.31 ^b	3.6 ^e	3.8 ^b	708 ⁱ	3686 ^l	57 ^b
4,4'-DDT	354	1.1 ^a	5.65 ^d	9.7 ^a		6278 ^l	68 ^b
4,4'-DDE	319	4.2 ^a	5.43 ^d	9.7 ^a			66 ^b
PECB	250	74 ^a	5.2 ^e	6.7 ^a			57 ^b
PCB-28	257	37 ^e	5.7 ^f	7.9 ^f	60 ⁱ	1423 ^l	33 ^c
PCB-52	292	31 ^e	5.9 ^f	8.2 ^f	1250 ^k	1350 ^l	31 ^c
PCB-101	326	43 ^e	6.3 ^f	8.2 ^f	2500 ^k	1715 ^l	30 ^c
PCB-118	326	37 ^e	6.7 ^f	9.4 ^f	2500 ^k	1314 ^l	50 ^c
PCB-138	360	45 ^c	7.2 ^f	9.7	5000	2372 ^l	
PCB-153	361	54 ^e	6.9 ^f	9.4 ^f	5125 ^k	2774 ^l	66 ^c
PCB-180	395	37 ^e	7.2 ^f	10.2 ^f	10000 ^k	1679 ^l	144 ^c

^aShen and Wania (2005); ^bXiao et al. (2004); ^cBamford et al. (2002); ^dHansch et al. (1995); ^eSangster (1993); ^fLi et al. (2003); ^gMakino (1998); ^hBeck and Hansen (1974), ⁱMackay (2001); ^jWöhrnschimmel et al. (2012); ^kSinkkonen and Passivirta (2000), ^lLuarte et al. (2023)

Text S1. Octanol-water partition coefficient (KOW) temperature-corrected using enthalpy of phase change

To adjust the octane-water partition coefficient (KOW) to the surface water temperature (SWT), we use the following equation (1):

$$\frac{KOW_{T_0}}{KOW_{T_{298.15}}} = e^{\left[\frac{-\Delta U_{AW}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{298.15}\right)\right]} \quad (\text{Eq. S1})$$

where K_{OWT_0} is the octanol-water partition coefficient at water surface temperature (K) in Fildes Bay, Antarctica (Table S4) and $K_{OWT_{298.15}}$ K_{OWT_0} is the octanol-water partition coefficient at 298.15 K (Table S5), respectively. The ΔU_{OW} is the enthalpy of phase change (KJ mol^{-1}) used for the temperature correction for each POP.

Text S2. Henry's law constant temperature-corrected using enthalpy of phase change.

To adjust the dimensionless Henry's law (H') for the surface water temperature (SWT), we use the following equation (2):

$$\frac{H_{T_0}}{H_{T_{298.15}}} = e^{\left[\frac{-\Delta U_{AW}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{298.15}\right)\right]} \quad (\text{Eq. S2})$$

where H_{T_0} is the Henry's law constants at water surface temperature (K) in Fildes Bay, Antarctica (Table S4), $H_{T_{298.15}}$ the Henry's law constant at 298.15 K (Table S5), respectively, ΔU_{AW} is the enthalpy of phase change (KJ mol^{-1}).

Text S3. Mapping of *linA* and *linB* genes in metatranscriptomics data

S3.1 Details in metatranscriptomic samples collection and sequencing

Seawater samples were collected between the 29th of November 2021 to the 8th of January at Maxwell-Fildes Bay, in King George Island (South Shetland Islands), Antarctica. 30 L of seawater were taken at 5m depth by means of GoFlo bottle and prefiltered through a 200 µm pore-size mesh. Samples were immediately transported to the wet lab in Escudero Station where 20-30 L of seawater were quickly (< 30 min) filtered through a 142mm diameter filter with a 0.2µm pore-size using a peristaltic pump. Then, filters were immediately placed inside 15 mL centrifuge tubes and stored at -80°C with 1 mL of RNA-Later. After the Antarctic expedition, samples were transported to a molecular lab, without breaking the cold chain. Once in the molecular lab, RNA was extracted following the following method

Filters were prepared for digestion. Filters were thawed carefully in cold conditions and 3 mL of sterile 1x PBS were added to dilute the salts of the RNA-Later, while gently rotating the tube to help the filter soak. Each sample was divided in two parts: the liquid inside the tube was transferred to a new 15 mL centrifuge tube, and the filter was transferred to a Petri dish. The liquid within the new 15 mL tube was centrifuged for 20 minutes at 5000 x g (room temperature) thus separating the RNA-Later salts from the sample. The formed pellet was recovered by resuspending it with Trizol reagent (TRIzol™, Invitrogen). Filter in petri dish was cut into small pieces using a sterile blade and the pieces were separated equitatively into two 15 mL falcon tubes. In each falcon with filter pieces, 4 mL of Trizol and 1 g of glass beads (sterile and RNAses-free) were added to each falcon. The 4 mL of Trizol included the volume used to resuspend the pellet.

To help the digestion of the sample by Trizol, the mix was incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature. Then, the tubes were shaken with a vortex (3 pulses of 30 seconds) to help the physical lysis of the cells. 0.8 ml of chloroform were added, and then tubes were capped and shaken to mix before incubating them at room temperature for 2-3 minutes. Then samples were centrifuged for 25 minutes at 5000 x g (4°C). Aqueous phase (upper part) contained the RNA (the sample) and was then transferred to a new tube.

For sample purification, the RNA Clean & Concentrator™-5 kit was used: 2 mL of ethanol (95%) was added to the sample, and sample was transferred to a Zymo-Spin IC Column (RNA Clean & Concentrator™-5 kit, Zymo research) with the collection tube incorporated.

Sample was centrifuged 45 seconds at 12500 x g. Eluate was discarded. 400 µl of RNA Prep Buffer were added and column was centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 45 seconds. Eluate was discarded. 700 µl of RNA Wash Buffer were added and the column was centrifuged again at 12500 x g for 45 seconds. Eluate was discarded. Column was transferred carefully to a RNase-free tube. 50 µL of DNase/RNase-Free water were added to the column, and column was centrifuged at 12500 x g for 1 minute. The eluate was recovered, as contains the RNA.

S3.2 Bioinformatic procedure

To determine the activity of *linA* and *linB* genes, we aligned metatranscriptomic reads against a bacterial database of 95 Gamma-hexachlorocyclohexane dehydrochlorinase and Haloalkane dehalogenase aminoacidic sequences obtained from the NCBI protein database. A total of 13 metatranscriptomes and two biological replicates of each one was used in this analysis. Quality filtered metatranscritomic reads were translated in the six open reading frames and aligned against the *linA* and *linB* database using Diamond (blastx -ultra-sensitive -e 0.00001; Buchfink et al., 2015). Subsequently, the number of reads aligned against each database were normalized by the total number of reads in each metatranscriptome using counts per million (CPM). The resulting count table was used to build a heat map, where samples were clustered according to the abundance of *linA* and *linB* transcripts by hierarchical clustering using the ComplexHeatmap (Gu et al., 2016; Gu, 2022) package in R.

Table S3. 6. Blank concentrations (pg sample⁻¹)

Compound	Air						Water			
	PUF Blanks	PUF Blanks	Solvent Blank - Soxtek	Solvent Blank - Soxtek	Solvent Blank - k XAD	Solvent Blank - k XAD				
HCB	0.234	1.43	<0,0160	0.0240	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	0.0221	0.0290	0.0312
α-HCH	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270
γ-HCH	<0,0450	0.190	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450
4,4'-DDT	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660
4,4'-DDE	0.0846	0.0646	0.0450	0.0419	0.0259	0.0253	0.0419	0.0463	0.0641	0.0380
PECB	0.326	5.38	0.0130	0.0119	0.0129	0.0123	0.0136	0.0119	0.0199	0.0277
PCB 9	<0,0100	0.0271	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100
PCB 11	0.274	1.21	0.0748	0.0612	0.0338	0.0396	0.0237	0.0853	0.0622	0.117
PCB 28	<0,0160	0.130	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160
PCB 52	<0,0150	0.0724	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150
PCB 101	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300
PCB 118	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270
PCB 138	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340
PCB 153	0.0320	0.0299	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290
PCB 180	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230

Table S3. 7. Air concentrations of POPs (gas phase, pg m⁻³).

Sample	HCB	α -HCH	β -HCH	γ -HCH	δ -HCH	ε -HCH	4,4'DDT	2,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDD	2,4'-DDD	4,4'-DDE	2,4'DDE	PECB
S1	35.52	0.12	<LOQ	0.43	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.13	<LOQ	7.99
S2	39.12	0.11	<LOQ	0.46	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.11	<LOQ	8.7
S3	35.59	0.08	<LOQ	0.32	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	8.79
S4	38.02	0.09	<LOQ	0.39	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.12	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.12	<LOQ	7.57
S5	41.76	0.13	<LOQ	3.41	<LOQ	<LOQ	2.8	2.74	0.38	0.21	3.36	0.43	8.81
S6	39.35	0.11	<LOQ	0.56	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.96	0.27	0.1	<LOQ	0.28	0.02	9.01
S7	38.58	0.08	<LOQ	0.39	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	8
S8	38.77	0.09	<LOQ	0.57	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	7.79
S9	41.65	0.11	<LOQ	0.57	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	<LOQ	8.06
S10	37.34	0.12	<LOQ	0.5	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.12	<LOQ	7.1
S11	37.13	0.16	<LOQ	0.67	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.14	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.13	<LOQ	5.89
S12	37.43	0.12	<LOQ	0.46	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.11	<LOQ	6.11
S13	38.73	0.15	<LOQ	0.64	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.13	<LOQ	5.99
S14	40.29	0.16	<LOQ	0.63	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	5.63
S15	39.94	0.11	<LOQ	0.31	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	7.23
S16	42.29	0.17	<LOQ	0.48	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	5.89
S17	39	0.15	<LOQ	0.73	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	0.06	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	<LOQ	6.17
S18	37.88	0.13	<LOQ	0.38	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	5.72
S19	41.14	0.14	<LOQ	0.62	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.06	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	7.03
S20	37.34	0.09	<LOQ	0.34	<LOQ	<LOQ	BDL	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	7.03
S21	34.53	0.09	<LOQ	0.4	<LOQ	<LOQ	BDL	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	7.18
S22	39.83	0.1	<LOQ	0.31	<LOQ	<LOQ	BDL	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	7.4
S23	41.98	0.15	<LOQ	0.57	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	<LOQ	7.58
S24	42.04	0.16	<LOQ	0.57	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08	<LOQ	7.19
S25	39.55	0.13	<LOQ	0.54	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.1	<LOQ	6.89

Continue

Sample	PCB 9	PCB 11	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 118	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180
S1	0.07	1.58	0.16	0.12	0.06	BDL	0.06	0.1	0.03
S2	0.08	2.21	0.26	0.2	0.09	0.03	0.07	0.1	0.03
S3	0.09	1.13	0.12	0.09	0.05	BDL	0.06	0.08	0.02
S4	0.11	1.99	0.22	0.13	0.05	BDL	0.07	0.09	0.03
S5	0.37	20.69	3.24	2.66	1.19	0.44	0.7	1.18	0.21
S6	0.12	2.52	0.28	0.24	0.13	0.08	0.1	0.14	0.06
S7	0.06	1.74	0.19	0.12	0.05	BDL	0.05	0.07	0.03
S8	0.1	2.16	0.34	0.21	0.09	BDL	0.05	0.1	0.03
S9	0.08	2.97	0.53	0.5	0.21	0.06	0.08	0.13	0.04
S10	0.08	2.24	0.34	0.29	0.19	0.05	0.08	0.12	0.04
S11	0.1	3.54	0.54	0.5	0.26	0.08	0.11	0.17	0.04
S12	0.12	2.46	0.32	0.22	0.16	0.06	0.07	0.12	0.04
S13	0.1	3.14	0.45	0.44	0.18	0.04	0.07	0.11	0.03
S14	0.07	3.57	0.38	0.44	0.24	0.09	0.12	0.19	0.05
S15	0.04	1.27	0.13	0.11	0.09	0.03	0.06	0.08	0.03
S16	0.06	1.94	0.24	0.22	0.19	0.08	0.11	0.19	0.07
S17	0.11	3.75	0.57	0.7	0.32	0.09	0.09	0.17	0.05
S18	0.08	1.77	0.2	0.21	0.19	0.09	0.09	0.14	0.04
S19	0.07	2.84	0.48	0.43	0.17	0.06	0.06	0.1	0.04
S20	0.06	3.84	0.14	0.09	0.07	<LOQ	0.04	0.07	0.02
S21	0.08	2.47	0.32	0.24	0.07	0.03	<LOQ	0.05	<LOQ
S22	0.05	1.08	0.14	0.09	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.03
S23	0.13	3.35	0.48	0.43	0.2	0.07	0.09	0.14	0.05
S24	0.15	2.32	0.53	0.29	0.13	0.06	0.08	0.11	0.04
S25	0.11	2.38	0.3	0.16	0.07	0.03	0.05	0.07	0.04

Table S3. 8. Water concentrations of POPs (reported as freely dissolved phase, $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

Sample	HCB	α -HCH	β -HCH	γ -HCH	δ -HCH	ϵ -HCH	4,4'-DDT	2,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDD	2,4'-DDD	4,4'-DDE	2,4'-DDE	PECB
S1	0.95	0.23	<LOQ	0.62	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.26	<LOQ	0.78
S2	1.67	0.54	<LOQ	1.23	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.35	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.44	<LOQ	1.45
S3	6.36	1.35	<LOQ	3.25	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.73	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.72	<LOQ	5.48
S4	5.82	1.06	<LOQ	2.84	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.88	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.64	<LOQ	5.82
S5	5.89	<LOQ	<LOQ	2.88	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.68	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.61	<LOQ	6.84
S6	6.88	1.00	<LOQ	2.20	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.53	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.54	<LOQ	8.33
S7	1.34	0.35	<LOQ	0.95	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.32	<LOQ	1.24
S8	1.22	0.39	<LOQ	0.70	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.29	<LOQ	1.04
S9	1.50	0.53	<LOQ	0.82	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.28	<LOQ	1.02
S10	0.92	0.25	<LOQ	0.22	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.20	<LOQ	1.32
S11	2.64	0.52	<LOQ	0.69	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.37	<LOQ	1.38
S12	2.73	0.77	<LOQ	1.57	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.55	<LOQ	2.45

Continue

PCB 9	PCB 11	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 118	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180
0.36	0.86	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
0.68	1.32	<LOQ	0.52	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.19	<LOQ
2.77	3.74	0.90	0.52	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.18	<LOQ
2.47	2.71	0.70	0.20	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
2.79	3.73	0.53	0.23	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.15	<LOQ
2.47	3.39	<LOQ	0.17	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
0.57	1.46	<LOQ	0.09	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
0.55	1.42	<LOQ	0.10	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
0.76	1.12	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
0.21	0.61	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
0.90	1.33	<LOQ	0.10	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
1.24	2.07	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ

Table S3. 9. Estimated biological degradation fluxes for OCs and PCBs $\text{ng m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$

Compound	Biodegradation
HCB	2.82
a-HCH	5.91
g-HCH	2.53
4,4'-DDT	0.31
4,4'-DDE	0.45
PECB	3.89
PCB 28	2.58
PCB 52	0.10
PCB 153	0.01

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Annex C

Supporting information to Chapter 4

Levels of Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and Organochlorine Pesticides (OCPs) in phytoplankton and zooplankton and estimation of bioconcentration, bioaccumulation and biomagnification factors in Fildes Bay, Antarctica.

This chapter is under preparation for submission to Environmental Pollution

Luarte, T., Hirmas-Olivares, A., Höfer, J., Giesecke, R., Chiang, G., Gómez, V., Pozo, K., Pybrilova, P., Martinik, J and Galbán-Malagón, C. Levels of Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and Organochlorine Pesticides (OCPs) in phytoplankton and zooplankton and estimation of bioconcentration, bioaccumulation and biomagnification factors in Fildes Bay, Antarctica.

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Text S1. Estimation of Concentration Truly Dissolved (C_{TD})

The methodology used in previous studies (Totten et al., 2001; Rowe et al., 2007; García-Flores et al., 2005; Nizzetto et al. al., 2011; Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b; Luarte et al., 2022) was used to estimate the concentration truly dissolved (CTD) in water, with equation (1):

$$C_{TD} = \frac{C_W}{1+10^{-9} \cdot K_{OW} DOC} \quad (1)$$

Where C_W is the POP concentration measured in water ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and K_{OW} is the octanol-water partition constant, dissolved organic carbon (DOC) in mg L^{-1} and the octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{OW}) corrected for temperature (see text S1; García-Flores et al., 2005). For DOC we used a concentration of 0.7 mg L^{-1} , following previous studies in the same area (e.g. Doval et al., 2002 and Galbán-Malagón et al., 2013b), the 10^{-9} correction factor is for transforming units from mg to μg . When concentrations were over LOD and below LOQ we divided the value of LOQ by 2 to estimate the fugacity gradient.

Table S.4 1. Details of distribution, temporal and volume of water samples

<i>Sample</i>	Sampling location		Sampling period		Volume
	<i>Latitude (S)</i>	<i>Longitude (W)</i>	<i>Start date</i>	<i>End date</i>	<i>(L)</i>
S1	-62.202325	-58.962658	03-12-19	04-12-19	209.0
S2	-62.202325	-58.962658	14-12-19	16-12-19	254.6
S3	-62.202325	-58.962658	18-12-19	20-12-19	202.7
S4	-62.202325	-58.962658	23-12-19	26-12-19	201.0
S5	-62.202325	-58.962658	29-12-19	30-12-19	200.3
S6	-62.202325	-58.962658	02-01-20	04-12-20	213.8
S7	-62.202325	-58.962658	06-01-20	09-01-20	204.4
S8	-62.202325	-58.962658	10-01-20	12-01-20	213.3
S9	-62.202325	-58.962658	14-01-20	17-01-20	190.9
S10	-62.202325	-58.962658	19-01-20	21-01-20	243.5
S11	-62.202325	-58.962658	23-01-20	25-01-20	208.7
S12	-62.202325	-58.962658	27-01-20	30-01-20	108.4

Table S.4 2. Details of temporal of plankton samples

Phytoplankton		Zooplankton	
Sample	Date	Sample	Date
S1	02-12-19	S1	02-12-19
S2	06-12-19		
S3	11-12-19	S2	11-12-19
S4	16-12-19	S3	16-12-19
S5	21-12-19	S4	21-12-19
S6	27-12-19	S5	27-12-19
S7	03-01-20	S6	03-01-20
S8	08-01-20	S7	08-01-20
S9	13-01-20	S8	13-01-20
S10	17-01-20	S9	17-01-20
S11	22-01-20	S10	22-01-20
S12	27-01-20	S11	27-01-20

Table S.4 3. Blank concentrations (pg sample⁻¹)

Compound	Water				Zooplankton							
	Solvent Blank - Soxtek	Solvent Blank - Soxtek	Solvent Blank - k XAD	Solvent Blank - k XAD	Trip Blank	Trip Blank	Trip Blank	Solvent Blank	Solvent Blank	Solvent Blank	Solvent Blank	
HCB	<0,0160	0.0221	0.029	0.0312	<0,0160	<0,0160	0.0209	<0,0160	0.0206	0.0221	0.0217	
α-HCH	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	
γ-HCH	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	<0,0450	
4,4'-DDT	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	<0,0660	
4,4'-DDE	0.0419	0.0463	0.0641	0.038	0.0502	0.0364	0.0328	0.0738	0.0508	0.0633	0.0493	
PCB	0.0136	0.0119	0.0199	0.0277	0.0129	0.0137	0.0162	0.0125	0.0127	0.0183	0.0128	
PCB 9	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	<0,0100	
PCB 11	0.0237	0.0853	0.0622	0.117	0.0505	0.0743	0.0669	0.0308	0.0451	0.0601	0.0391	
PCB 28	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	<0,0160	
PCB 52	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	<0,0150	
PCB 101	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	<0,0300	
PCB 118	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	<0,0270	
PCB 138	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	<0,0340	
PCB 153	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	<0,0290	
PCB 180	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	<0,0230	

Table S.4 4. Physical-chemical properties of objective POPs. Data shown are the molecular weight (MW), Henry's law constant (H), octanol-water partition coefficient (log K_{OW}).

Compound	MW (g mol ⁻¹)	H (Pa m ³ mol ⁻¹ at 25°C)	log K _{OW}
HCB	285	53 ^a	5.7 ^d
α-HCH	291	0.74 ^b	3.8 ^d
γ-HCH	291	0.31 ^b	3.6 ^e
4,4'-DDT	354	1.1 ^a	5.65 ^d
4,4'-DDE	319	4.2 ^a	5.43 ^d
PECB	250	74 ^a	5.2 ^e
PCB-28	257	37 ^c	5.7 ^f
PCB-52	292	31 ^c	5.9 ^f
PCB-101	326	43 ^c	6.3 ^f
PCB-118	326	37 ^c	6.7 ^f
PCB-138	360	45 ^c	7.2 ^f
PCB-153	361	54 ^c	6.9 ^f
PCB-180	395	37 ^c	7.2 ^f

^aShen and Wania (2005); ^bXiao et al. (2004); ^cBamford et al. (2002); ^dHansch et al. (1995);
^eSangster (1993); ^fLi et al. (2003)

Table S.4 5. Concentrations truly dissolved (CTD) of OCPs and PCBs recorded in water (ng L⁻¹)

Sample	HCB	A_HCH	G_HCH	PP_DDT	PP_DDE	PECB	PCB 9	PCB 11	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 118	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180
S1	0.00026	0.00010	0.00029	0.00004	0.00008	0.00024	0.00011	0.00027	0.00001	0.00001	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S2	0.00046	0.00024	0.00058	0.00010	0.00013	0.00045	0.00021	0.00041	0.00001	0.00014	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00004	0.00001
S3	0.00177	0.00060	0.00153	0.00021	0.00021	0.00169	0.00086	0.00115	0.00025	0.00014	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00004	0.00001
S4	0.00162	0.00047	0.00134	0.00025	0.00019	0.00179	0.00076	0.00084	0.00019	0.00005	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S5	0.00164	0.00047	0.00136	0.00019	0.00018	0.00211	0.00086	0.00115	0.00015	0.00006	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00003	0.00001
S6	0.00191	0.00044	0.00103	0.00015	0.00016	0.00257	0.00076	0.00105	0.00001	0.00005	0.00002	0.00001	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S7	0.00037	0.00016	0.00045	0.00005	0.00009	0.00038	0.00018	0.00045	0.00001	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S8	0.00034	0.00017	0.00033	0.00004	0.00009	0.00032	0.00017	0.00044	0.00001	0.00003	0.00002	0.00001	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S9	0.00042	0.00023	0.00038	0.00005	0.00008	0.00031	0.00023	0.00034	0.00001	0.00001	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S10	0.00026	0.00011	0.00010	0.00004	0.00006	0.00041	0.00007	0.00019	0.00001	0.00001	0.00002	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001
S11	0.00073	0.00023	0.00033	0.00004	0.00011	0.00042	0.00028	0.00041	0.00001	0.00001	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00002	0.00001
S12	0.00076	0.00034	0.00073	0.00009	0.00016	0.00075	0.00038	0.00063	0.00002	0.00002	0.00003	0.00003	0.00003	0.00003	0.00002

Table S.4 6. Concentrations of OCPs and PCBs detected in phytoplankton (ng g⁻¹)

Sample	HCB	α -HCH	γ -HCH	4,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDE	PECB	PCB 9	PCB 11	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180	Σ PCBs
S1	0.52	<LOQ	0.35	<LOQ	0.38	0.32	0.07	0.90	0.15	0.12	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.24
S2	0.33	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.24	0.16	0.07	0.77	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.84
S3	0.50	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.23	0.29	0.08	0.84	0.16	0.18	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.26
S4	1.10	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.25	0.41	<LOQ	0.63	<LOQ	0.11	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.74
S5	2.18	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.21	1.41	0.05	0.64	<LOQ	0.13	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.83
S6	0.35	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.29	0.22	0.18	1.13	<LOQ	0.12	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.43
S7	0.33	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.26	0.21	0.14	1.44	0.19	0.20	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.97
S8	0.32	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.42	0.25	0.09	1.15	0.18	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.43
S9	0.51	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.44	0.61	0.14	1.25	0.24	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.63
S10	0.43	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.26	0.31	<LOQ	0.88	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.88
S11	0.32	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.25	0.15	<LOQ	0.57	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.57
S12	0.41	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.30	0.21	<LOQ	0.84	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.84

Table S.4 7. Concentrations of OCPs and PCBs detected in zooplankton (ng g⁻¹)

Sample	HCB	α-HCH	γ-HCH	4,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDE	PeCB	PCB 9	PCB 11	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180	ΣPCBs
S1	0.98	<LOQ	1.15	<LOQ	0.74	0.51	0.77	4.30	0.90	0.71	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	6.67
S2	0.22	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.16	0.09	<LOQ	0.32	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.32
S3	0.12	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.15	0.07	<LOQ	0.28	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.28
S4	0.29	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.42	0.17	<LOQ	1.05	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.05
S5	0.35	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.58	0.40	<LOQ	1.40	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.40
S6	0.25	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.30	0.14	0.10	0.94	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.04
S7	0.65	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.77	0.45	<LOQ	2.09	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	2.09
S8	0.87	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.42	0.44	<LOQ	3.60	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	3.60
S9	0.70	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.01	0.57	<LOQ	2.31	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	2.31
S10	1.54	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.76	1.22	<LOQ	1.48	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.48
S11	0.18	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.30	0.15	<LOQ	0.81	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.81

Figure S.4 1. Log BCF and Log BAF estimated over the sampling season.

Figure S.4 2. Estimated Log BCF versus Log K_{OW} per sample

Figure S.4 3. Estimated Log BAF versus Log K_{ow} per sample

Figure S.4 4. Nonparametric linear regression results between A) log BCF slope versus chlorophyll a (mg m⁻³) and B) log BAF slope versus chlorophyll a (mg m⁻³).

Figure S.4 5. Chlorophyll a, windspeed and wind direction during the sampling season.

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Annex D

Other contribution to science development in the research field conducted by the author of the present PhD Thesis

List of publications:

Wilkinson, J. L., Boxall, A. B., Kolpin, D. W., Leung, K. M., Lai, R. W., Galbán-Malagón, C., ...**Luarte, T.**,... & Teta, C. (2022). Pharmaceutical pollution of the world's rivers. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(8), e2113947119.

Tucca, F., **Luarte, T.**, Nimptsch, J., Woelfl, S., Pozo, K., Casas, G., ... & Galbán-Malagón, C. (2020). Sources and diffusive air–water exchange of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in an oligotrophic North–Patagonian lake. *Science of the Total Environment*, 738, 139838.

Luarte, T., Tucca, F., Nimptsch, J., Woelfl, S., Casas, G., Dachs, J., ... & Galbán-Malagón, C. (2022). Occurrence and air-water diffusive exchange legacy persistent organic pollutants in an oligotrophic north Patagonian lake. *Environmental Research*, 204, 112042.

Galbán-Malagón, C., Zapata, J., Perez-Venegas, D.J., Vargas, R., Latorre-Padilla, N., **Luarte, C.**, Ahrendt, C., Hirmas-Olivares, A., Gómez-Aburto., V., Tapia, P., Isamit, P., Arce, P., Sánchez, C., and Pozo, K. (2023). Occurrence, source estimation, and risk assessment of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in coastal seawaters from the Quintero Industrial Complex (Valparaíso, Chile). *Science of The Total Environment*, 878, 162957.

Congresses:

Participation in the marine science congress 2023, poster session. "Occurrence and diffusive air-seawater exchanges of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in Fildes Bay, King George Island, Antarctica" (Chapter 3).